

INCENTIVE
CITIZEN SCIENCE HUBS

D1.3

Requirements and motivations of quadruple helix stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science

White Research

July, 2021

The INCENTIVE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101005330

PROJECT INFORMATION

TITLE	INCENTIVE – Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society.
START DATE	1 February 2021
DURATION	36 months
WEBSITE	www.incentive-project.eu
COORDINATOR	Universiteit Twente (DesignLab) (NL)
PROJECT OVERVIEW	INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs in four EU Universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

LEGAL NOTICE

The information and views set out in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

© INCENTIVE Consortium, 2021-2023

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Grant Agreement: 101005330 | Coordination and Support Action | 2021 – 2023 | Duration: 36 months

Topic: SwafS-23-2020 - Grounding RRI in society with a focus on citizen science

D1.3: Requirements and motivations of quadruple helix stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science Hubs

Issued by: White Research SRL
 Issue date: 26/07/2021
 Due date: 31/07/2021
 Work Package Leader: Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public	x
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

VERSION CONTROL SHEET

Version	Date	Main modifications	Organisation
1.0	09/07/2021	Draft version	WR
2.0	21/07/2021	Comments from AUTH and SDA Bocconi	WR
3.0	26/07/2021	Final version	WR

MAIN AUTHORS

Name	Organisation
PSALTOGLOU Artemis, BAKRATSAS Thomas	WR
STYLIANIDIS Efstratios	AUTH
WILDEVUUR Sabine	UT
ARIÑO VILA Xavier, MIÑARRO VIVAS Begoña	UAB
SKARZAUSKIENE Aelita, MACIULIENE Monika	VGTU
TRENDAFILI Kevin, POLITIS Christos	Q-PLAN

QUALITY REVIEWERS

Name	Organisation
STYLIANIDIS Efstratios, KARATZAS Konstantinos	AUTH
NASI Greta, NOVARO Riccardo	SDA Bocconi

Table of Contents

1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
2.	INTRODUCTION	9
2.1	About INCENTIVE project.....	9
2.2	Aim and scope of D1.3.....	9
3.	REQUIREMENTS AND MOTIVATIONS OF QH STAKEHOLDERS FOR ACTIVE ENGAGEMENT IN THE CITIZEN SCIENCE HUBS.....	11
3.1	Problem statement.....	11
3.2	Objectives and research questions.....	11
3.3	Overall methodology.....	11
3.4	Timeline of research activities	12
4.	STEP 1 - EXPLORATORY RESEARCH.....	14
4.1	Objectives.....	14
4.2	Methodology	14
4.3	Findings	15
	4.3.1 <i>Introduction to Citizen Science: concept, trends and links with EU policies.....</i>	<i>15</i>
	4.3.2 <i>Drivers and obstacles regarding public and stakeholders' participation in citizen science</i>	<i>17</i>
	4.3.3 <i>Status, trends and enabling/hindering factors on citizen science at the RPOFs ecosystem.....</i>	<i>26</i>
5.	STEP 2: INTERVIEWS WITH STAKEHOLDERS.....	36
5.1	Objectives.....	36
5.2	Methodology	36
	5.2.1 <i>Selection of interviewing method and development of interview guide.....</i>	<i>36</i>
	5.2.2 <i>Participants and procedure.....</i>	<i>37</i>
	5.2.3 <i>Data analysis.....</i>	<i>38</i>
5.3	Findings	39
	5.3.1 <i>Hindering factors, barriers and obstacles.....</i>	<i>39</i>
	5.3.2 <i>Driving factors and enablers.....</i>	<i>43</i>
6.	STEP 3: LARGE-SCALE SURVEY.....	48
6.1	Objectives.....	48
6.2	Methodology	48
	6.2.1 <i>Sample.....</i>	<i>48</i>
	6.2.2 <i>Questionnaire structure.....</i>	<i>50</i>
6.3	Findings	51
	6.3.1 <i>Demographics and sample structure.....</i>	<i>51</i>
	6.3.2 <i>Familiarity and previous experience with Citizen Science.....</i>	<i>54</i>
	6.3.3 <i>Statistical analysis at national level.....</i>	<i>62</i>

6.3.4 Cross-national comparisons.....	84
7. CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD.....	85
REFERENCES.....	87
ANNEX A: INTERVIEW GUIDE.....	91
ANNEX B: CONSENT FORM AND PRIVACY POLICY	93
ANNEX C: METHODOLOGICAL NOTE ON THE STATISTICAL ANALYSIS	101
ANNEX D: SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE	111

List of figures

Figure 1. Number of scientific publications that include at least one affiliation from Greece and are related to CS or crowdsourcing, according to Scopus search.....	29
Figure 2. Mapping of Greek citizen science projects.....	30
Figure 3. Venn diagram for the concepts of citizen science, open science and transdisciplinary research. Source: NPOS, 2020.....	33
Figure 4. Network structure for Citizen science Netherlands (CS-NL Network).	34
Figure 5. Surveyed countries and distribution of sample.....	49
Figure 6. Level of familiarity with the term "Citizen Science"	55
Figure 7. Level of familiarity with the term "Responsible Research and Innovation".....	56
Figure 8. Type of previous experience with Citizen Science.....	57
Figure 9. General perceptions about Citizen Science and Citizen Science Hubs in Greece	63
Figure 10. Willingness to join Citizen Science activities in Greece (per stakeholder group).....	64
Figure 11. Topics of interest in Greece (per stakeholder group).....	65
Figure 12. Stage of the research process that you like to be involved (per stakeholder group).....	66
Figure 13. General perceptions about Citizen Science and Citizen Science Hubs in Lithuania.....	69
Figure 14. Willingness to join Citizen Science activities in Lithuania (per stakeholder group).....	70
Figure 15. Topics of interest in Lithuania (per stakeholder group)	71
Figure 16. Stage of the research process that you like to be involved (per stakeholder group).....	72
Figure 17. General perceptions about Citizen Science and Citizen Science Hubs in the Netherlands	75
Figure 18. Willingness to join Citizen Science activities in the Netherlands (per stakeholder group).....	76
Figure 19. Topics of interest in the Netherlands (per stakeholder group).....	77
Figure 20. Stage of the research process that you like to be involved (per stakeholder group).....	77
Figure 21. General perceptions about Citizen Science and Citizen Science Hubs in Spain.....	80
Figure 22. Willingness to join Citizen Science activities in Spain (per stakeholder group).....	81
Figure 23. Topics of interest in Spain (per stakeholder group).....	82
Figure 24. Stage of the research process that you like to be involved (per stakeholder group).....	82

List of tables

Table 1. Division of research activities between partners.....	13
Table 2. Factors that facilitate and hinder the participation of citizen and stakeholders in citizen science activities and projects.....	23
Table 3. Most important enabling and hindering factors for CS at national level.....	32
Table 4. Most important enabling and hindering factors for CS in VGTU.....	32
Table 5. Thematic framework of identified barriers and obstacles to participation to Citizen Science ..	40
Table 6. Thematic framework of driving factors and enablers for participation to Citizen Science.....	44
Table 7. Number of observations by country	51
Table 8. Sample distribution by demographics and QH group.....	53
Table 9. Representativeness of sample in terms of gender.....	54
Table 11. Previous experience with Citizen Science.....	56
Table 12. Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for policy-makers.....	59
Table 13. Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for business and private sector.....	60
Table 14. Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for civil society and general public	61
Table 15 Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for Greece.....	66
Table 16. Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for Lithuania.....	73
Table 17. Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for the Netherlands	78
Table 18 Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for Spain	83

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Complete version
CS	Citizen Science
CSH	Citizen Science Hub
EU	European Union
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
RPFO	Research Performing and Funding Organizations
QH	Quadruple Helix

1. Executive summary

This deliverable presents the “Requirements and motivations of quadruple helix stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science Hubs” of the H2020 INCENTIVE Project. The deliverable provides a current overview of the perceptions, attitudes, concerns, motivational factors and obstacles with regard to participation in Citizen Science activities in four pilot countries: Greece, Lithuania, the Netherlands, and Spain. Under INCENTIVE, four Citizen Science Hubs will be established and tested during the life-span of the project in the facilities of four Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS): University of Twente (the Netherlands), Autonomous University of Barcelona (Spain), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (Lithuania). Essentially, the Hubs will aim to bring different stakeholders together and bridge society with science under the emerging paradigm of Citizen Science, in an institutionalised way.

To identify the enabling and hindering factors, as well as the personal experiences, perspectives and dispositions, the deliverable deploys a mixed methodology, entailing an in-depth literature review, a series of semi-structured interviews with QH stakeholders, and a large-scale survey targeting the citizens and general public from the local ecosystems of the pilot RPFOS.

The results reveal a wide range of findings, both for at the EU (aggregated) level, and for each national setting of pilot RPFOS (individual level). More importantly, the analysis of the data shows that the four countries differ strongly regarding the current social trends and perceptions vis-à-vis Citizen Science, as well as the role and limitations of the envisioned Citizen Science Hubs. In addition, the results show diversification – in some instances quite strong – of perceptions across the QH stakeholder groups.

Furthermore, it is evident that no factor, either positive or negative, can be singled out as most important. Depending on the country and the pre-existing level of Citizen Science maturity, the results provide a complicated network of factors that unlock or block participation in CS activities. These factors include, to name a few, political maturity, civic engagement, technological infrastructures, economic growth, culture of stakeholder collaboration, psychological stimulus, and surplus of resources. Each section presents in detail the different research methods used together with the respective findings.

2. Introduction

2.1 About INCENTIVE project

Europe's Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS) have a crucial role to play as agents of institutional change towards firmly grounding RRI in our society. The successful fulfilment of this challenging yet highly significant role calls for the values of RRI to be well-embedded into their governance as well as their operation with greater and more systematic participation of citizens and all R&I stakeholders.

INCENTIVE's central mission is to navigate European RPFOS towards achieving lasting institutional change through the successful implementation of citizen science. For this reason, the project guides four RPFOS to establish their unique Citizen Science Hub, a space where citizens, stakeholder groups and scientists will join forces for stimulating and supporting excellent citizen science in line with RRI principles, to serve the needs of the QH stakeholders. In simple words, the project helps RPFOS to adopt at their institutional core the concept of Citizen Science, which entails the active participation of general public and stakeholders in the co-creation, implementation and evaluation of scientific research, and allows R&I stakeholders to effectively adopt CS as a research methodology, therefore leading to inclusive and more effective science, therefore unleashing the full potential of European research.

The project aims to demonstrate the potential of such Citizen Science Hubs in four universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT). By doing so, the project accelerates the transition of these institutions to more inclusive, open and democratic innovation and scientific governance, under the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation. We tailor the governance and operating models of their hubs to their unique institutional specificities and regional ecosystems of R&I stakeholders, before putting them to the test to drive institutional change through a series of RRI-grounding actions conducted with and for society (citizen science, co-creation of public policies, R&I agenda setting, etc.).

All in all, our Citizen Science Hubs, besides being a sustainable institutional change themselves, will serve as a vehicle for introducing substantial institutional changes in our RPFOS and their communities. INCENTIVE will closely monitor, evaluate and report the performance and outcomes of our Citizen Science Hubs and their actions, providing evidence of societal, democratic, economic and scientific impacts. Along the way, INCENTIVE will foster mutual learning and networking opportunities amongst RPFOS across Europe to share our experiences and develop practical tools to enable RPFOS to drive similar institutional changes in other contexts.

2.2 Aim and scope of D1.3

The aim of D1.3 – "Requirements and motivations of quadruple helix stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science Hubs" is to engage external quadruple helix (QH)

stakeholders (i.e., civil society, private sector, public administration, academic stakeholders) of the four participating RPFs' ecosystems in defining and discussing their views, perceptions, concerns, terms of engagement, expectations and motivations for actively engaging in the Citizen Science Hubs that are expected to be established during the duration of the INCENTIVE project.

In particular, the document seeks to provide answers regarding the factors that motivates or discourages the QH stakeholders and the wider public in Citizen Science activities in general, and specifically in the Citizen Science Hubs that will be developed in four Research Performing and Funding Organisations across four European countries: University of Twente (the Netherlands), Autonomous University of Barcelona (Spain), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (Greece) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (Lithuania). The document offers a range of rich insights about hindering and enabling factors of CS in these four countries, and aspires to contribute to the wider literature on CS that focuses on motivations, perspectives, possibilities and limitations with respect to public engagement.

Essentially, the document sheds light and validates a series of findings that are of direct interest to the four pilot RPFs for the future operation of their CS Hub. At the same time, its added-value lies in the overall theoretical proposition in the wider field of Citizen Science, and how the latter can effectively and efficiently attract and retain different stakeholder groups and citizens, under a collaborative approach.

In more detail after a short introduction (Section 2) and a brief presentation of the project (Section 3), the document is structured as follows:

In Section 4, the main objectives and research questions that underlie the document are concisely described, alongside the main methodological rationale followed and tools deployed. A detailed timeline of the research activities that took place from February 2021 to June 2021 is provided.

In Section 5, the findings from the exploratory literature review (Step 1) are presented. After a general introduction to the concept and most recent trends of Citizen Science, the most important drivers and obstacles that are identified in the studied literature are discussed. Then, the document zooms into the status, trends and enabling/hindering factors in the four pilot countries of INCENTIVE project, where the envisioned Citizen Science Hubs will be developed.

In Section 6, the findings from 8 semi-structured interviews with external stakeholders (2 per pilot RPF) are thoroughly analysed and discussed (Step 2). Moreover, the methodology and analytical process are outlined, so as to pave the way for future qualitative research on this aspect that seeks to provide new data on QH stakeholders' perceptions, or validate the data in the document therein.

Section 7 presents the methodology, steps and results of a large-scale survey that run in all pilot countries, during which approximately 2.000 citizens participated and provided their views on the issue of Citizen Science and their potential engagement in the upcoming Citizen Science Hubs. The results contain both descriptive statistics and statistical analysis per country.

Finally, Section 8 closes the document with some concluding remarks.

3. Requirements and motivations of QH stakeholders for active engagement in the Citizen Science Hubs

3.1 Problem statement

3.2 Objectives and research questions

The central research question that this document seeks to answer is the following: **"what is the current state of play in terms of Citizen Science engagement in the four participating countries, and which are the main driving and hindering factors that affect the type and level of engagement?"**. However, given the overall amount of the different research activities that were performed in order this document to be produced, a series of research sub-questions had to be first addressed. These questions are meticulously outlined and answered in the respective sections of Step 1, Step 2, and Step 3 of the present document. However, a preliminary overview of the different research questions is the following:

- What is the current maturity level of Citizen Science in the four participating countries of INCENTIVE project?
- How Citizen Science is understood and implemented in the four participating countries?
- What are the main attitudes, perceptions and views from the different stakeholder groups vis-à-vis Citizen Science in the four participating countries?
- What are the main driving factors and enablers that positively affect the level of participation in Citizen Science in the four participating countries?
- What are the main hindering factors and obstacles that negatively affect the level of participation in Citizen Science in the four participating countries?

These research questions are addressed in each research step of the document therein.

3.3 Overall methodology

In this document, a mixed research methodology is used. Under that approach, a series of different methodological pathways have been selected and leveraged, with the aim to address the abovementioned research questions from different theoretical angles. In particular, three different methodological methods were combined into a coherent narrative: (i) a qualitative literature review in Step 1; (ii) a qualitative thematic analysis on semi-structured interviews in Step 2; (iii) a quantitative large-scale survey and subsequent statistical analysis in Step 3.

Each methodological pathway served a different theoretical and practical purpose. In the first qualitative step, the current landscape of Citizen Science was thoroughly examined by synthesising secondary sources, in order to develop a new holistic framework that can accommodate all the previous existing theoretical findings on the literature on Citizen Science, with a focus on the four participating countries of the project. In the second qualitative step (the in-depth semi-structured interviews), the subjective views and perceptions of local

stakeholders were elicited, analysed and interpreted in a bottom-up approach, with the aim to generate new theoretical insights (or themes, as explained in the respective section). Finally, in the third step, a positivist methodological approach was adopted, whereby survey participants were asked their opinion on given barriers and drivers of Citizen Science, thus allowing the quantification of results.

By combining, under an exploratory approach (DRG, 2021), the strengths that each research paradigm can offer – the interpretivist rationale of qualitative research under which new theoretical ideas emerge, and the positivist rationale of quantitative research under which preformulated ideas are tested and confirmed – this document adopts a third paradigm. In other words, **the document opts for a mixed research methodology as a "third road"** that transcends the quantitative-qualitative divide (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). According to the latter, since qualitative and quantitative methods "do not study the same phenomena, quantitative and qualitative methods cannot be combined". This document refutes this thesis, because it essentially showcases how a mixed research design (Robson and McCartan, 2016) can effectively generate new insights on Citizen Science engagement factors, but also test these new insights through quantitative statistical analysis. As such, the document deploys triangulation, both as a means of complementing missing information (e.g., in-depth interviews filling the gap from the literature review) but also as way to check the validity of data by juxtaposing different primary sources (statistically corroborate whether identified driving factors have an actual effect on Citizen Science engagement level), therefore reducing the risk of drawing false conclusions (Hammersley, 2008).

3.4 Timeline of research activities

The overall data collection and analysis took place from February to July 2021, spanning a period of six months in total. In more detail, the periods in which research activities unfolded are the following:

- **Step 1** – Literature review: February – March 2021
- **Step 2** – Interviews with stakeholders: March – April 2021
- **Step 3** – Large-scale survey and statistical analysis: April – July 2021
- **Step 4** – Report writing: July 2021

Even though White Research, as Task leader, was the responsible for the majority of research activities (e.g., allocation of roles and management, literature review, interviews performance and data analysis, development of survey questionnaire and statistical analysis of data), a big team of researchers from consortium partners, and particularly from the four pilot RPOs of the participating countries, actively contributed in all research activities. As such, their contribution should be acknowledged and presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Division of research activities between partners

Activities	Partner(s)
Contribution to literature review and synthesis of findings Development of interview guide, interviewing and analysis of results Development of survey questionnaire and statistical analysis Report writing	White Research
Contribution to literature review Identification of stakeholders to be interviewed Active collection of survey responses from the regional ecosystem	University of Twente Autonomous University of Barcelona Aristotle University of Thessaloniki Vilnius Gediminas Technical University
Contribution to literature review	Q-Plan

During the overall period of research activities, White Research remained in close contact with all contributing partners in order to provide proper instructions, coordinate activities, identify potential risks and problems, and effectively mitigate them within the scheduled timeline. To that end, regular bilateral or consortium-wise meetings were held during the duration of D1.3 development, in which the progress, obstacles and mitigation measures were collectively discussed among consortium partners and decisions were taken for the next steps.

In the remainder of the document, the three research steps are presented in detail, alongside the main findings that were generated from research activities.

4. Step 1 - Exploratory research

4.1 Objectives

Research activities commenced with an exploratory research, whose objective was to identify a range of cross-national driving factors and barriers with regard to Citizen Science participation from the citizens on the one hand, while on the other hand presenting the current landscape of Citizen Science maturity level in the four participating countries: Greece, Lithuania, the Netherlands and Spain. The research was hence divided into two layers: a European/international layer, and four national layers. The core research questions posed in that step were the following: (i) what is Citizen Science and what are its current trends; (ii) what are the main driving and hindering factors that usually affect Citizen Science participation, irrespectively of time and place; and (iii) what are the current patterns in Citizen Science in the four participating countries.

4.2 Methodology

The exploratory research has been conducted in the form of a traditional literature review. Recent literature sources and published material were examined, and a summary table was created to aggregate all the knowledge collected, in line with the principles of traditional review (Robson and McCartan, 2016). At the same time, literature review, as a form of secondary data analysis – as opposed to primary data analyses in Step 2 and Step 3 – offered a series of advantages from a research point of view: it saved cost and time that were used for the in-depth interviews and the large-scale survey; it offered high-quality data as a starting point to the consortium; and it opened new possibilities for re-interpretation of existing primary data (Bryman, 2012). The latter advantage is of particular importance, because it permitted a holistic approach (see Table 1) of the enablers and obstacles of Citizen Science, by assembling diverse primary data, which had been found through original research studies across countries and time, into a single analytical framework.

Upon selection of the optimal methodological approach, the division of the work was the following: White Research and Q-Plan focused on the general concept of Citizen Science, the current trends at European level, as well as the linkages with official EU policies. Moreover, a comprehensive overview of drivers and obstacles regarding public and stakeholders' acceptance of and participation in Citizen Science activities was accomplished, so the reader can understand the general context on Citizen Science's enabling and hindering factors. Then, the four pilot RPFOS narrowed their focus down on the status, trends and enabling/hindering factors at their local ecosystem. Each RPFOS undertook the responsibility to cover the literature for their respective country. The decision was taken on the basis that partners from pilot RPFOS could consult literature sources (either primary or secondary) in their national language, thus enriching the findings. Once all partners had collected the required information, WR was responsible for merging everything together into a coherent narrative.

4.3 Findings

4.3.1 *Introduction to Citizen Science: concept, trends and links with EU policies*

Concept

Citizen science (CS), also known as "Community science", "Amateur science", "Crowdsourced science", and "Volunteer monitoring" (Scistarter, 2021), is defined as the participation of non-scientific stakeholders in the scientific process. It entails collaboration between the public and researchers/institutes but also engages governments and funding agencies (Hacklay et al., 2021). However, this is a generic and not a uniform (i.e., applicable to all cases and at all times) definition. Various organisations worldwide use different starting points and criteria for defining citizen science, each with its own focus according to different contexts and objectives (Hacklay et al., 2021).

Citizen science projects may cover various scientific fields, such as biology, astronomy, medicine, computer science, statistics, psychology and engineering (National Geographic, 2021a; Pérez and Costa, 2018). They may also range from large international projects, which involve professional scientists and research institutions, to small projects by groups with a common interest (Grey et al. 2016). Besides, people's participation in such projects may take various forms. It can span from being better informed about science to contributing to the scientific process itself by developing the research question, designing the method, gathering and analysing data, and communicating the results (EC, 2020; ECSA, 2015). Opinion polls and projects that collect public data from social media, or incentivise participation without clearly stating their scientific purpose, are generally not considered citizen science. A necessary requirement for every CS initiative is voluntary and active public engagement with research (Grey et al. 2016).

Scientists usually create citizen-science programs to capture crowdsourced data that would be hard to obtain otherwise due to time, geographic, or resource constraints, or to make use of the collective intelligence of humans that outperform automatic procedures in identifying and classifying information in data collected via various ways. Classical examples are the identification of protein or galaxy structures in massively collected relevant images. For this purpose, they often work with community groups that are already collecting such information (National Geographic, 2021a). For instance, several participative sciences programs have been developed in Coral reef studies. This is because the millions of tourists who enjoy underwater photography have superior coverage power than professional scientists, who cannot spend so much time in the field (Peterson et al., 2020).

On top of this, **universities may deploy CS projects** to (i) engage with a wide range of stakeholders who can provide insights, suggestions and ideas to improve existing research activities or propose new research questions; (ii) contribute to their overall educational and societal mission by encouraging people to get involved into science; (iii) build meaningful relationships with communities, which may promote Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

and (iv) as a research method together with other methods of scientific research, in the frame of a research project or activity (EPA, 2019; Grey et al., 2016; Kasperowski et al., 2017).

However, not only professional scientists benefit from taking part in CS projects. **Citizen scientists** can harness learning opportunities and gain personal enjoyment, social benefits, and satisfaction by contributing to scientific evidence and influencing policy (ECSA, 2015). It is worth noting that citizen scientists come from all walks of life, including retirees, online gamers, educators and students (Scistarter, 2021). Besides, they may have varying levels of expertise, from kids in their backyards to amateur scientists with home equipment (National Geographic, 2021a).

Much of the work entailed in a CS project may occur in the countryside, close to home, or even sometimes in people's backyards, living rooms and kitchens, according to established science protocols and tools and guidance from professional scientists (National Geographic, 2021b). However, in recent years, a small number of world-leading Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS) worldwide have established transdisciplinary hubs for stimulating and supporting excellent citizen science. These hubs are commonly known as "**Citizen Science Hubs**".¹

Trends

"Citizen science" is a relatively **new term but an old practice**². Before the 20th century, several amateurs or self-funded researchers, such as Isaac Newton, Benjamin Franklin, and Charles Darwin, existed. By the mid-20th century, science was dominated by researchers employed by universities and governmental bodies. But, by the 1970s, this transformation was being called into question (Silvertown, 2009). Especially in the late 1990s, the Internet's widespread availability made information sharing easier to people, and the number of citizen-science programs increased.

Today, the number and scope of citizen science projects have expanded due to the development of smartphones that have built-in GPS receivers and other sensors (National Geographic, 2021a). Besides, **worldwide participation in citizen science is growing** (i) because the percentage of highly educated, well informed, and active citizens interested in science is also increasing; and (ii) due to growing concerns about various issues, such as environmental sustainability (Grey et al., 2016; Wikipedia, 2021). In 2018, related research showed that the top five citizen science communities worldwide have 3.75 million participants (Wikipedia, 2021)³.

¹ To the best of our knowledge in Europe, only two official and operative structures of this sort exist: the Citizen Science Center Zurich, jointly established by the University of Zurich and ETH Zurich, and the Citizen Science Lab of Leiden University.

² It is worth noting that the term "citizen science" provides with a clear increasing percentage of appearance in the online GoogleTrends search engine for the period 2004 till today.

³ Although there is likely substantial overlap between the communities.

Other recent developments in the CS field are (i) the emergence of several networks and associations that encourage and coordinate citizen science projects by initiating journals, developing policies and organising conferences and events; and (ii) the development of crowdsourcing platforms that enable volunteers to contribute to different research projects, essentially encouraging greater volunteers' retention. In the future, the use of machine learning technologies and artificial intelligence may extend citizen science platforms' capabilities, especially those depending on human intelligence. As a result, citizens' roles in citizen science projects may expand further and become more demanding (Grey et al., 2016).

Links with EU policies

Citizen science can be interpreted as a part of *"the wider open science movement, along with open access publishing, open data standards and alternative metrics for impact assessment"* (Grey et al., 2016). It can (i) **promote the efficient and transparent use of science and research funding**; (ii) lead to better engagement in research, governance and accountability; (iii) bring European policy-making closer to the people in a scientific and data-driven approach; and (iv) contribute to economic growth through open innovation (EC, 2020).

In this frame, **politicians throughout Europe progressively see citizen science as an opportunity** for greater public engagement and science democratisation. The Science Communication Unit (2013) is currently investigating the potential of CS as input for environmental policy-making in the Knowledge Innovation Project and supports CS in its research funding programs (e.g., Citizens' Observatories, Responsible Research and Innovation). Besides, funding agencies promote CS with tailored programs, such as the European Horizon 2020 "Science with and for Society" program (EC, 2020).

4.3.2 Drivers and obstacles regarding public and stakeholders' participation in citizen science

Understanding the diversity and complexity of factors that either enable or hinder the participation of general public and stakeholder groups – such as the representatives of the scientific community – is of critical importance for any successful citizen science initiative. Since citizen science is de facto based on creating and sustaining a critical mass of participation, in the same way volunteer-based projects does, it is vital to identify what are the conditions that may foster or discourage the level of citizen involvement (Larson et al., 2020). Nevertheless, identifying the multitude of factors is not an easy process, taking into consideration the different levels and types of factors that are at interplay. First of all, there are internal motivations that concern the psychosocial desires of the citizen scientists⁴ at individual level. Furthermore, there are types of motivation that regard the achievement of goals that go beyond the mere satisfaction of feelings, such as the obtainment of a certificate or monetary gains (Geoghegan

⁴ By "citizen scientists", it is meant the citizens and members of general public who are formally enrolled in and participate to a citizen science project or initiative. The term should not be confused with the "scientists" who are the formal representatives of the scientific community.

et al., 2016). On the other hand, the importance of factors that refer to the structural conditions of the ecosystem (e.g., cultural, historical, socio-economic, institutional, etc.), which impact the agent's decision to become a citizen scientist, cannot be neglected. Another category of factors refer to those that impact the decision of other stakeholder groups, thus interacting with the (de)motivators of citizen scientists (Larson et al., 2020). Finally, all these factors can change over time and at different stages of citizen scientists' participation.

The remainder of the section deals with this complicated plethora of positive and negative factors, by exploring both drivers for and barriers to citizens' and stakeholders' active engagement in citizen science initiatives and projects. These factors have been extracted from the relevant literature and identified through case-studies that cover different countries and contexts, thus the results aspire to provide a holistic picture that is able to accommodate – at conceptual level – as many dimensions as possible.

Drivers and enabling factors

In principle, drivers can be distinguished between those stemming from subjective perceptions, desires, motivations and personal goals, and to drivers that refer to objective circumstances of the macroenvironment, such as the overall environmental conditions (e.g., weather), cultural, social and economic conditions.

At individual level, egoistic values – such as personal interest and enthusiasm in the scientific subject of the citizen science initiative – have been a recurring driver across contexts (Rotman et al., 2014a; Butteriss, 2019; Geoghegan et al., 2016; Jennett et al., 2016; Larson et al., 2020; Kragh, 2016). Psychosocial parameters such as the ability of citizen scientists to express their personal value and creativity (Scotland Counts, 2016), as well as fulfilment of curiosity and personal desires for discovery (Larson et al., 2020; Kragh, 2016) are also important. Self-prestige and personal growth matter: fostering personal reputation among community members, increasing scientific literacy and acquiring new skills and information are typical examples of internal motivations (Rotman et al., 2014a; Butteriss, 2019; Geoghegan et al., 2016; Jennett et al., 2016; Larson et al., 2020; Asingizwe et al., 2020). Additional emotional drivers include the desire to achieve positive hands-on experience and satisfaction through participation (Gordienko, 2013); to accomplish personal love towards natural environment (Geoghegan et al., 2016; Scotland Counts, 2016); to fill a sense of self-efficacy and usefulness to scientific research (Rotman et al., 2014b; Jennett et al., 2016; Kragh, 2016); to address health concerns and personal problems (Asingizwe et al., 2020); and to feel active member of the society (Scotland Counts, 2016).

Individual motivations are not only emotional and psychosocial. There are plenty of drivers that regard the individual level but either seek to accomplish outcomes that go beyond emotional satisfaction, or are influenced by objective facts. Accomplishment of such goals pertain to learning benefits through participation in citizen science (Rotman et al., 2014b; Martin et al., 2016); fostering personal CV and career track, especially for young persons (Gordienko, 2013; Butteriss, 2019; Geoghegan et al., 2016; Larson et al., 2020; Asingizwe et al., 2020) as well as creating new professional contact points (Scotland Counts, 2016); monetary incentives as compensation for the efforts and time devoted (Gordienko, 2013); incentives for recreation and

nature-based activities (Geoghegan et al., 2016; Kragh, 2016); formal accreditation of citizen science activities and achievements like certificates (Scotland Counts, 2016); and opportunities for socialisation with like-minded peers who participate in the same project (Scotland Counts, 2016; Kragh, 2016). On the other hand, there are factors that can directly impact and determine the individual motivations in citizen science endeavours. These factors include the alignment of the local needs of the participant with the scientific priorities (Pocock et al., 2018); the existence of proper mentorship to citizens from training courses to closeness with the scientists through personal interaction (Rotman et al., 2014a); positive competitive elements in citizen science activities (Gordienko, 2013) such as gamification (Geoghegan et al., 2016); and level of education, income and overall degree of independence (Rotman et al., 2014b; Larson et al., 2020). All the above mentioned can shape the emotional dynamics of citizens and either encourage or demobilise them.

Individual motivational factors are important, but the significance of collective motivational factors cannot be neglected. Some of these conditions are important per se, but may also influence the public's involvement because they will be interpreted as substantial by the latter. Collective motivational factors that are perceived to be critical are the existence of previous good practices and "success stories" of citizen science that will inspire stakeholders (Wilson Center, 2014) or the professional recognition of citizen scientists' efforts and encouragement for further work (Garcia-Soto et al., 2017; Rotman et al., 2014a; Rotman et al., 2014b; Science Communication Unit, 2013; Butteriss, 2019) and the public acknowledgement of impact and contribution of citizen scientists by the scientific community (Geoghegan et al., 2016; Jennett et al., 2016). The existence of scientists with previous engagement in citizen science activities, who are more "outward-facing" and show higher level of trust in the regional ecosystem is another factor (Burgess et al., 2016) that may facilitate the creation of team bonds and sense of sharing common goals (Jennett et al., 2016). Values related to altruism and collectivism may turn out particularly powerful collective drivers. A sense of socio-ecological responsibility and commitment to a common cause can push individuals towards actions (Rotman et al., 2014a; Rotman et al., 2014b; Butteriss, 2019; Geoghegan et al., 2016; Larson et al., 2020; Kragh, 2016; Asingizwe et al., 2020). The same positive results can be achieved through a more general sense of belonging to community, the existence of national pride, societal empathy and communitarian values, which will lead to the development of a common identity (Rotman et al., 2014a; Rotman et al., 2014b; Larson et al., 2020). Common goals and expectations between stakeholder groups will encourage the agent's level of involvement (Rotman et al., 2014b). Finally, approval by family members and acquaintances (Martin et al., 2016) can have a profound impact on individual's decision to participate.

A last dimension to consider is those enabling factors that transcend the individual and collective motivational level and stem directly from the wider macro-context. In other words, they are related to objective conditions that refer to economic necessities, socio-cultural factors, and the political and institutional environment. Adequate communication mechanisms between scientists and citizens as well as constant and good communication on project's concept, objectives and progress through channels such as website, social media, mails, and newsletters is a precondition to create a critical mass for participation (Rotman et al., 2014a;

Butteriss, 2019). To that end, media coverage and presentation of citizen science as enjoyable activity can be quite beneficial (Gordienko, 2013; Scotland Counts, 2016). The dynamics within the regional ecosystem define to a large extent the level and quality of citizens' involvement. Partnerships with universities, other federal agencies, contractors, museums, philanthropists, and schools (Wilson Center, 2014); the existence of working groups, training personnel and communities of practice (Wilson Center, 2014; Butteriss, 2019); the presence of educational institutions that support local initiatives (Rotman et al., 2014b); and a vibrant community of active of NGOs (Burgess et al., 2016), all these factors can play crucial role. The notion of organizational capacity is of paramount value (Hecker et al., 2018) and entails clearly defined roadmaps, instructions and structured protocols (Wilson Center, 2014; Rotman et al., 2014a; Gordienko, 2013), and feedback channels and state-of-the-art feedback technologies (Mitchell et al., 2017; Rotman et al., 2014a). Project must be tailored to accommodate local communication preferences and interests (Martin et al., 2016). Technological resources that support social networking and development are essential. Mature e-infrastructures for interoperability, communication and data access, like mobile phones and desktop laptops are much needed, and the same applies to mobile connectivity. In general, local technologies have to be fully leveraged if participation is to be sustained in the long-term (Hecker et al., 2018; Gordienko, 2013; Butteriss, 2019; Rotman et al., 2014b). Institutions and governance can unlock citizen science potential. Accountability and transparency in scientific governance and policy institutions (Rotman et al., 2014a; Rotman et al., 2014b), open access to data ("data commons"), and political guarantees that the data findings from the citizen science project will be properly exploited (Science Communication Unit, 2013) are indicative of good governance. Last but not least, pre-existing culture, social norms and tradition on volunteerism (Larson et al., 2020; Burgess et al., 2016) and external relationships of the citizen science stakeholders with broader community can lead to positive spill-over effects and multiple participation rates (Rotman et al., 2014b).

Barriers and hindering factors

To a large extent, the barriers and factors that hinder the participation of citizens and stakeholders in citizen science activities and projects can be understood as the reversal of the facilitating factors outlined above (Martin et. al, 2016). The negative inversion of the factors does not apply only to most of the factors, but also to their categorization itself: de-motivational factors at individual level, either subjectively perceived or posed by external barriers; impeding structural conditions at the macro-environment such as culture, history, economy, institutions and politics; or socially constructed narratives that produce a general sense of pessimism.

At individual level, it is often the misleading perceptions by the citizens themselves that block them from initiating and continuing their active participation. The false perception from citizens of being unable – as inadequately educated and thus amateur – to deliver high-quality, reliable and rigorous scientific pushes them to believe that the results and data will be of poor quality (Garcia-Soto et al., 2017; Wilson Center, 2014; Mitchell et al., 2017; Pocock et al., 2018; Science Communication Unit, 2013; Martin et al., 2016). Low levels of self-confidence regard also the false inability to collect adequate data volume (Mitchell et al., 2017). At the same time, citizen scientists may also be uncertain regarding the honesty of the exploitation of the data they have

collected from scientists, potentially leading to harmful effects. This is linked to the fear of potentially inappropriate policy decisions, such as block to public access to natural sites (Martin et al., 2016). Finally, a very common barrier is inertia and lack of general interest from participants (Pocock et al., 2018).

There are however, objective barriers that can seriously inflict the individual's decision to enter a citizen science initiative. Age is an objective factor: the desire to voluntarily participate in citizen science increases until the 20s and then again between 40 and 45; consequently, demographic dynamics is an important factor (Wilson Center, 2014; Geoghegan et al., 2016). Low scientific literacy and poor skills from participants can indeed occur (Pocock et al., 2018), which can cause various observer and sampling biases (Burgess et al., 2016). Language barriers (Pocock et al., 2018) and high level of difficulty in the assigned tasks (Kleinke et al., 2018) can function as burden for participants and discourage them. Still, one of the gravest obstacles can be time. When there are time constraints from the side of citizen scientists, and when citizen science activities require excessive time, then, this time-consuming process may simply exhaust participants and lead to drop out, eventually blocking the scientific venture (Collins et al., 2015; Kleinke et al., 2018; Butteriss, 2019; Rotman et al., 2014b; Martin et al., 2016; Asingizwe et al., 2020). In addition, poor literacy of ICT technologies and problematic access to relevant resources have been found to act as barriers or to negatively affect participation to CS projects (Kassandros et al., 2021)

Citizens are not the only whose distorted perceptions about citizen science can pose obstacles. Misperceptions at collective level and from other stakeholder groups can often prevail and burden citizen science's success. Policy makers and the scientific community at large can share analogous, yet often unfounded, fears about the quality of citizen science efforts and outcomes. Fears of privacy violation and issues related to ownership of results and IPR is often recorded (Wilson Center, 2014; Hecker et al., 2018; Gordienko, 2013). Some scientists believe that ethics mismanagement and misuse of public data is hard to avoid in citizen science (Parthenos project, 2019; Hecker et al., 2018). Often, there is limited awareness from scientists on the benefits and potentials of citizen science, whereas bias and scepticism pervade the scientific community members regarding the acceptance of data sources from citizen science. The latter is justified on lack of rigorous research design, data collection inconsistencies and a general tendency to opt for data traditionally collected from peer scientists (Burgess et al., 2016). Unsurprisingly, this cultivates mistrust between the scientific community, policy makers and citizen scientists, leading to low levels of social capital through a vicious cycle (Parthenos project, 2019; Hecker et al., 2018; Pocock et al., 2018).

Problematic structures of macro-level complement the puzzle of barriers. For instance, institutional barriers such as bureaucratic rigidities, organizational incapacity, lack of leadership and proper planning inevitable generate hurdles citizens' involvement (Wilson Center, 2014; Pocock et al., 2018). Organizational problems may pertain to lack of clear instructions and counselling, or even the existence of complicated processes and protocols that confuse participants (Wilson Center, 2014; Kleinke et al., 2018). The situation can become worse when there are no previous/relevant successful local citizen science initiatives (Wilson Center, 2014), or when a mismatching between scientific agendas and local communities' needs is observed

(Parthenos project, 2019). It has already been stressed that communication is vital; the same is true for its absence. When communication between citizen scientists and formal scientists is poor or absent, the drop-out rate increases (Rotman et al., 2014b). Robust funding is necessary for a citizen science activity to flourish, so when there is lack of funding channels or opportunities, and when budgetary constraints arise due to absence of national funding schemes, citizen science becomes a luxury (Wilson Center, 2014; Parthenos project, 2019; Collins et al., 2015; Pocock et al., 2018). Some authors (Mitchell et al., 2017; Burgess et al., 2016) mention data validation and verification techniques, as well as limited networking opportunities (Pocock et al., 2018) as additional burdens. Another significant dimension is technology (rather than its absence or poor quality). When no suitable, proper or adequate technology, such as smartphones or internet connection, is in place, and especially in rural areas, the prospects of wide and long-lasting participation diminish (Pocock et al., 2018; Martin et al., 2016). Governance is also an essential element. Top-down and excessively centralized governance structures of citizen science projects suffocate participation (Rotman et al., 2014b), while unsuitable science types may be selected and create extra problems (Burgess et al., 2016). Remaining factors to take into consideration are cultural barriers and lack of awareness opportunities (Rotman et al., 2014b); inappropriate or absent training structures (Burgess et al., 2016). Finally, bad weather conditions can also discourage participation regarding activities that take place in natural settings (Martin et al., 2016).

A holistic approach

The overall complexity of the identified factors indicates that dynamics at micro-, meso- and macro-level interact with each other and can either create the necessary conditions to unlock the full participation of public and stakeholder groups in citizen science, or reversely pose barriers and obstacles that hinder participation. Table 2 summarizes visually all the factors at the aggregated level, as divided per category.

Table 2. Factors that facilitate and hinder the participation of citizen and stakeholders in citizen science activities and projects

	Individual (micro-level) factors	Collective (meso-level) – Structural (macro-level) factors
Subjective – Emotional factors	<p>Drivers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Personal interest and enthusiasm in the scientific subject - Ability to express personal values and creativity - Fulfilment of curiosity and personal desires for discovery - Self-prestige and personal growth: reputation in community, increase scientific literacy and learn new information and professional skills - Achieving positive hands-on experience and satisfaction - Accomplishing love towards natural environment - Sense of self-efficacy and usefulness to scientific research - Sense of remaining active - Concerns for health - Need to address own problems 	<p>Drivers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existence of previous "success stories"/best practices that inspire participants - Professional acknowledgement/recognition/attribution of citizen scientists' efforts and encouragement for further work - Public acknowledgement of impact and contribution of citizen scientists - Existence of scientists with previous engagement on citizen science activities who are more "outward-facing" and show higher level of trust - High levels of trust between volunteers and project organizers; strong social capital in regional ecosystems - Creation of team bonds and sense of sharing common goals - Sense of socio-ecological responsibility; commitment to a common cause; altruism and principism - Sense of belonging to community; national pride and empathy; communitarian values and collectivism spirit; development of a common identity - Common goals and expectations between stakeholder groups - Approval from family and acquaintances
	<p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - False perception from citizens of inability (from inadequately educated and amateur citizen scientists) to deliver high-quality, reliable and rigorous scientific data, resulting in poor/low-quality results and data - False perception from citizens of inability to collect adequate data volume - Uncertainty/untrust from citizen scientists on honest data exploitation from scientists; fear of harmful effects - Fear of wrong policy decisions and consequent block of access to natural sites - Lack of interest from participants 	<p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fear of privacy violation; ownership and IPR issues - Fear of ethics mismanagement and misuse of public data - Lack of trust between scientific community, policy makers and citizen scientists and low social capital levels - Bias, scepticism, and negative perceptions from scientific community in accepting certain data sources: lack of rigorous research design, data collection inconsistencies, preference for data from other scientists - Limited awareness from scientists on citizen science potentials

Objective factors	<p>Drivers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Early and active involvement from participants to align local needs with scientific priorities - Learning benefits - Proper mentorship to citizens: training courses, empowerment, closeness through personal interaction - Positive competitive elements in citizen science activities - Monetary incentives - Level of education - Income and degree of independence - Incentives for recreation and nature-based activities - Gamification of citizen science activities - Formal accreditation of efforts, such as certificates - Opportunities for socialization with like-minded peers - Fostering personal CV, resume and career track - Create new professional contact points 	<p>Drivers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proper communication mechanisms between scientists and citizens; constant and good communication on project's concept, objectives and progress through website, social media, mail, newsletters, media. - Partnerships with universities, other federal agencies, contractors, museums, philanthropists, and schools - Existence of working groups, training personnel and communities of practice; proper mentorship - Clearly defined roadmaps, instructions and structured protocols - Feedback channels and state-of-the-art feedback technologies - Good and timely organization to enable public participation - Resources that support social networking and technology development - Technological resources, open technologies and mature e-infrastructures for interoperability, communication and data access, like mobile phones and desktop laptops; mobile connectivity; exploitation of local technologies - Accountability and transparency in scientific governance and policy institutions - Open access to data: "data commons" - Political guarantees that data findings will be properly leveraged - Pre-existing culture, social norms and tradition on volunteerism - Active NGOs ecosystem - Media coverage and presentation of citizen science as enjoyable activity - Educational institutions that support local initiatives - External relationship with broader community and potential for spill-over effects - Tailored projects that accommodate local communication preferences and interests
	<p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Under-representation of lower socio-economic groups or minorities and social exclusion: false participation - Age: volunteerism increases until 20s and then again between 40 and 45 - Time constraints; time-consuming activities; excessive time demands lack of time 	<p>Barriers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Poor or absent communication between citizen scientists and scientists - Bureaucratic rigidities and institutional barriers such as organizational (in)capacity, lack of leadership and planning - Lack of clear instructions and counselling, or complicated protocols

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Language barriers - Low scientific literacy and skills from participants and citizen scientists - Observer and sampling biases - High level of difficulty in assigned tasks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of funding channels/opportunities and national funding schemes; budgetary constraints - Lack of previous/relevant successful local citizen science initiatives - Lack of data validation and verification techniques - Mismatching between scientific agendas and local communities' needs - Lack of suitable, proper and adequate technology, such as smartphones, internet connection, etc., especially in rural areas - Limited networking opportunities - Lack of awareness opportunities - Inappropriate or absent training structures - Cultural barriers - Unsuitable science type for specific citizen science initiatives - Top-down and centralized governance of citizen science projects - Bad weather conditions and visibility
--	--

4.3.3 *Status, trends and enabling/hindering factors on citizen science at the RPOFs ecosystem*

The case of UAB (Spain)

In Spain there is a long tradition of Citizen Science initiatives. In fact, there are 77 citizen science projects with Spanish participation funded by the Framework Programs of the European Union, and 28 are led by Spanish groups. The importance of this approach to research was evidenced in 2018, when an agreement was signed among Ibercivis Foundation and the Ministry of Science and Innovation (Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology - FECYT), two main actors of Citizen Science in Spain, to consolidate the concept and practice and to promote its presence in the most relevant events on the European and international scene. In fact, since 2016 there is the Observatory of Citizen Science in Spain and the web portal "<https://ciencia-ciudadana.es/>" which are the result of a project developed by the Ibercivis Foundation with the collaboration of FECYT. The objectives of the Observatory are:

- Increase the knowledge and vision of citizen science
- Give visibility to the projects to facilitate participation and to disseminate their objectives and results
- Identify the actors (research groups, funding programs, citizens' initiatives, physical spaces, NGOs, etc.), analyse the impacts of the various projects, promote the adoption of best practices, and lay the foundations for continuous monitoring over time of citizen science in Spain
- Facilitate coordination, synergies and collaborations between projects, and share resources and methodologies in the different fields of scientific research
- Understand the influence of citizen science on scientific culture
- Understand how this scientific methodology is changing the relationship between science and society as a whole, through the various practices of citizen participation in research

The Observatory has had the financial support of the FECYT since 2016, through its annual call for grants for the development of scientific, technological and innovation culture. This call includes citizen science among its lines of action and every year funds many CS initiatives.

Regarding the Spanish R&I policies, in September 2020 was approved the Spanish Science and Technology Strategy for the period 2021-2027. It is the fundamental instrument to consolidate and reinforce the Science, Technology and Innovation System (SECTI) in the next years and it includes citizen science among its four basic principles. The Strategy adapts its time period to facilitate the articulation and synergies between the national R & I policy and the policies of the European Union, especially with Horizon Europe (2021-2027). In this context, it is also proposed to promote participation in new infrastructures in the field of innovation and citizen science, for example in the living labs of the Digital Innovation Hubs network, so that the infrastructures can also give access to small research groups, technology centres, companies, etc. The document once again refers to citizen science as one of the transversal elements of the entire Strategy.

At regional and local level, one of the most relevant initiatives promoting Citizen Science initiatives is the "Barcelona Citizen Science Office" (Barcelona.cat, 2021). The Office's mission is to support citizen science in Barcelona by advising, accompanying and promoting projects that want to work in the city and its Metropolitan Area, as well as developing actions aimed at bringing citizens and research closer together and strengthening the connection with new civic and cultural agents. The Barcelona Citizen Science Office was created in 2012 by the Barcelona City Council's Institute of Culture. During last years, has contributed significantly to the consolidation of projects in Barcelona area where citizenship becomes an essential part of the research process and accompanying them in facing the social and environmental challenges of the city.

During this time, the Office has promoted a space for shared learning based on the knowledge and experience achieved thanks to more of twenty scientific projects that have been part of it and in which they have participated over the years. At the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona level, at least for the last few years, it has been developing a variety of initiatives and activities in connection to Citizen Science (UAB, 2021). Most of them are the based on the usual approach to CS, in which citizens contribute collecting and analysing data. However, there are different levels of complexity in the participation of scientific citizens.

In 2018, the UAB launched the HubB30 initiative (HubB30, 2021) a multisector platform that promotes research and innovation in the B30 territory by interacting with actors to identify and work on the territorial challenges, co-design shared visions of the future and promote collective action. The mission of the HubB30 is to generate participative dynamics with the quadruple helix which promote the territory's socio-economic transition by identifying challenges and proposing solutions, sharing knowledge and promoting the collaboration of the actors. It should play a significant role in establishing connections with external bodies (e.g., public administrations, industry) and building partnerships. The HubB30 has a role to play when it comes to linking citizen science and innovation.

In any case, the development of collaborative responses to the territorial challenges requires collaborative workspaces, where the actors can meet, share knowledge and work jointly to develop effective responses to the complex challenges via shared agendas. In this framework, the UAB OpenLabs network initiative (UAB Open Labs, 2020) has taken on a new dimension, providing laboratories or spaces for collaborative innovation, which are essential parts of responsible research and innovation ecosystems. The objective of the UAB OpenLabs network is to create and promote spaces of participation and co-creation in the territory, which produce new environments for experimentation, innovation and demonstrations of new technologies and methodologies.

However, there is still some reticence from researchers to participate in CS initiatives. There is a need for capacity building (on ways in which to engage citizens in research and how to 'find' them, as well as on the benefits of citizen science for research) and for institutional support (methodology, legal aspects, data management, etc.). In addition, is required a right scientific acknowledgment for SC contributions. A systemic change, include new indicators to complement the conventional indicators for research quality and impact, so as to do justice to

citizen science and open science practices. The social impact of citizen science needs to be rewarded in metrics at European, national, and institutional level. In the current reward system, which privileges the number of scientific publications, there is little external motivation for researchers to invest time and effort in citizen science and adopt new methodologies.

The case of AUTH (Greece)

Citizen Science is evolving worldwide and is constantly gaining ground thanks to new technologies that can easily and directly bring citizens in touch with the scientific community. In Greece, over the last decade, Citizen Science initiatives have started to be developed and evolve. However, there is limited integrated information available regarding the status, trends and enabling/hindering factors of this kind of initiatives at national, regional, and local level.

Recent research on the topic by Vohland et al. (2021), revealed that although the economic crisis, the austerity measures and their impact on youth have led to a decline of public participation and volunteering, it seems that in Greece the participation of citizen groups or NGOs in citizen science projects began around 2008.

The citizen science projects that have been implemented or currently running in Greece are usually part of large EU – funded projects or projects that broke ground mainly at national and local level.

The Environmental Informatics Research Group at the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH, 2021) recently performed a detailed mapping of the ongoing or recently finished citizen science projects in Greece (Bakousi, 2021). A total of 91 projects were identified. The analysis performed showed that most of the projects deal with topics related to air quality (9%), society (8%), education (8%), agriculture (7%) urban environment (6%) as well as biodiversity and sea biodiversity (4% each) (Figure 1 **Error! Reference source not found.**). In general, it seems that more than 70% of the projects deal with STEM activities.

Moreover, in a literature review concerning papers published with the participation of at least one scientist affiliated to a Greek RPFO, in relation to citizen science or crowdsourcing, it was made evident that the number of titles published per year demonstrate a stable increase trend on the last ten years, summing 297 publications.

Documents by year

Figure 1. Number of scientific publications that include at least one affiliation from Greece and are related to CS or crowdsourcing, according to Scopus search

A key aspect of the results is that educational and research clusters in Greece are those leading or participating in citizen science initiatives. Indicatively, at local level in Thessaloniki, the Aristotle University has participated in at least 14 citizen science projects and initiatives since 2017 (64.29% STEM-related and 35.71% non-STEM). Similarly, many CS projects and activities have been carried out by the Centre for Research and Technology and other Universities located in the broader area of the Region of Central Macedonia.

As such, one way to map the trends of the citizen science evolvement in Greece is to say that research and science establishes opportunities to involve and engage the citizens and the general public so as to close the gap, benefit both and bring added value at societal, economic and environmental level.

Figure 2. Mapping of Greek citizen science projects⁵

The case of VGTU (Lithuania)

Citizen Science is considered as the main driver to facilitate and foster more inclusive societies, in a sustainable way, by generating innovation towards addressing major societal problem (Robinson et al., 2018). Engaging a specific interest group is a great challenge, considering that the motivation is not necessarily shared among the participants. Even more, there is a significant number of people among these groups with low digital skills, or even limited relevant resources to access the provided tools and material. In 2017, 43% of the EU population had an insufficient level of digital skills, 17% had none at all, as they either did not use the internet or barely did so, and only about 31% of people were with low education levels or no education (DESI, 2019). It is also very often that the tools that are used to engage the society in activities exclude these groups, eliminating the impact expected and strengthening the social barriers and margins. The citizens and communities in Lithuania remain cautious and hesitant, as technology evolves and it pushes fast societal transformations in everyday habits and norms (Skaržauskienė and Maciuliene, 2020). However, the country has all preconditions to become a "smart" society: relatively high level of the infrastructure of information technologies, high level user

⁵ Bakouši, K (2021). A first approach to citizen science in Greece.

accessibility (high-quality Internet accessible not only in cities but also to 98.7% of rural areas), the small number of inhabitants (2.7 Mln.). The web's growth in reach and capability set the stage for the explosive growth of online communities in Lithuania, but their potential is not used to their fullest due to the lack of citizen engagement. In Lithuania, as well in other post-soviet countries, the common attitude that citizens cannot influence social life or the adopted decisions by government is deeply embedded. The perfect technological pre-conditions do not encourage growth of collective intelligence since people do not collaborate, they express their opinion but do not structure it, and also do not assume obligations to implement decisions (Skaržauskienė, 2015).

CS can effectively serve policy making initiatives and processes by providing evidence and useful insights to support regulatory compliance with a transparent and participatory way and in addition to this, it can also serve society by offering opportunities to address special societal issues that directly affect citizens and effect decision making about these issues at national and EU level (Strasser et al., 2018). A number of policies have been discussed at national layer, although policy makers and stakeholders (including public authorities and other national and EU initiatives) still lack an appropriate readiness level in understanding the innovations brought forward by the citizens' inclusion. Policy makers often have different interest, motivations, expectations and understanding towards the achievements and outcomes of the citizens' science activities and efforts (Butkevičienė, 2020).

From the Lithuanian industry/business perspective, CS could be considered as a possible competitor against well-established large-scale platforms which gain profit from people's data. The barrier to overcome is the identification of right stakeholders in different sectors that can take advantage from the planned CS outcomes. Strengthening communication about the value and opportunities of CS is another big challenge to overcome.

Looking from the academic angle, the major concerns of the Lithuanian researchers` are about how the participatory process could be facilitated to strengthen the role of citizens as key actors in the research "process". Around these challenges, critical barriers that act as most relevant towards an effective collaboration are three dimensions: data, awareness, synergies (Mitchell et al., 2017). The strong focus and risk lay in quality assurance, regulatory framework, all-inclusive schemes for citizens contribution to EC open access policy and fully implements relevant approaches to facilitate scientific results visibility and to support reuse and extension of its CS outputs, as open science contributions.

Another problem is that CS has been predominantly pursued within the realms of the natural sciences (Tauginiene et al., 2020). Activities and projects following social sciences and humanities (SSH) topics and approaches are less easily discernible in CS practices, although they may be fuelled by some genuine and challenging questions (Heiss and Matthes, 2017).

Table 3. Most important enabling and hindering factors for CS at national level

Hindering factors at national level	Enabling factors at national level
From civil society perspective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest and motivation • Low digital skills resources • Available/commonly used practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective communication • Online and offline activities • Close collaboration with local government
From policy makers perspective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different interests' motivation and expectations • Understanding of Citizen Science value, achievements and outcomes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Openness and readiness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active discussions with the communities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact assessment • Inclusive society strategy as Smart specialization for Lithuania
From industry perspective	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders/ market players awareness • Lack of collaboration with universities and researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding opportunities • The involvement of quadruple helix stakeholders in research in Lithuania is increasingly encouraged, but actual involvement is still limited 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU support • There are several institutions encouraging stakeholder involvement in science

Table 4. Most important enabling and hindering factors for CS in VGTU

Hindering factors at VGTU	Enabling factors at VGTU
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of data collected <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of data • Lack of understanding of citizen science in scientific community • Lack of innovative solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open access • Ethics standards in research <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications • Developed university ecosystem (e.g., infrastructure, industry partners, administration) • VGTU's ecosystem includes several dispersed actors interested in promotion of open science, which, if provided with proper support, could enable more coordinated actions

The case of UT (The Netherlands)

This section provides an overview of the status of citizen science in the Netherlands, based on the final report of the Citizen Science Working Group (NPOS, 2020). The Netherlands is among the frontrunner EU countries in the field of citizen science. There is a long tradition of high-profile citizen science projects, ranging from research into particulate matter, medieval texts and benthic animals to research into burial mounds. In this context, citizen science is considered to be highly relevant with both open science and transdisciplinary research (Figure 3). More specifically, citizen science should by definition be open science, while reaching the centre of the cross-section (full transdisciplinary collaboration) is essential for addressing urgent but complex societal and scientific challenges.

Figure 3. Venn diagram for the concepts of citizen science, open science and transdisciplinary research. Source: NPOS, 2020.

During the recent years, the interest in citizen science has increased, not only among professional scientists but also among citizen scientists and civic organisations. This is aligned with the overarching objective to strengthen the connection between science and society and drive scientific research towards serving social purposes. However, structurally connecting actors from the professional scientific world and citizen scientists is still a crucial challenge.

With the growth in the number of citizen science initiatives, the need for knowledge and experience exchange is becoming increasingly clear. To this direction, and aligned with the National Open Science Programme (NPOS) of the Netherlands, the Citizen Science Working Group (CSWG) has been set up to embrace existing and encourage new collaboration structures in the field of citizen science. The working group aims to support the Dutch ambitions in the field of citizen science and provides policymakers, initiators (both scientists and citizen scientists or civic organisations) and financial backers with tools to promote citizen science. To

do so, the working group focuses on innovation in the domain, building on knowledge and expertise from the Netherlands and abroad.

More specifically, the working group defines two core themes for citizen science: **network development** and **quality promotion**. These two themes were identified since the starting point of the working group in 2019 as necessary conditions for the next step in the development of citizen science in the Netherlands. Regarding the first theme, the working group proposes the establishment of a network structure that stimulates collaboration and the sharing of knowledge and experience and fills gaps by connecting new and existing networks. This structure will, moreover, lay fertile ground for innovation in the citizen science domain. The network structure is presented in Figure 4. The board consists of representatives of scientific and social institutions and citizen scientists and is assisted by a scientific-social advisory council. The staff office is placed with a chairing organisation and coordinates, organises, informs, connects and starts or supervises pilot projects.

Figure 4. Network structure for Citizen science Netherlands (CS-NL Network).

To promote the quality and effectiveness (scientific and social success) of citizen science projects, a quality matrix is introduced, which builds on the ten principles for citizen science of the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA, 2015). This tool can also serve for the assessment and evaluation of citizen science activities.

Some examples of citizen science projects in the Netherlands are the following:

1. Waag: citizen sensing in the Province of Noord-Holland
2. University of Twente: TOPFIT Citizen Lab
3. National Institute for Public Health and the Environment: Gezond Sloterveer and Kijk! A healthy community.
4. Leiden University: Citizen Science Lab
5. 'Bodemierendagen' (the Netherlands Institute of Ecology and the Centre for Soil Ecology)

The University of Twente (UT), coordinator of the INCENTIVE project, has also created the "Shaping Expert Group Citizen Science" (SEG-SC) in 2020. This group will develop the Citizen Science component within the Shaping 2030 strategy/ Research Strategy of UT, aiming to connect the outside-in through a citizen science movement to bridge possible gaps between innovation and society. More specifically, the SEG-SC will play a role in supporting researchers and train students in the field of citizen science, thereby increasing the opportunities in research calls that focus on citizen science and help to shape researchers of the future in this field linked to societal challenges.

5. Step 2: Interviews with stakeholders

5.1 Objectives

The next step was the performance of 8 semi-structured interviews with stakeholders from the regional ecosystem of the four participating RPOs, as a means to complement the information found from the literature research at national level in Step 1. The objective was to capture individual experiences, perceptions and attitudes regarding Citizen Science trends, problems and success factors within the four different national settings. Consequently, the core research question of the in-depth interviews was the following: what are the national specificities concerning Citizen Science participation in the examined country, and what are the key obstacles and enablers at the local level.

Since the national literature, that was investigated under Step 1, was proven to be often scarce, the interviews functioned as the optimal complementary technique to fill in missing information and reveal specificities about the local ecosystems that are unknown. The interviews thus facilitated the triangulation of literature findings as means of producing complementary data (Hammersley, 2008).

5.2 Methodology

5.2.1 *Selection of interviewing method and development of interview guide*

The findings from the literature review were calibrated into a single interview guide. Interviews were performed in the form of semi-structured, qualitative interviews. This approach offered flexibility to the interviewer to adapt the sequence of questionnaire items according to the flow of the interviewing process, and to follow-up with probes. A set of questionnaire items were developed based on the literature findings, but these items were not treated as fixed items that the interviewer should adhere to, but rather as baseline points for the discussion with the interviewee. Given that the aim of the interviews was not to confirm with the interviewees pre-existing theoretical insights but rather to produce new knowledge, a semi-structured interview guide was the most appropriate tool (Bryman, 2016).

White Research developed the interview guide and distributed it to all consortium partners to provide their comments. Once WR had incorporated the partners' feedback, the interview guide was finalised and the interviews started. The interview guide consisted of an introductory note and four core parts:

1. **Introduction:** The interviewee was informed about the INCENTIVE project, the concept and the overall purpose of the interview
2. **Opening (warm-up):** The interviewee was asked some opening questions related to their background, familiarity and previous experience with Citizen Science
3. **Main part (core questions):** The interviewee was asked about the current level of maturity and the most recent development of Citizen Science in their country, the most

important factors that either support the initiation and sustainability of, or pose problems to a Citizen Science project in their country, and how these problems can be overcome.

4. **Closing (clean-up):** The interviewee was asked to follow-up with any additional information or thoughts they would like to provide.
5. **Background information:** The interviewee was asked a series of background information, such as nationality and educational level.

The complete version of interview guide can be found on Annex A of the present document.

5.2.2 Participants and procedure

In total, 8 external stakeholders (i.e., stakeholders that do not work in the pilot RPFO of their country) were interviewed – 2 per country. Pilot universities were responsible for suggesting to White Research a list of stakeholders from their regional network (each pilot RPFO suggested at least 3 candidate stakeholders to be interviewed). White Research then selected the stakeholders that would interview, and contacted them to arrange the date and time-slot for the interview. Upon selection, and before the interview, all selected stakeholders were provided with document about the formal privacy policy of the project, while they also had to sign and send to WR a document whereby they were giving their consent to participate in the interview, agreeing that their data could be used for the development of this document. The privacy policy and consent form documents are found on Annex B.

Representation in terms of QH stakeholder groups was considered of outmost importance. Therefore, 2 stakeholders were interviewed per stakeholder group (i.e., 2 from academia, 2 from civil society, 2 from public administration, and 2 from the private sector), while WR ensured that the 2 stakeholders from the same group were coming from different countries.

Interviews lasted approximately 30 to 40 minutes, including the opening and closing sections. Two interviewers participated from the side of White Research. Since the interviews were not recorded for reasons of privacy and ethics, one interviewer was responsible from conducting the questions to the interviewee and guiding the whole process, while the second interviewer was taking notes, with particular emphasis on capturing original phrases and sentences as stated by the interviewee. The second interviewee was also responsible for making ad-hoc interventions and probing.

Upon completion of the interviews, the interviewees were thanked for their participation and informed about the upcoming development of this document. All interviewees' personal data and transcripts were kept by White Research, in line with the overall data management plan of the project.

5.2.3 Data analysis

Once all transcripts were collected and stored in a single database by WR, a qualitative data analysis was performed to transform the raw data and original phrases into meaningful results. To that end, a thematic analysis was considered the most appropriate analytical tool. This type of analysis can be defined as “a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data. It minimally organises and describes your data set in (rich) detail”. Through the thematic analysis, the original data were broken down, re-formulated and re-appeared in the form of organised themes, through which the original data can be understood in new, meaningful lenses (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The main advantage of thematic analysis was the flexibility of the method. In the case of the 8 semi-structured interviews, the type of thematic analysis that was opted for was inductive (i.e., data were coded in an open way, without being added into an existing coding framework), semantic (i.e., data were interpreted into new ways, and not just described, but always within the framework of what the interviewees had said), and realist (i.e., meaning, patterns and themes were theorised in a direct way, avoiding putting the meaning into larger socio-cultural national contexts due to the limited number of interviews per country) (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Initially, transcripts were organised into codes, through a process of open, bottom-up coding, meaning that no particular codes were sought for throughout the data from the beginning. Once the number of all potential codes had been saturated, and no additional codes could be produced (Bryman, 2016), codes were clustered into basic themes, which form the “lowest-order premises evident in the text” (Attride-Stirling, 2001). The basic themes were then grouped to create organising themes, which constitute a higher level of abstract premises. Finally, the organising themes were grouped under global themes, that are the most high-level theoretical categories of the transcripts (Attride-Stirling, 2001). In that case, the global themes already existed in either as barriers and obstacles or as driving factors and enablers. The organising themes were thus fed into one of the two global themes. Regarding saturation, it must be underlined that due to the sampling limitation, the process of saturation focused on the (non) identification of new emerging codes grounded in the existing dataset, rather than on sampling range of the theoretical categories – for that, it could be defined as “inductive thematic saturation”, as proposed by Saunders et al. (2018).

To present all findings into a coherent way, a traditional thematic framework was deployed. The latter can be defined as “a matrix base method for ordering and synthesising data”. To support and substantiate the codes and themes of the matrix, quoted material was retrieved from the transcripts (Bryman, 2016). The matrix offered the possibility to simultaneously examine the themes within each national context, but also under a cross-national, comparative approach, by looking how two or more countries either share or not the same themes. This, in turn, help the reader to identify similarities and differences across national realities (Bryman, 2016).

5.3 Findings

5.3.1 *Hindering factors, barriers and obstacles*

Table 5 presents the thematic framework for the hindering factors, barriers and obstacles, as identified and analysed from the interviews. In total, **7 basic themes** emerged from the analysis:

- (i) **Lack of communication**, which includes lack of physical interaction, lack of awareness, conflicting perspectives from stakeholders, absence of collaboration and lack of information;
- (ii) **Poor planning**, which entails lack of clear targets, inadequate preparation, insufficient scale for implementation, lack of common purpose and poor stakeholder engagement;
- (iii) **Resource insecurity**, which includes time constraints and limitations from the side of citizens, lack of appropriate funding sources and consequent increasing competition for grants, and a general societal insecurity with respect to jobs and decent income;
- (iv) **Insufficient scientific model**, which includes top-down scientific structures, emphasis on particular scientific fields, and power asymmetry between scientific and non-scientific stakeholder groups;
- (v) **Institutional rigidities**, which includes the existence of rigid structures in universities, bureaucratic obstacles, insufficient public administration governance, and lack of integration of Citizen Science in educational curricula;
- (vi) **Motivational deficit**, which includes lack of critical mass and commitment from stakeholder groups to Citizen Science projects, inertia and a general lack of interest from the side of public, a weak civil society, and high levels of attrition during participation; and
- (vii) **Behavioural constraints**, which includes subjective suspiciousness from the side of scientists towards Citizen Science, a biased culture against Citizen Science, and a general introvert attitude from scientists against external stakeholders.

These basic themes formed in turn three higher-level organising themes: (i) **poor organisation and performance**, (ii) **weak governance structures**, and (iii) **socio-cultural inertia and exclusion**.

It is interesting to notice that aside from commonalities, there are differences across countries. In the Netherlands, lack of communication, insufficient scientific models and institutional rigidities appear to be the most recurring themes. In Greece, on the other hand, all identified themes are present, but cultural barriers, attrition and resources insecurity prevail. In Lithuania, poor human capital, elitism from science, a general low economic development level and a subsequently feeble civil society are the most important themes. Finally, in Spain, the current bureaucratic structures and overall academic introversion and suspiciousness from universities and formal scientific centres are the most critical hindering factors. Apparently, and despite the similarities, the overall socio-economic, cultural and political framework in each country heavily impact how Citizen Science is experienced, and therefore different hindering factors dominate.

Table 5. Thematic framework of identified barriers and obstacles to participation to Citizen Science

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles						
Organizing themes	Poor organisation and performance		Weak governance structures			Socio-cultural inertia and exclusion	
Basic themes	Lack of communication	Poor planning	Resource insecurity	Insufficient scientific model	Institutional rigidities	Motivational deficit	Behavioral constraints
Interviewee 1 The Netherlands	Lack of physical interaction: <i>"...communication needs to be face-to-face."</i> Conflictual perspectives Lack of awareness			Top-down structures	Rigid structures in universities: <i>"There is no structure [for citizen science] to fit in."</i>		Suspiciousness: <i>"...the big unreachable academic thing."</i>
Interviewee 2 Greece	Lack of common language: <i>"It is imperative the process is attractive for the participants."</i>	Lack of clear targets: <i>"...you start without knowing to whom to address."</i> Inadequate preparation: <i>"...you have to be very well prepared, otherwise it won't work."</i> Unilateral agendas	Time constraints	Power asymmetry in online workshops	Lack of formalisation Institutional difficulties	Lack of critical mass Lack of commitment Problem with keeping up the pace Inertia	"Business-as-usual" model Suspiciousness on data liability
Interviewee 3 Spain	Disconnection Conflictual perspectives	Insufficient planning Insufficient scale for implementation		Inflexible participatory process	Bureaucracy Insufficient public administration	Lack of interest	Academic introversion

	Lack of collaboration	Lack of common purpose					Different expectations
Interviewee 4 The Netherlands	Lack of physical interaction Conflictual perspectives: "...there are different motivations..."		Lack of funding: "...you need people to be able to be paid for their work [...] need financial support." Dependence on donations Increasing competition for grants	Top-down structures Pressure for commercialization	Lack of marketing skills from academics Limitations from academics	Lack of interest: "...scholars are not interested in leading people in these projects." Lack of incentives	
Interviewee 5 Lithuania	Lack of awareness		Time constraints: "[Citizen Science] means extra work for scholars to train." Lack of funding Economic insecurity: "If you think getting a second job, you wouldn't be thinking doing extra research, right?"	Insufficient recognition on policy level Over-emphasis on hard sciences		Low levels of motivation Poor voluntary engagement Weak civil society	Misperception that working in community does not count Academic introversion

Interviewee 6 Spain			Time constraints: <i>"...people are going to be exhausted."</i>		Lack of formalisation Lack of integration in curricula	Lack of interest: <i>"waste is something that people usually hate [...] not a fancy thing to talk about."</i> Low levels of motivation: <i>"not just work with the usual suspects."</i>	Suspiciousness: <i>"... [scientists believe that] you are not going to get the same data as you would with your scientific team."</i> Different expectations: <i>"...not all of them [i.e., of participants] are willing to engage."</i>
Interviewee 7 Greece			Poor human capital: <i>"...low education level..."</i>			Attrition: <i>"It is a slow process, it takes time."</i>	Cultural bias: <i>"It is really a matter of culture to convince someone that [Citizen Science] can actually help."</i>
Interviewee 8 Lithuania	Elitism: <i>"...new concept for the general public [...] very formal concept [...] not attracting the general public."</i> Lack of information: <i>"...there are few articles in Lithuanian language about the concept [...] there is lack of information, people are not familiar."</i>	Lack of clear post-project strategies Poor stakeholder engagement Absence of concrete milestones	Poor human capital: <i>"There is a digital divide."</i>	Scientific unilateralism: <i>"Natural sciences should not be the only in the core of Citizen Science."</i>			Suspiciousness: <i>"There are plenty of risks related to Citizen Science about data accuracy..."</i> Biased information

5.3.2 *Driving factors and enablers*

Moving on the driving factors and enablers, Table 6 summarises them into the respective thematic framework. Once again, **7 basic themes** were created once codes were re-ordered and clustered:

- (i) **Good communication**, which includes provision of feedback, demonstration of added value to participants, and constant communication between the different stakeholder groups;
- (ii) **Planning and vision**, which includes good metrics and indicators from the beginning, responsibility and allocation of roles, having a clear target audience and vision, and being transparent;
- (iii) **Empathy**, which includes the capacity to understand local realities, needs and reciprocate, as well as the ability to provide appropriate support and respect different stakeholders' views;
- (iv) **Provision of incentives**, which means stimulate enthusiasm, inspire through storytelling, and give monetary rewards to participants;
- (v) **Existence of resources**, which includes having the required time, human capital and economic and technological resources;
- (vi) **Democratic governance**, which includes an open, democratic and tolerant society and political system, transparent structures and power symmetries between stakeholder groups; and
- (vii) **Open structures**, which means that there is space for flexibility and adaptation from the side of scientific stakeholders, but also that the information flow can facilitate the emergence and acceptance of alternative scientific paradigms.

The basic themes are clustered under 3 organising themes: (i) "**strong management and execution**", (ii) "**socioeconomic and political maturity**", and (iii) "**motivational support**".

Similar to the hindering factors, there are interesting commonalities and differences between the four countries. The organising theme "strong management and execution" is present across all countries – a fact that highlights its significance. The organising theme "socioeconomic and political maturity", which is related to governance, political and social dimensions, is recurring in Greece and Lithuania. On the other hand, it must be underlined that the organising theme "motivational support" – entailing empathy and the provision of incentives – is either strongly grounded in some interviewees, or completely absent. Nevertheless, this theme is present in all countries. Finally, Spain stands out for the fact that the basic theme "existence of resources" does not apply in the country.

All the themes and related original quotes from interviewees are presented in detail below.

Table 6. Thematic framework of driving factors and enablers for participation to Citizen Science

Global theme	Driving factors and enablers						
Organizing themes	Strong management and execution		Motivational support		Socioeconomic and political maturity		
Basic themes	Good communication	Planning and vision	Empathy	Provision of incentives	Existence of resources	Democratic governance	Open structures
Interviewee 1 The Netherlands	Feedback: <i>"People need to know how their contribution affects [...] prove that their data are enriching science."</i>	Good metrics Clear vision	Understand new realities Understand local needs Reciprocity and equality	Storytelling of good practices	Time: <i>"...aged people have more spare time."</i> Human capital: <i>"...educational level is important."</i>	Democratic society	
Interviewee 2 Greece	Feedback: <i>"...[participants felt] that their opinions matter".</i>		Continuity and proximity: <i>"...[participants] felt that they were being taken care of..."</i> Psychological support	Enthusiasm Material/monetary rewards		Democratic society	
Interviewee 3 Spain	Demonstration of added value Constant communication	Responsibility: <i>"... [we must pass] from awareness to collective action."</i> Clearly defined goals: <i>"... [we must</i>	Ability to work together Respect: <i>"... [you must] treat citizens as smart people."</i>	Stress relevance: <i>"... problems that are relevant to citizens [...] that appeals them."</i>		Co-design from the beginning	Transformation: <i>"...change [the] mental frames of the people."</i> Space for alternative solutions: <i>"...to</i>

		<p><i>be] honest on what we are going to do."</i></p> <p>Clear role allocation</p> <p>Common objectives</p>					<p><i>see the problem with another view."</i></p>
<p>Interviewee 4 The Netherlands</p>	<p>Feedback: <i>"A human being needs to work in communication feedback."</i></p>	<p>Appropriate scale of implementation</p> <p>Clear target audience</p> <p>Common objectives: <i>"...there must be a shared vision."</i></p>	<p>Respect: <i>"...appreciation of different skills."</i></p>	<p>Enthusiasm: <i>"...passion exists."</i></p> <p>Sense of ownership</p>		<p>Diplomacy</p> <p>Empowerment</p>	<p>Adaptability</p> <p>Flexibility</p>
<p>Interviewee 5 Lithuania</p>	<p>Feedback: <i>"Constantly showing what is the progress of project, so people can see that their contribution matters."</i></p> <p>Demonstration of added value: <i>"I think first of all is showing the benefits of the project to the lay people."</i></p> <p>Constant communication</p>	<p>Clearly defined goals</p> <p>Clear vision</p>					

<p>Interviewee 6 Spain</p>	<p>Demonstration of added value: <i>"The added value of demonstrating the impact of the project is still missing from Citizen Science."</i></p>	<p>Transparency: <i>"If you promise that you are going to change a lot, and then they see that this is not going to happen, you find angry people [...] be honest with the expectations [...] try not to sell things that you are not going to provide."</i></p>				<p>Good public administration Gamification</p>	
<p>Interviewee 7 Greece</p>	<p>Demonstration of added value: <i>"When benefits are straightforward [...] then the initiative will thrive. For instance, we see that in the issue of recycling, participation is receiving attention [...] due to the explicit benefits."</i></p> <p>Feedback: <i>"To maintain something, there must be concrete outcomes [...] so the citizens can understand their own benefits."</i></p>				<p>Human capital: <i>"All these initiatives are based on behavioural models, so they are related to the background of citizens. To this, educational level matters."</i></p> <p>Economic development: <i>"...with new markets, development of new services and products [...] there can be cooperation that leads to win-win outcomes."</i></p>	<p>Networking Partnerships between universities, private sector and public authorities Transparency</p>	<p>Open access Information flow</p>

<p>Interviewee 8 Lithuania</p>	<p>Awareness: <i>"Know the interests of the society"; "Inform about the problems companies have."</i></p> <p>Feedback: <i>"Dialogue is needed."</i></p>		<p>Understand needs: <i>"Take into account needs, interests, and problems the nation is facing."</i></p>	<p>Enthusiasm: <i>"Encourage citizens to become a small scientist."</i></p> <p>Stress relevance: <i>"Being close to research interests."</i></p>	<p>Human capital: <i>"There is need for educated people."</i></p> <p>Infrastructures: <i>"Technological advancements are key enablers to Citizen Science."</i></p>	<p>Cross-stakeholder partnerships: <i>"Cooperation with the business sector [...] dialogue is needed between tech industry and citizen science."</i></p> <p>Bottom-up approach</p>	<p>Openness: <i>"Target other scientific areas."</i></p>
--	---	--	--	--	--	--	--

6. Step 3: Large-scale survey

6.1 Objectives

The aim of the large-scale survey, which constitutes the final step of this large-scale research endeavour, is to quantitatively capture the factors shaping the willingness of the Quadruple Helix stakeholders, and of the general public at large, to actively participate in the Citizen Science Hubs, in the four pilot countries of the project. As such, the survey strives for presenting numeric data and to translate them into meaningful insights regarding general perceptions, patterns, knowledge and attitudes about Citizen Science, as well as to explore which factors affect either positively or negatively participation in Citizen Science activities. The final objective is to supply the four pilot RPFOS (UT, AUTH, UAB, and VGTU) with concrete evidence about their citizens' and stakeholders' views and attitudes, so as to create Citizen Science Hubs that respect these views and therefore can address actual needs and problems.

6.2 Methodology

6.2.1 Sample

The survey uses a quota sample of 1.936 responses in total, from the general public in four countries across Europe: Greece, Lithuania, the Netherlands, and finally Spain. These four countries represent the four pilot RPFOS of the INCENTIVE project. It was decided to collect responses from the national population instead of only from the regional population of the pilot ecosystems. The decision was based on the fact that the project's RPFOS have a nationwide scope in terms of students, visiting personnel and networking channels, and therefore having evidence from the overall national population will help them co-create Citizen Science Hubs that reflect national patterns. Data collection took place from April 2021 to June 2021. Initially, a quota sample of 500 responses was set as target for each country (resulting to 2.000 responses roughly). However, the demographic dynamics and uneven sizes of the selected countries necessitated a different internal division of the sample, so as to achieve representation in terms of actual population sizes. Therefore, following an open deliberation between WR and the pilot partners, it was decided that 350 responses should be collected approximately for the cases of Greece and Lithuania, while 600 responses should be collected approximately for the cases of the Netherlands and Spain.

Apart from the core questionnaire sections (in more detail below), the survey also collected demographic information about the participants, such as educational level, age and occupational status. Another critical element was the classification of responses according to the quadruple helix groups: private sector/industry (e.g., SMEs owners, entrepreneurs, CEOs), public administration (e.g., policy makers, civil servants, elected officials), academia (e.g., professors, researchers) and civil society (e.g., CSOs representatives, NGOs representatives). For participants that were reluctant to choose one the previous categories, the category of "general public", could be selected. Understanding the perceptions and attitudes towards Citizen Science of the last category is particularly important, since Citizen Science Hubs are

expected to pay special attention to ordinary citizens, especially those who are unfamiliar with the concept. A final important point that was collectively agreed by all partners was that the sample should be representative in terms of gender for all countries (see Table 10).

Figure 5. Surveyed countries and distribution of sample.

Source: MapChart.net

White Research was the responsible for drafting the initial questionnaire for the survey. For the creation of the survey, the EC survey platform was used. The questionnaire was then provided to the consortium for further discussion and improvements. After WR has integrated all partners' feedback, the survey was translated into the national languages by the pilot RPFs, and then distributed to them by WR through a survey link. As such, pilot RPFs took over responsibility for collecting the required number of responses and meet the internal quotas. In the cases of Greece and Lithuania, AUTH and VGTU used a variety of dissemination channels respectively to distribute the survey to the general population. These channels included:

- The internal community of the pilot universities (e.g., staff, researchers, students).
- The network of supporting partners that have provided with letters of support to the INCENTIVE project. This network included various stakeholders and organizations.
- Local associations and networks where representatives from the pilot universities' team are active members.
- Stakeholders from the local media who shared the survey in their social media accounts.

In the case of Spain, due to the overall larger national population, an external platform was used to collect the number of responses needed through crowdsourcing. In particular, the [Clickworker](#) platform was used for the dissemination of the survey. Crowdsourcing was selected as the most suitable option to generate a large number of responses in a time- and cost-effective manner. Crowdsourcing platforms, such as Clickworker, allow the recruitment of an independent global workforce for the objective of working on a specifically defined task or set of tasks and provide quick and easy access to data from a large number of participants spanning different geographies, age, sex, educational and professional background, interests, etc. Moreover, despite primary concerns over the equivalence of online data collection in comparison to traditional methods, evidence suggests that there are no significant differences between the two methods. Administering and collecting such a vast number of responses through field research would have been prohibiting either due to logistical considerations such as time and monetary resources or participants' availability. Finally, in the case of the Netherlands, the external agency Markeffect was commissioned to disseminate the survey and collect the answers. The selection was justified on the basis of the considerable population size of the country, similar to the case of Spain. The fact that crowdsourcing was used for Spain and an external agency was commissioned for the Netherlands explain also the differences of the uneven division of the total sample from a practical point of view (even though it was decided among partners that the sample division should roughly mirror the unequal sizes of the national populations from the 4 countries, as previously explained).

Once all pilot RPOs have met their internal quotas, WR closed the survey and started the analysis of the data.

6.2.2 Questionnaire structure

Based on the results from the qualitative literature review (step 1) and semi-structured interviews (step 2), that have identified the current state-of-the-art in terms of trends, barriers and drivers of Citizen Science in each pilot country, the survey questionnaire was structured so as to get additional insights about these aspects, and quantitatively confirm the findings from the previous analysis. The descriptive characteristics of the sample and the distribution of the collected responses are presented in detail in Section 7.3.1.

Regarding the process of the questionnaire development, WR has incorporated the findings from the literature review and thematic analysis and presented a draft version of the questionnaire to the consortium, for peer-review and discussion. The final version of the survey questionnaire reconciles – to the extent possible – the range of views and opinions from all partners and can be found on Annex D.

The survey questions were clustered in 6 main sections, each of which corresponds to a research question. Each section and its rationale are presented briefly below:

- 1. Section 1 – Introduction to the topic:** In this section, stakeholders' views were captured regarding their level of familiarity with concepts such as Citizen Science and Responsible Research and Innovation, as well as their type of previous experience with Citizen

Science, if any. The second question aims at identifying insights about general public perceptions regarding future trajectories of the regions.

2. **Section 2 – Perceptions towards Citizen Science:** In this section, stakeholders, opinion was asked about Citizen Science in general, such as what are the most significant benefits of Citizen Science, what should be the role of citizens in CS activities, and how the envisioned pilot CS Hubs should respond to current needs.
3. **Section 3 – Barriers:** In this section, the most important barriers to participation in CS activities were captured, with particular emphasis on citizens' concerns about potential drawbacks of and obstacles to Citizen Science.
4. **Section 4 – Drivers:** In this section, the most important driving factors and enablers of CS activities were captured. The focus was on the factors that motivate citizens to participate in a CS initiative, as well as how they would like a CS project to unfold.
5. **Section 5 – Willingness to join:** In this section, the preferred scientific topics and stages of CS activities were captured, with the aim to understand what fields attract most people and in which phases they would like to be involved.
6. **Section 6 – General information:** This section includes basic demographic information such as sex, age, country, educational background, occupational status and others.

All demographic information was collected in compliance with the general data protection regulation (GDPR) of the European Union and used solely for research and statistical reasons. In addition, to participate in the survey all research subjects had to fill-in a consent form that was included in the introductory session of the questionnaire. Finally, the management of datasets including such information adheres to the project's data management plan.

6.3 Findings

6.3.1 Demographics and sample structure

The large-scale survey tried to capture the current state-of-the-art in the four different countries of pilot RPFOs (Greece, Lithuania, the Netherlands, and Spain), by collecting ~2.000 questionnaires in total. Table 7 indicates the final numbers of collected questionnaires.

Table 7. Number of observations by country

Country	Observations	Percentage
Greece	322	16.63%
Lithuania	342	17.67%
Netherlands	675	34.86%
Spain	597	30.84%
Observations	1936	100.00%

In order to better understand the survey results, an initial descriptive analysis of the sample for each country is needed. This provides all the necessary information regarding the type of

stakeholders that have participated in our survey, alongside their demographic characteristics (age, sex, education level and occupational status). In this regard, Tables 8 and 9 present the overall sample structure (per absolute value⁶ and percentage, respectively), highlighting that it is gender balanced in all countries. In terms of age structure, the Greek sample is characterised by an increased share of persons between 20-29 years old (40.68%) compared to other regions, followed by a very low share of under 20 years old (8.07%) and 60+ years old group of participants (5.28%). On the other hand, the opposite trend is observed in the Netherlands, where people from 60+ years old group form the majority (37.33%), with the shares of participants from other age groups decreasing in the same manner as the age intervals decrease. In Spain, the vast majority of respondents fall under the age groups 20-29 and 30-39 years old (64.16%), while participation from under 20 years old and 60+ years old group is marginal. Finally, in Lithuania, there is a more even distribution regarding participation from the different age groups, with people belonging to 40-49 years old age group being the majority.

When taking a closer look at the educational structure of the national samples, the distribution between the four pilots shows strong deviations. Although in all cases no education covers less than 5% of the samples, secondary education in the case of the Netherlands covers almost half of the collected sample (42,88%). At the same time, tertiary education shares, including both bachelor's degree and master's degree levels of tertiary education, are higher for the cases of Greece (57.63%), Lithuania (76.97%), and Spain (58.49%). It is also noticeable that in Greece, almost 1 out of 4 participants hold a PhD or equivalent (24.22%).

Stakeholder distribution is of equal importance to understand better the national samples. For the case of Lithuania, the distribution of stakeholders is interestingly even, with almost all categories having a share of roughly 20%, except from participants from the general public and civil society (43.28%). On the other hand, both in the cases of the Netherlands and Spain, the majority of respondents come from the general public/civil society (60.00% and 43.05%, respectively). However, the two countries differ regarding the distribution among the other stakeholder groups. In Spain, academic stakeholders come second (25.80%), while in the Netherlands the second highest stakeholder group is industry (21.04%). Finally, in Greece stakeholders from academia form the majority of participants, with a noticeable share of 63.04%.

The last demographic insight that we used for describing our samples refers to the occupational status of our survey participants. In this case, the majority in all cases – with the exception of Greece – refers to employed persons, which cover almost half or more than half of the national samples: 68.32% in Lithuania, 51.11% in the Netherlands, and 49.16% in Spain. Some particularities that differ between countries include the following: (i) high shares of students in Greece (42.50%); (ii) high levels of unemployed in Spain (17.62%); (iii) high share of retired

⁶ For some demographic variables, response was optional. That explains the differences in the total sum of answers.

persons in the Netherlands (24.44%); and finally (iv) very low shares of household activity for Greece, Lithuania, and Spain.

Table 8. Sample distribution by demographics and QH group

Gender	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
Male	45,03% (145)	42,69% (146)	50,96% (344)	48,41% (289)
Female	54,97% (177)	57,31% (196)	49,04% (331)	51,59% (308)
Total	100,00% (322)	100,00% (342)	100,00% (675)	100,00% (597)
Age	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
Under 20 years	8,07% (26)	0,88% (3)	1,93% (13)	4,52% (27)
20-29 years	40,68% (131)	16,67% (57)	12,00% (81)	36,52% (218)
30-39 years	17,08% (55)	28,07% (96)	13,19% (89)	27,64% (165)
40-49 years	13,98% (45)	30,12% (103)	16,30% (110)	20,44% (122)
50-59 years	14,91% (48)	19,88% (68)	19,26% (130)	9,55% (57)
60+ years	5,28% (17)	4,39% (15)	37,33% (252)	1,34% (8)
Total	100,00% (322)	100,00% (342)	100,00% (675)	100,00% (597)
Educational level	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
Less than a High School Diploma	0,00% (0)	0,00% (0)	4,01% (27)	5,04% (30)
High School Diploma	18,07% (58)	9,15% (29)	42,88% (289)	34,12% (203)
Bachelor's Degree or equivalent	30,84% (99)	26,50% (84)	27,30% (184)	35,63% (212)
Master's Degree or equivalent	26,79% (86)	50,47% (160)	20,62% (139)	22,86% (136)
PhD or equivalent	24,30% (78)	13,88% (44)	5,19% (35)	2,35% (14)
Total	100,00% (322)	100,00% (342)	100,00% (675)	100,00% (597)
Stakeholder group	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
Academia / Research	63,04% (203)	21,35% (73)	12,59% (85)	25,80% (154)
Public administration	10,87% (35)	19,30% (66)	6,37% (43)	8,21% (49)
Private sector/ Industry	7,14% (23)	16,08% (55)	21,04% (142)	22,95% (137)
Civil society / General public	18,95% (61)	43,28% (148)	60,00% (405)	43,05% (257)
Total	100,00% (322)	100,00% (342)	100,00% (675)	100,00% (597)
Occupational status	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
Employed	41,88% (134)	68,32% (220)	51,11% (345)	49,16% (293)
Unemployed	2,81% (9)	2,48% (8)	2,67% (18)	17,62% (105)
Self-employed/entrepreneur	10,31% (33)	15,84% (51)	7,56% (51)	10,40% (62)
Student	42,50% (136)	9,94% (32)	3,85% (26)	18,62% (111)
Household activity	0,31% (1)	0,93% (3)	6,07% (41)	1,01% (6)
Retired	0,94% (3)	1,55% (5)	24,44% (165)	1,34% (8)
Other	1,25% (4)	0,93% (3)	4,30% (29)	1,85% (11)
Total	100,00% (322)	100,00% (342)	100,00% (675)	100,00% (597)

Table 9. Representativeness of sample in terms of gender

Gender	Greece		Lithuania		Netherlands		Spain	
	Sample	National population						
Male	45,03%	48,66%	42,69%	46,68%	50,96%	49,68%	48,41%	49,01%
Female	54,97%	51,34%	57,31%	53,32%	49,04%	50,32%	51,59%	50,99%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%

The sample accomplished representativeness in terms of gender, which was the core requirement, as collectively agreed by all partners. Table 9 shows the gender breakdown both at sample level and national population level for each country. As it can be observed, in all countries the sample ratios correspond roughly to the gender ratio at national population level (with Spain reaching the highest level of representativeness). Furthermore, with the minor exception of the Netherlands, in all countries the golden standard of women exceeding men proportionately, has been respected. The figures for national population have been retrieved by Statista (2021, 26/07, last accessed), and refer to year 2020.

6.3.2 Familiarity and previous experience with Citizen Science

The next of the descriptive analysis is to explore the level of familiarity with the term "Citizen Science". To ensure that all participants approach the concept in an identical way, a description of the term was provided in the survey questionnaire as follows: "Citizen science refers to the active engagement of the general public in scientific research tasks of several disciplines (from natural sciences to social sciences and humanities) and the collaborative production of new knowledge". This definition was selected as the most inclusive one, so people from different countries and therefore socio-economic and cultural settings could easily understand the term and provide valid answers. Figure 6 presents the level of familiarity with the term for all countries, in a scale from 1 to 5, with 1 indicating total absence of familiarity, and 5 indicating very high levels of familiarity.

Interestingly enough, results reveal that the lowest levels of familiarity are detected in the Netherlands (57.60%) and Lithuania (57.60%). Spain presents a more balanced distribution of scales of familiarity, even though people who declare that they are "somewhat familiar" form the majority (26.97%). Nevertheless, more than 1 out of 4 participants in Spain state that they are completely unfamiliar with the term. Greece shows some common patterns with Spain. On the one hand, the largest proportion of participants (30.12%) fall under the category "not at all familiar". On the other hand, people who state that they are "somewhat familiar" form the second highest category, with 23.60%. At the same time, across all countries, Spain and Greece have the highest shares of people who say that they are extremely familiar with the term (7.54% and 8.07%, respectively).

Nevertheless, it must be stressed that the national variations on the awareness of CS can be partly explained by the age groups and educational level of participants. For instance, the higher levels of awareness in Spain and Greece are influenced by the fact that CS is a quite new concept and in those countries the percentage of 20-29 years old is higher with respect to Netherlands and Lithuania. Moreover, in Greece, half of participants hold either a Master's

degree or PhD, and there may be a positive correlation between educational level and level of CS awareness. At the same time, more than 4 out of 10 participants in the Netherlands hold only a high school diploma – a fact that may affect how knowledgeable are about Citizen Science. Background variables must be taken into account when unpacking the reasons of awareness levels.

Apart from examining the level of familiarity with Citizen Science, the degree of familiarity with the term "Responsible Research and Innovation" was investigated as well. As in the case of Citizen Science, a definition was provided to participants in the questionnaire: "Responsible Research and Innovation is an approach that anticipates and assesses potential implications and societal expectations with regard to research and innovation, with the aim to foster the design of inclusive and sustainable research and innovation". This definition was chosen because it is the official definition by the European Commission (2021, 07/07, last accessed). Figure 7 presents the different levels of familiarity across all countries.

What is interesting to observe in the figure is the similarities with Figure 6. In other words, once again in the Netherlands and Lithuania, the majority of participants (43.11% and 45.32%, respectively), belong to the category "not at all familiar". Reversely, Spain and Greece show the lowest levels from all countries regarding the category "not at all familiar" (14.41% and 19.25% respectively), while in the other side of the spectrum, they display high shares of participants who declare that they are "moderately familiar" with the term (25.29% and 23.29%, respectively). It is also worth-mentioning that in all countries, an interval of 20-25% of participants falls under the category "slightly familiar" with the term. Still, a general conclusion that can be drawn from both Figure 6 and Figure 7 is that the terms "Citizen Science" and "Responsible Research and Innovation" are not yet widely diffused in the general public.

Figure 6. Level of familiarity with the term "Citizen Science"

Figure 7. Level of familiarity with the term "Responsible Research and Innovation"

Table 10 deals with the previous experience, if any, with Citizen Science from participants from all pilot countries. In this case, all national countries show exactly the same trends: more than 8 out of 10 respondents have not any previous experience whatsoever with the Citizen Science activities. On the other hand, it should be mentioned that Greece and Lithuania present the highest shares of people who have some previous experience (18.32% and 18.42%, respectively).

Table 10. Previous experience with Citizen Science

Previous experience	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
No	81,68%	81,58%	85,63%	86,10%
Yes	18,32%	18,42%	14,37%	13,90%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%

The participants who answered "Yes" in the survey questionnaire were re-directed to another question that captures the precise type of previous experience with Citizen Science (Figure 8). Strong differences can be observed between pilot countries. In Lithuania (63.39%) and Spain (38.27%), most people responded that their type of experience is "I have heard the term Citizen Science". However, in the Netherlands, more than half of the sample (52.17%) stated that they initiated and/or designed themselves a citizen science project – this finding strongly contrasts the findings from the other countries. Finally, in Greece, almost half of participants (45.76%) selected the category "I have participated myself in a citizen science project".

As general conclusion, it can be inferred that the maturity level of Citizen Science varies across countries, and even if two countries show commonalities, there are still differences with respect to the actual type of experience of the general public with CS activities. This necessitates different governance structures and possibly dissemination and engagement channels for the development of proper Citizen Science Hubs that respond to local social realities.

Figure 8. Type of previous experience with Citizen Science

Tables 11-14 present the results for the factors acting as significant benefits, drivers and barriers for citizen science projects related to the different types of stakeholders. To do so, the collected data from all pilot countries based on the type of stakeholder categorization were analysed and therefore, it was possible to get some specific insights about each type separately. Starting from the academics and the researchers that participated in the survey (Table 11), they have highlighted all identified benefits – apart from considering citizen science as a hobby – as significant for their perceptions and involvement in citizen science projects. In terms of drivers, their involvement seems to be motivated by continuous feedback, acknowledgements, inspiring coordination teams and clear guidelines and instructions. Barriers related to their perceptions include concerns whether they belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community, lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback, scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups and fear that the project will not be properly organized and managed.

At this point, it must be stressed that all the identified factors that encourage or hinder participation with respect to CS activities, were statistically analysed and then selected as most important. This is valid for the hindering/enabling factors that were examined both for each stakeholder group and for the local ecosystems of the pilot RPOs (Section 6.3.3). The factors that were found to be statistically significant (i.e., they have an important impact on the perception or involvement of participants) are marked with a tick sign in all respective tables. More detail on the statistical method that was used and on the initial results that emerged from the statistical analysis can be found on Annex C.

Table 11 Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for academics and researchers

Benefits	Perception	Involvement
Benefits related to the individual (economic, social, educational).	✓	
Benefits related to knowledge and skills.	✓	✓
Benefits derived when considering citizen science as a hobby.		
Benefits related to new professional/career opportunities.	✓	✓
Benefits related to society and/or natural environment.	✓	✓
Drivers	Perception	Involvement
Continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project	✓	✓
Acknowledgement of the contribution.		✓
The project is well-organized and managed		
Inspiring coordination team		✓
Clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks	✓	✓
Barriers	Perception	Involvement
Lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities.		
Lack of the technological equipment that might be required.		
Belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community	✓	
Lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback.	✓	
Low participation rate.		
Fear that the contribution will be exploited by scientists/policy makers.		
Fear of leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions.		✓
Lack of time to participate in such activities.		✓
Lack of financial incentives to participate.		
Fear of not finding an interesting research topic.		✓
Scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.	✓	✓
Fear that the project will not be properly organized and managed.	✓	✓

Source: Authors' elaborations (see Annex C for the detailed statistical results).

When taking a closer look at the responses received from policymakers, it is obvious that fewer factors can be captured referring to these aspects (Table 12). More specifically, benefits related to society and/or natural environment are the only significant factor in the first group, alongside with continuous feedback, inspiring coordinators and clear guidance that can work as significant drivers for policymakers and stakeholders coming from the public sector. Moreover, barriers related to their involvement in citizen science projects include lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback.

Table 12. Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for policy-makers

Benefits	Perception	Involvement
Benefits related to the individual (economic, social, educational).		
Benefits related to knowledge and skills.		
Benefits derived when considering citizen science as a hobby.		
Benefits related to new professional/career opportunities.		
Benefits related to society and/or natural environment.	✓	✓
Drivers	Perception	Involvement
Continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project	✓	✓
Acknowledgement of the contribution.		
The project is well-organized and managed		
Inspiring coordination team		✓
Clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks	✓	
Barriers	Perception	Involvement
Lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities.		
Lack of the technological equipment that might be required.		
Belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community		
Lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback.		✓
Low participation rate.		
Fear that the contribution will be exploited by scientists/policy makers.		✓
Fear of leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions.		
Lack of time to participate in such activities.		
Lack of financial incentives to participate.		
Fear of not finding an interesting research topic.		
Scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.	✓	✓
Fear that the project will not be properly organized and managed.		

Source: Authors' elaborations (see Annex C for the detailed statistical results).

Table 13 presents the findings in relation to participants from the business and the private sector. Again, almost all factors included in the benefits' list can significantly improve perceptions and involvement of this group in citizen science projects. Drivers in this case include – once more – continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project, together with good organization and management. At the same time, barriers referring to perceptions highlight the importance of the lack of the technological equipment that might be required, receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback, the feeling of belonging to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community, as well as concerns about the ability to effectively cooperate with other stakeholder groups. When it comes to actual involvement in citizen science project, the identified barriers include low participation rates and lack of time to participate in such activities from persons in the private sector.

Table 13. Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for business and private sector

Benefits	Perception	Involvement
Benefits related to the individual (economic, social, educational).	✓	✓
Benefits related to knowledge and skills.	✓	✓
Benefits derived when considering citizen science as a hobby.		
Benefits related to new professional/career opportunities.	✓	
Benefits related to society and/or natural environment.	✓	✓
Drivers	Perception	Involvement
Continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project	✓	✓
Acknowledgement of the contribution.		
The project is well-organized and managed	✓	
Inspiring coordination team		
Clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks		
Barriers	Perception	Involvement
Lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities.		
Lack of the technological equipment that might be required.	✓	
Belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community	✓	
Lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback.	✓	
Low participation rate.		✓
Fear that the contribution will be exploited by scientists/policy makers.		
Fear of leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions.		
Lack of time to participate in such activities.		✓
Lack of financial incentives to participate.		
Fear of not finding an interesting research topic.		
Scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.	✓	
Fear that the project will not be properly organized and managed.		

Source: Authors' elaborations (see Annex C for the detailed statistical results).

The final stakeholder group under investigation refers to citizens and the civil society. Table 14 shows that all identified benefits seem to motivate general public towards participating and having an increased perception of citizen science initiatives. In terms of drivers, even though being acknowledged for your contribution and provided with specific guidelines and instructions for the tasks can boost positive perceptions, only receiving continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project seems to effectively improve participation in citizen science projects by general public. At the same time, it is interesting to notice that there are more barriers that affect both perceptions and involvement when compared to the other stakeholder groups. Common barriers between these two attitudes include: lack of the technological equipment, fear that the contribution will be exploited by scientists/policy makers, fear of leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions and scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups. Barriers that are solely related to overall perception

about citizen science refer to the lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities, the feeling of belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community, the lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback and fear that the project will not be properly organized and managed. Finally, additional barriers that significantly affect citizens' involvement in these initiatives include low participation rates, lack of time and fear of not finding an interesting research topic.

Table 14. Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for civil society and general public

Benefits	Perception	Involvement
Benefits related to the individual (economic, social, educational).	✓	✓
Benefits related to knowledge and skills.	✓	✓
Benefits derived when considering citizen science as a hobby.	✓	
Benefits related to new professional/career opportunities.		✓
Benefits related to society and/or natural environment.	✓	✓
Drivers	Perception	Involvement
Continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project	✓	✓
Acknowledgement of the contribution.	✓	
The project is well-organized and managed		
Inspiring coordination team		
Clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks	✓	
Barriers	Perception	Involvement
Lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities.	✓	
Lack of the technological equipment that might be required.	✓	✓
Belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community	✓	
Lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback.	✓	
Low participation rate.		✓
Fear that the contribution will be exploited by scientists/policy makers.	✓	✓
Fear of leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions.	✓	✓
Lack of time to participate in such activities.		✓
Lack of financial incentives to participate.		
Fear of not finding an interesting research topic.		✓
Scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.	✓	✓
Fear that the project will not be properly organized and managed.	✓	

Source: Authors' elaborations (see Annex C for the detailed statistical results).

The next section presents a more thorough descriptive analysis on the trends and patterns in each of the four pilot countries, with the aim to provide a more detailed picture of attitudes, perceptions and propensities at national level.

6.3.3 Statistical analysis at national level

Greece (AUTH)

The first country to be presented with regards to the statistical analysis is Greece. Figure 99 displays a number of results that refer to eight questionnaire items of the survey about general perceptions and views on both Citizen Science as practice, but also the envisioned Citizen Science Hub that will be established and operationalise in Aristotle University of Thessaloniki.

To begin with, it is interesting to notice that even though the overall perception of Citizen Science is positive among citizens (77% replied either "Agree or Strongly Agree"), 1 out of 5 respondents state their uncertainty about the positive dimensions of the concept (Q5_1). This scepticism is complemented by the fact that in Q9_1 – "In my opinion, citizens should have an active role in the design and execution of scientific projects", 34% of the respondents – which equals 1 out of 3 – adopted a neutral position ("neither agree, nor disagree"), while 13% said that they disagree. This is important, because the neutral 34% is exactly the same as the positive 34% of respondents who selected "I agree".

With respect to the citizens' abilities to participate in Citizen Science activities, the vast majority agreed (33%) or strongly agreed (47%) with the necessity to first provide adequate training to citizens, with only 4% disagreeing (Q9_3). However, opinions are divided regarding whether citizens have the required skills and knowledge for actual participation (Q9_2). Even though most participants agreed that citizens lack the necessary skills and know-how, 20% disagreed with the statement and 6% strongly disagreed. This dichotomy becomes more complex by adding a 33% of neither agreeing nor disagreeing.

Moving on the role that Citizen Science Hubs should have upon development, a number of insights emerged from the analysis. There is a general agreement that the Hubs should provide a space for discussion about scientific progress and societal challenges (Q7_1), since 73% - almost 3 out of 4 – either agreed or strongly agreed. In Q7_2, it is demonstrated that participants support the enhancement of soft and technical skills through the Hubs (49% strongly agreed and 40% agreed). On the other hand, in Q7_3 – "I would like Citizen Science Hubs to empower citizens to become more actively involved in science and initiate their own citizen science projects", there is more scepticism among respondents, despite the general support, since 22% decided neither to agree nor disagree.

This picture is roughly the same concerning the involvement of vulnerable groups in the Hubs (Q7_4). There, 80% either agreed or strongly agreed, and 14% remain neutral. Nonetheless, an evident split is detected in Q9_1 – "In my opinion, citizens should have an active role in the design and execution of scientific projects". No category is prevailed, with people who agreed and those who neither agreed nor disagreed having both a 34%. In addition, 13% disagreed with the statement. These results corroborate the finding that in Greece many citizens are still reluctant about the level of general public's involvement in Citizen Science, and that a very active engagement would not be yet widely accepted.

Q5_1. My overall perception of Citizen science is positive

Q7_1. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to act as open places for discussion about scientific progress and societal challenges

Q7_2. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to enhance soft and technical skills and improve citizens' understanding of scientific knowledge

Q7_3. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to empower citizens to become more actively involved in science and initiate their own citizen science projects

Q7_4. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to involve vulnerable groups.

Q9_1. In my opinion, citizens should have an active role in the design and execution of scientific projects

Q9_2. In my opinion, citizens lack the knowledge and skills to be part of the scientific process

Q9_3. In my opinion, citizens need to be trained in order to participate in science

Figure 9. General perceptions about Citizen Science and Citizen Science Hubs in Greece

Figure 10 presents the willingness to join Citizen Science activities, as expressed per QH stakeholder groups. Overall, the patterns are even between the different stakeholder groups. In all stakeholder groups, almost half, or more than half of participants agreed that they would join a CS activity, even though it is interesting to highlight that among the groups, the lowest percentage comes from academia (47.78%) and the largest from public administration (57.14%). However, regarding the trends on the participants who strongly agreed about participating in CS, the highest percentage comes from of scientific stakeholders (27.09%), and the lowest (19.76%) from the general public and civil society. On the other side, compared to the other groups, academia has the highest shares of aggregated disagreement: more than 5% either disagreed or strongly disagreed. Still, it is the private sector that concentrates the highest percentage of people who disagreed with the statement (4.35%, as opposed to 2.46% from academia). Finally, it should be mentioned that the general public/civil society demonstrates the lowest levels regarding disagreement.

Figure 10. Willingness to join Citizen Science activities in Greece (per stakeholder group)

Figure 11 shows the main topics of interest per stakeholder group for the Greek case. As we can see, there are some common topics between the different types of stakeholders, such as

energy and sustainability, educational and environmental sciences. However, we can see that there are some specific topics that are of interest only in some of the quadruple helix groups. More specifically, we can see that topics related to public administration and policy are of high interest in the case of stakeholders coming from the public sector (as expected), circular economy, human media interaction and communication science are in the centre of attention when it comes to stakeholders from the business sector, whilst health and educational services lie in the heart of interest when it comes to citizens and academics.

Figure 12 *Figure 11. Topics of interest in Greece (per stakeholder group)*

presents the various stages in which the different stakeholder groups are interested in participating. The findings show that participants from academia are mostly interested in designing studies and analysing data, policymakers want to be involved in the interpretation of results, persons from the business sector like identifying research questions and exploiting results, whilst citizens focus on data collection.

Figure 11. *Topics of interest in Greece (per stakeholder group)*

Figure 12. Stage of the research process that you like to be involved (per stakeholder group)

When taking a closer look at the factors affecting participants' opinion, our results suggest that almost all the identified factors can act as significant benefits for increasing perceptions and involvement in citizen science projects for the case of Greece (Table 15). These include individual benefits, benefits related to knowledge and skills, new professional opportunities, society and natural environment. In terms of drivers, continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project, together with acknowledgement processes of each person's contribution, are essential for increasing participation in citizen science projects. Moreover, clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks is another important factor. Barriers related to perceptions are very limited, focusing mostly on potential scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups and concerns that the project will not be properly organized and managed.

Table 15 Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for Greece

Benefits	Perceptions	Involvement
Benefits related to the individual (economic, social, educational).	✓	✓
Benefits related to knowledge and skills.	✓	✓
Benefits derived when considering citizen science as a hobby.		
Benefits related to new professional/career opportunities.	✓	✓
Benefits related to society and/or natural environment.	✓	✓
Drivers	Perceptions	Involvement
Continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project	✓	✓

Acknowledgement of the contribution (e.g., certificate, monetary rewards, public acknowledgment)	✓	✓
The project is well-organized and managed		
Inspiring coordination team		
Clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks	✓	
Barriers	Perceptions	Involvement
Lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities.		✓
Lack of the technological equipment that might be required (e.g., personal computer, smartphone, internet access).		
Belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community		
Lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback during the project.		
Low participation rate.		✓
Fear that the contribution will be exploited by scientists/policy makers.		
Fear of leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions.		
Lack of time to participate in such activities.		✓
Lack of financial incentives to participate.		
Fear of not finding an interesting research topic.		
Scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.	✓	✓
Fear that the project will not be properly organised and managed.	✓	

Source: Authors' elaborations (see Annex C for the detailed statistical results).

Lithuania (VGTU)

Moving on to the findings from Lithuania, Figure 13 presents the results from 8 different questionnaire items that pertain to overall perceptions and views on Citizen Science as concept, as well as the Citizen Science Hub that will be established in the premises of VGTU. Compared to the results from Greece, which were analysed in the previous sections, the findings from Lithuania indicate even sharper divisions regarding both the value of Citizen Science and the role that the Hub should play as testbed for institutionalised CS activities.

Starting with Q5_1 – “My overall perception of Citizen Science is positive”, even though 4 out of 10 participants (41%) either agree or strongly agree, it is noticeable that almost 30% of respondents selected to either disagree (16%) or strongly disagree (13%). Another 30% had a neutral position, complementing the complicated landscape about the society's perspective on CS.

The same patterns can be observed concerning the role of Citizen Science Hubs. The majority of respondents agree (30%) that the Hubs should act as open spaces for discussion on science and societal challenges (Q7_1). Nevertheless, next to that figure, a 28% of participants neither agree nor disagree, whereas 19% disagree. Results are almost identical concerning Q7_2 about the contribution of the Hubs to the enhancement of soft and technical skills of general public. Once again, 30% replied that they agree, and 28% decided to neither agree nor disagree. Disagreement level was slight lower, at 18%; still, the figures highlight that public opinion is

divided on the actual contribution of the Hubs. Results from Q7_3 – “I would like Citizen Science Hubs to empower citizens to become more actively involved in science and initiate their own citizen science projects” are in line with previous findings. A worth-mentioning difference is the reversed figures regarding people who agreed (28%) and people who neither agree nor disagree (30%, a figure that renders them majority). In addition, 19% expressed their disagreement. Opinions are even more conflicting on the inclusion of vulnerable groups in the operational schemes of the Hubs (Q7_4). Participants who neither agree nor disagree form the majority (32%), while those agreeing and those disagreeing with the involvement of vulnerable segments of the population are almost even, with 25% and 19% respectively.

The overall perception is more positive when it comes to the role and capacities of citizens in CS activities. 45% of participants either agreed (32%) or strongly agreed (13%) that citizens should have an active role in designing and implementing scientific projects (Q9_1). On the other hand, almost 1 out of 3 respondents neither agreed nor disagreed, and 18% opposed the idea. Regarding Q9_2 on whether citizens lack the necessary skills and Q9_3 on the subsequent necessity to train citizens in order to be involved in scientific activities, the public opinion is relatively more ambivalent. In both questionnaire items, the level of agreement and the level of neither agreement nor disagreement is almost the same, with those agreeing slightly being the majority. This shows a general consistency between results, since it follows naturally that respondents who advocate that those citizens who lack the scientific expertise must first be adequately trained. The latter point is explicitly supported by the fact that 22% strongly agreed that citizens need to be trained.

Q5_1. My overall perception of Citizen science is positive

Q7_1. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to act as open places for discussion about scientific progress and societal challenges

Q7_2. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to enhance soft and technical skills and improve citizens' understanding of scientific knowledge

Q7_3. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to empower citizens to become more actively involved in science and initiate their own citizen science projects

Q7_4. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to involve vulnerable groups.

Q9_1. In my opinion, citizens should have an active role in the design and execution of scientific projects

Q9_2. In my opinion, citizens lack the knowledge and skills to be part of the scientific process

Q9_3. In my opinion, citizens need to be trained in order to participate in science

Figure 13. General perceptions about Citizen Science and Citizen Science Hubs in Lithuania

In Figure 14, the willingness to join CS activities in Lithuania is presented and broken down per QH stakeholder group. In general, in most stakeholder groups, the majority of participants agree, thus showing willingness to participate. The highest levels of agreement come from academic stakeholders, with 43.84% agreeing and 1 out of 4 respondents (24.66%) strongly agreeing, contrary to previous findings that highlight the biases from academic community towards CS. Public administration is also positively positioned, with more than half of participants (60.61%) agreeing to be willing to join CS activities. General public/civil society participants are also eager to support the participation in CS activities, since more than 41% agreed and a further 10.81% strongly agreed. On the other hand, interestingly enough, the highest levels of rejection come from both the private sectors and the general public. In the case of the private sector, the majority of participants either disagreed (21.82%) or strongly disagreed (16.36%). Once these two figures are aggregated, they result to 38.18%, surpassing the 34.55% of neither agreeing nor disagreeing. Finally, regarding the general public/civil society, when combining "disagree" and "strongly disagree", the result is 22.98%, which however does not surpass the sum of "agree" and "strongly agree" (52.03% in total). 25% neither agreed nor disagreed.

Figure 14. Willingness to join Citizen Science activities in Lithuania (per stakeholder group)

Figure 155 shows the main topics of interest per stakeholder group for Lithuania. As we can see, topics related to educational and communication sciences, as well as information technologies are essential for stakeholders being part of the academia. Moreover, participants coming from public administration are interested to a large extent in public administration and policy issues, alongside human media interactions and communication sciences. Private sector stakeholders mostly focus on circular economy and information technologies, whereas citizens are interested in health, human media interactions and environmental sciences.

Figure 15. **Topics of interest in Lithuania (per stakeholder group)**

presents the various stages in which the different stakeholder groups are interested in participating. We can see that participants from academia are mostly interested in identifying research questions, collecting and analysing data. At the same time, policymakers also want to be involved in the interpretation of results, whilst stakeholders coming from the private sector are interested in interpreting and exploiting research outcomes. Finally, citizens focus on data collection, analysis and interpretation.

Figure 15. **Topics of interest in Lithuania (per stakeholder group)**

Figure 16. Stage of the research process that you like to be involved (per stakeholder group)

In the case of Lithuania, Table 16 shows that benefits related to knowledge and skills, alongside aspects related to society and environment can boost perceptions around citizen science, whereas benefits related to new career opportunities can effectively promote involvement in these projects. Good organization and management, together with clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks are key elements for positive perceptions, whilst continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the projects can act a significant driver for involvement. Barriers for increased perceptions refer to the lack of the technological equipment that might be required (e.g., personal computer, smartphone, internet access), low participation rates and lack of time to participate in such activities. Lack of the technological equipment and time are also significant barriers for being involved in these activities, complemented by individual concerns of leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions and not being able to find an interesting research topic, as well as lack of financial incentives and scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.

Table 16. Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for Lithuania

Benefits	Perceptions	Involvement
Benefits related to the individual (economic, social, educational).		
Benefits related to knowledge and skills.	✓	
Benefits derived when considering citizen science as a hobby.		
Benefits related to new professional/career opportunities.		✓
Benefits related to society and/or natural environment.	✓	✓
Drivers	Perceptions	Involvement
Continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project		✓
Acknowledgement of the contribution (e.g., certificate, monetary rewards, public acknowledgment)		
The project is well-organized and managed	✓	
Inspiring coordination team		
Clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks	✓	
Barriers	Perceptions	Involvement
Lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities.		
Lack of the technological equipment that might be required (e.g., personal computer, smartphone, internet access).	✓	✓
Belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community		
Lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback during the project.		
Low participation rate.	✓	
Fear that the contribution will be exploited by scientists/policy makers.		
Fear of leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions.		✓
Lack of time to participate in such activities.	✓	✓
Lack of financial incentives to participate.		✓
Fear of not finding an interesting research topic.		✓
Scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.		✓
Fear that the project will not be properly organised and managed.		

Source: Authors' elaborations (see Annex C for the detailed statistical results).

The Netherlands (UT)

The third country of the statistical analysis is the Netherlands, a where in which, as already discussed, the overall maturity levels of Citizen Science are higher compared to Greece and Lithuania. The analysis of data from the survey corroborates this. In Figure 17, the results from 8 questionnaire items on the perceptions and views about CS activities and CS Hubs are presented. Looking at the results, a first general conclusion that can be inferred is that the vast majority of people have a positive stance towards CS, and would support the CSH that is envisioned to be developed in the premises of the University of Twente.

Digging deeper, it is observed that as far as the overall perception of Citizen Science is concerned (Q5_1), 3 out of 4 participants (75%) either agree or strongly agree with having a positive perception. Only 5% had a negative perception, and a further 20% neither agreed nor disagreed. This picture is complemented by the fact that a considerable number of respondents either have a neutral position (32%) or disagreed (16%) with the statement "In my opinion, citizens lack the knowledge and skills to be part of the scientific process" (Q9_2). Even though half of the sample (48%) either agreed or strongly agreed with the statement, it remains a fact that many citizens believe that citizens have already the necessary skills to engage in CS. Nevertheless, the vast majority of respondents agree (38%) with the necessity to further train the citizens for CS activities, with an additional 36% strongly agreeing (Q9_3). Finally, results from Q9_1 about whether the citizens should have an active role in the design and execution of scientific projects, 36% of respondents agreed, and 21% strongly agreed, thus indicating a general support in genuine civic engagement in CS. However, it must be mentioned that 31% remains more sceptical, with neither agreeing nor disagreeing.

When it comes to the role of Citizen Science Hubs, 3 out of 4 participants (75%), agree or strongly agree that the Hubs should act as open places for discussion about scientific progress and societal challenges (Q7_1), with 21% having a neutral position. The same patterns are observed regarding the enhancement of soft and technical skills of citizens through the Hubs (Q7_2) and the scientific empowerment of citizens, with the ultimate aim to initiate their own scientific endeavours (Q7_3). In both cases, more than 75% either agreed or strongly disagreed, and 19% neither agreed nor disagreed. In addition, it is interesting to highlight that, as opposed to Greece and Lithuania, in which there is more reluctance, Dutch participants are quite open regarding the involvement of vulnerable groups in the CS Hubs (Q7_4). The majority of people (38%) strongly agreed, followed by 33% of people who agreed.

Q5_1. My overall perception of Citizen science is positive

Q7_1. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to act as open places for discussion about scientific progress and societal challenges

Q7_2. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to enhance soft and technical skills and improve citizens' understanding of scientific knowledge

Q7_3. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to empower citizens to become more actively involved in science and initiate their own citizen science projects

Q7_4. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to involve vulnerable groups.

Q9_1. In my opinion, citizens should have an active role in the design and execution of scientific projects

Q9_2. In my opinion, citizens lack the knowledge and skills to be part of the scientific process

Q9_3. In my opinion, citizens need to be trained in order to participate in science

Figure 17. General perceptions about Citizen Science and Citizen Science Hubs in the Netherlands

Figure 18 presents the results on the willingness to join Citizen Science activities, organised per stakeholder group. Overall, the patterns are the same between the different stakeholder categories. In all cases, the majority agree with actively engaging in CS; a finding that is in line with the results from previous questionnaire items. Moreover, in all stakeholder groups, the second biggest category are people who strongly agree and would thus be very committed to joining CS endeavours. It should be mentioned that the overall levels of disagreement or strongly disagreement are very low across all stakeholders. Only stakeholders from public administration (8.16%) and the private sector (6.57%), show a comparatively higher level of disagreement, but these figures do not change the general positive landscape.

When taking a closer look within each stakeholder group, some specific findings that are worth mentioning are the following: even though the higher level of agreement comes from the general public/civil society (46.60%), when the figures of those who agree and strongly agree are summed, academic stakeholders (71.43%) score equally high with the general public (71.87%); the highest share of those who strongly agree is observed within the private sector (32.12%); and finally, the highest share of those who strongly disagree comes once again from the private sector (5.11%).

Figure 18. Willingness to join Citizen Science activities in the Netherlands (per stakeholder group)

Figure 19 indicates that energy and sustainability, health and environmental sciences are the three most interesting topics for academics and researchers in the case of the Netherlands. As we can see, the first two are common topics between all different types of stakeholders. Policymakers are also interested in transport and mobility issues and public administration and policy topics. Participants from industry seem to be also interested in circular economy, transport and mobility issues, whereas citizens do not have any other particular interest apart from the areas of energy, sustainability and health.

When it comes to specific stages throughout the research process, Figure 20 shows an increased interest of academics and researchers in the early stages of these processes, including identifying research questions, designing studies and collecting data. Data collection

is a high priority for policy makers, businesses and citizens, together with data analysis and exploitation. A common pattern exists between these three stakeholder groups.

Figure 19. Topics of interest in the Netherlands (per stakeholder group)

Figure 20. Stage of the research process that you like to be involved (per stakeholder group)

Results for the case of the Netherlands indicate that almost all of the identified benefits significantly affect participants' perceptions and involvement (Table 17). Individual, knowledge and skills, as well as environmental benefits refer to both cases. However, benefits offered by citizen science projects related to personal interests (hobbies) can boost perceptions, whilst benefits referring to professional opportunities can act as motivators on personal involvement. Once more, continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project is a significant driver in both cases. Clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks affect perceptions, whereas acknowledgement of the contribution (e.g., certificate, monetary rewards, public acknowledgment) seem to have a positive effect on individual involvement. Some common barriers include lack of time, concern for leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions and lack of proper organization and management. Additional barriers related to perceptions are the lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in citizen science activities and fear that the contributions will be exploited by scientists/policy makers. Other barriers affecting participation in citizen science initiatives are the feeling that the person belongs to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community and scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.

Table 17. Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for the Netherlands

Benefits	Perceptions	Involvement
Benefits related to the individual (economic, social, educational).	✓	✓
Benefits related to knowledge and skills.	✓	✓
Benefits derived when considering citizen science as a hobby.	✓	
Benefits related to new professional/career opportunities.		✓
Benefits related to society and/or natural environment.	✓	✓
Drivers	Perceptions	Involvement
Continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project	✓	✓
Acknowledgement of the contribution (e.g., certificate, monetary rewards, public acknowledgment)		✓
The project is well-organized and managed		
Inspiring coordination team		
Clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks	✓	
Barriers	Perceptions	Involvement
Lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities.	✓	
Lack of the technological equipment that might be required (e.g., personal computer, smartphone, internet access).		
Belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community		✓
Lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback during the project.		
Low participation rate.		
Fear that the contribution will be exploited by scientists/policy makers.	✓	
Fear of leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions.	✓	✓

Lack of time to participate in such activities.	✓	✓
Lack of financial incentives to participate.		
Fear of not finding an interesting research topic.		
Scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.		✓
Fear that the project will not be properly organised and managed.	✓	✓

Source: Authors' elaborations (see Annex C for the detailed statistical results).

Spain (UAB)

The last country to be presented is Spain. As in all the previous countries, Figure 21 presents the results from a set of questionnaire items that aimed to capture participants' views and attitudes towards both Citizen Science and Citizen Science Hubs. Similar to the case of the Netherlands, results at first glance reveal an overall positive mindset from the Spanish society towards Citizen Science. In particular, in Q5_1, which address the overall perception of Citizen Science, 39% agreed that their perception is positive, and 36% strongly agreed, whereas only 4% disagreed, and 20% neither agreed nor disagreed. Moving on to whether citizens should have an active role in the design and execution of scientific projects (Q9_1), the share of those who don't agree or disagree is higher (31%). Nevertheless, supporters of the statement form the majority, with more than half of the sample (57%) either agreeing or strongly agreeing. The distribution changes and becomes more conflicting when it comes to the skills and knowhow of citizens. In Q9_2 – "In my opinion, citizens lack the knowledge and skills to be part of the scientific process", 31% agree that citizens do not possess the knowhow, but 32% remain indecisive and 20% disagree or strongly disagree. There is consensus, however, regarding the need to train citizens and prepare them for CS activities (Q9_3): 38% agreed that citizens need to be trained in order to participate in science, and 36% strongly agreed.

On another note, the average perception on the potential role of CSH is positive. Almost half of respondents (44%) agree that they would like Citizen Science Hubs to act as open places for discussion about scientific progress and societal challenges (Q7_1), and an additional 31% strongly agree. The same level of support is recorded for Q7_2 about the potential improvement of soft and technical skills of citizens, as well as their scientific knowledge, through their participation in the Hub: 40% agreed and 36% strongly agreed. The very low levels of disagreement are also noticeable. Results are identical for Q7_3 – "I would like Citizen Science Hubs to empower citizens to become more actively involved in science and initiate their own citizen science projects", with some very small changes in the percentages of those agreeing and strongly agreeing. Based on this, it can be inferred that Spanish society is mature enough to accept a very active engagement of citizens. Finally, there is support from respondents on the involvement of vulnerable segments of the population in the Hub. This is underlined by the fact that the majority of respondents (38%) strongly agreed, follow by 33% who agreed. 22% neither agreed nor disagreed, and only 5% disagreed with engaging vulnerable groups.

Q5_1. My overall perception of Citizen science is positive

Q7_1. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to act as open places for discussion about scientific progress and societal challenges

Q7_2. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to enhance soft and technical skills and improve citizens' understanding of scientific knowledge

Q7_3. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to empower citizens to become more actively involved in science and initiate their own citizen science projects

Q7_4. I would like Citizen Science Hubs to involve vulnerable groups.

Q9_1. In my opinion, citizens should have an active role in the design and execution of scientific projects

Q9_2. In my opinion, citizens lack the knowledge and skills to be part of the scientific process

Q9_3. In my opinion, citizens need to be trained in order to participate in science

Figure 21. General perceptions about Citizen Science and Citizen Science Hubs in Spain

In Figure 22, the levels of willingness to join Citizen Science activities are presented for each of Quadruple Helix. In general, the willingness levels are quite high across all stakeholder groups, and naturally, those who show disagreement form the minority in all cases. However, regarding the level of disagreement, it should be stressed that the biggest shares are recorded from stakeholders from public administration (8.16%) and private sector (6.57%). On the other hand, academic stakeholders have a very high share of people who agree to join CS (40.26%), but also of people who are strongly willing to participate (31.17%). Despite this last figure, it is the private sector in which the highest percentage of people who strongly agree is recorded (32.12%), indicating that private sector stakeholders are to certain extent divided regarding their willingness to join. Finally, stakeholders from civil society and the general public have the highest level of agreement (46.60%), while more than 1 out of 4 (25.27%) strongly agree.

Figure 22. Willingness to join Citizen Science activities in Spain (per stakeholder group)

Figure 23 shows the main topics of interest per stakeholder group for the Spanish case. As we can see, there are some common topics between the three out of four types of stakeholders (academia, business and citizens), such as energy and sustainability, health and environmental sciences. However, we can see that policymakers indicate a diversified pattern regarding the topics they seem to be interested in, as they mostly highlight the areas of circular economy, public administration and policy and educational sciences. It is interesting to notice that communication sciences have received less attention in almost all cases.

At the same time, Figure 24 presents the various stages in which the different stakeholder groups are interested in participating. The findings show that survey participants from all stakeholder groups are mostly interested in participating in data collection and analysis processes. Survey design and interpretation of results are of increased interest in the case of

academia and policy makers, whereas exploitation of research outcomes is an interesting stage mostly for stakeholders coming from the private sector.

Figure 23. Topics of interest in Spain (per stakeholder group)

Figure 24. Stage of the research process that you like to be involved (per stakeholder group)

Data coming from the Spanish pilot revealed benefits related to skills, society and the environment as significant factors for positively affecting citizen science projects (Table 18). At the same time, individual and professional benefits play a key role in overall perceptions and involvement in citizen science projects, respectively. In terms of key drivers in both cases, our

analysis captured the significant role of continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project, together with the need to provide clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks. When it comes to barriers, lack of the necessary skills, the sense of belonging to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community and scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups are related to overall perceptions on citizen science. Moreover, lack of the technological equipment, time, financial incentives, low participation rate, as well as concerns that the contributions will be exploited by scientists/policy makers and will lead to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions are some significant barriers that affect participants' involvement in citizen science initiatives.

Table 18 Identified benefits, drivers and barriers related to perceptions and the involvement in citizen science projects for Spain

Benefits	Perceptions	Involvement
Benefits related to the individual (economic, social, educational).	✓	
Benefits related to knowledge and skills.	✓	✓
Benefits derived when considering citizen science as a hobby.		
Benefits related to new professional/career opportunities.		✓
Benefits related to society and/or natural environment.	✓	✓
Drivers	Perceptions	Involvement
Continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project	✓	✓
Acknowledgement of the contribution (e.g., certificate, monetary rewards, public acknowledgment)		
The project is well-organized and managed		
Inspiring coordination team		
Clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks	✓	✓
Barriers	Perceptions	Involvement
Lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities.	✓	
Lack of the technological equipment that might be required (e.g., personal computer, smartphone, internet access).		✓
Belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community	✓	
Lack of receiving the necessary guidelines and feedback during the project.		
Low participation rate.		✓
Fear that the contribution will be exploited by scientists/policy makers.		✓
Fear of leading to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions.		✓
Lack of time to participate in such activities.		✓
Lack of financial incentives to participate.		
Fear of not finding an interesting research topic.		✓
Scepticism about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.	✓	✓
Fear that the project will not be properly organised and managed.		

Source: Authors' elaborations (see Annex C for the detailed statistical results).

6.3.4 *Cross-national comparisons*

As naturally expected, the four countries yielded different results with respect to perceptions, views, and enabling and hindering factors. Starting from the eastern part of Europe, it can be summarised that in Greece, societal perceptions towards Citizen Science, and the role of the Hubs, seem quite positive and receptive. This is an intriguing finding, given that the concept is still at an infant stage in the Eastern Mediterranean country. Still, the percentage of people who remain indecisive on CS and CSH cannot be overlooked. All QH groups show roughly the same levels of willingness to participate, whereas common fields of interest are energy and sustainability, educational and environmental sciences.

On the other hand, Lithuania presents much more different results. As opposed to Greece, the Lithuanian society – which is also at an immature stage regarding CS institutionalisation – appears more rigid and sceptical vis-à-vis CS and the potential of the Hub. In particular, the Lithuanian private sector and the general public demonstrate high levels of reluctance and rejection on participating to CS activities. This may be interpreted as a typical example of a post-soviet country, where civic engagement and private economy were anaemic for many decades. The rich variation across stakeholder groups regarding the scientific topic of interest for CS is also noticeable.

The landscape differs when moving to the western side of Europe. In the Netherlands, a nation with heavily industrialised and developed economy, and a robust civil society, stakeholder groups and the general public are quite open and supportive to CS and the CSH, with very few people opposing them. The patterns concerning the willingness to join CS activities are balanced between stakeholder groups. Moreover, all Dutch stakeholder groups have as common scientific topics of interest energy and sustainability and health.

Finally, Spain lies in between the Netherlands and Greece when it comes to the perception towards CS and the Hubs. In other words, even though the majority of participants are receptive and would support CS and CSHs (as in the Netherlands), the percentage of people who remain neutral is also substantial (as in Greece). This may be explained by the fact that Spain essentially has similarities with both the Netherlands and Greece: it historically belongs to the western European nations and has followed the same development trajectories, but it is also a traditional Mediterranean country, with cultural, economic and social similarities with other European Mediterranean nations. Common topics of interest for all stakeholder groups are energy and sustainability, health and environmental sciences. Interestingly enough, the scientific topic of energy and sustainability is prevalent in all countries, which may imply that issues of energy and environmental sustainability are of pan-European concern when it comes to Citizen Science.

7. Conclusions and way forward

This document has presented the findings of a 5-month research on the hindering and enabling factors of actively engaging the QH stakeholder groups in Citizen Science in general, and in Citizen Science Hubs in particular, in four participating countries: Greece, Lithuania, the Netherlands, and Spain. After following a mixed exploratory methodology, a rich number of results have been produced and are thorough detailed in the document.

The most important conclusion that can be drawn from the findings is that despite their commonalities in many patterns, the four countries differ considerably in many aspects. This should not come as a surprise. As shown through the exploratory literature review, civic engagement and active retainment in CS activities are impacted by a plethora of factors, in which institutional structures, historical pathways, political maturity and economic development play profound role. The macro-environment matters as much as the micro- and meso-levels. Since the four countries are located in different angles of Europe, they have unique characteristics and historical backgrounds, which in turn affect how Citizen Science is understood and experienced. Technological and scientific maturity vary across the four countries, as do the level of civic participation, the economic resources, the political environment and the social norms. In sum, Citizen Science could not be possibly practiced and endorsed in the same way in so different national contexts.

The implications of the findings necessitate the alignment of the envisioned Citizen Science Hubs with the local dynamics in each country. A CS Hub can be easily presented as a theoretical prototype, but when practically created and operationalised, adaptations become inevitable across national settings. It has been shown that not all factors have the same effect in all countries and that the level of perception and readiness fluctuates in many sensitive issues, such as the involvement of vulnerable groups, the support to citizens to initiate their own scientific project, and the topics of scientific interest. To make matters more complicated, these factors further differ when the QH stakeholder groups within a country are considered. Given the complexity of the landscape, understanding the specificities of each country and the priorities of stakeholder groups is of outmost importance to deliver Citizen Science Hubs that effectively fulfil local needs and urgent problems.

A further important implication is the acknowledgment that financial and organisational aspects of engagement in CS projects are expected to influence the establishment and operation of CS hubs. As shown from the literature, the thematic analysis and the statistical results, funding and financial support in general is a critical ingredient. As such, further research during the project can shed light on the influence of available public and private funding which is necessary for fuelling CS initiatives. Unpacking the possibility of leveraging, under certain conditions and limitations, CS as part of the scientific arsenal to conduct research (and therefore receive relevant financial support by funding sources related to research and academic activities), may help in this direction. In the frame of subsequent work packages, pilot RPOs can benefit from any information that may support the development of a business model for establishing and

running their Hub, even if this aspect was not initially considered for the operationalisation of the Hubs.

Finally, even though the focal point of the document has been the external ecosystems of the pilot RPOs, the analysis has brought into the surface some preliminary findings regarding the current degree of CS penetration into the R&I community at the local level, and in particular in the pilot universities. The low level of CS penetration is exemplified several times throughout the document. For instance, the thematic analysis highlights the insufficient scientific models and power asymmetry between scientific and non-scientific stakeholder groups as key obstacle, and the statistical analysis proves that a non-negligible percentage of academic stakeholders remain at least indecisive about their willingness to join CS activities. Once these preliminary findings that relate to the maturity level of CS *within* pilot universities are combined with the fact that currently the number of academic publications with keywords including "Citizen Science" for the period 2006-2021 are very low (AUTH: 3, UT: 13, VGTU: 0, UAB: 5)⁷, it becomes apparent that more research is needed to quantify the level of inertia that will be met from the pilot RPOs themselves in terms of adopting CS-related methods and activities at local level.

As such, the added value of this document lies in its capacity to inform the subsequent tasks of INCENTIVE project that seek the creation and operationalisation of the Citizen Science Hubs in the four RPOs. The results of the deliverable will directly feed the development of the QH stakeholders incentivising methods and engagement techniques that are foreseen under Task 2.3 – "Manual and tools for incentivising and engaging quadruple helix stakeholders in the CSHs". In addition, Task 2.2 – "Defining the governance structure and operating model of the Citizen Science Hubs" will be heavily informed by this deliverable. At the same time, the whole WP3 which concerns the set-up and operation of the Citizen Science Hubs, will keep drawing lessons and inspiration from the findings of this document, eventually succeeding in including all stakeholder groups and creating a culture of collaborative science.

However, the legacy of this document is not confined within the operational life-span of the INCENTIVE project. As new societal challenges continue to emerge, and new democratic models of scientific progress become ever more a necessity, this document at the end aspires to contribute to the wider literature of Citizen Science, and how the latter evolve into the new scientific norm, by overcoming current barriers and strengthening its enablers.

⁷ The results come from a research at [Scopus.com](https://scopus.com) performed by AUTH, with the aim to identify publications with keywords including "citizen science" and with affiliation of at least one co-author from one of the 4 participating universities. The results cover the period 2006-2021.

References

- Asingizwe, D., Poortvliet, P., Koenraad, C., van Vliet, A., Ingabire, C., Mutesa, L., & Leeuwis, C. (2020). Why (not) participate in citizen science? Motivational factors and barriers to participate in a citizen science program for malaria control in Rwanda. *PLOS ONE*, 15(8), e0237396. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0237396
- Attride-Stirling, J. (2001). Thematic networks: an analytic tool for qualitative research. *Qualitative Research*. SAGE Publications (London, Thousand Oaks, CA and New Delhi) vol. 1(3): 385-405. [1468-7941 (200112) 1:3; 385-405; 019991]
- AUTH (2021). Environmental Informatics Research Group. Retrieved from: <https://www.meng.auth.gr/en/node/483>
- Bakousi, K (2021). A first approach to citizen science in Greece. Retrieved from: <https://eu-citizen.science/forum/forum/%CF%B7-%CF%B5%CF%80%CF%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CF%AF%CF%BC%CF%B7-%CF%84%CF%89%CF%BD-%CF%80%CF%BF%CF%BB%CF%B9%CF%84%CF%8E%CF%BD-%CF%83%CF%84%CF%B7%CF%BD-%CF%B5%CF%BB%CF%BB%CF%AC%CF%B4%CF%B1-57/topic/a-first-approach-to-citizen-science-in-greece-102/>
- Barcelona.cat (2021) Citizen science. Retrieved from: <https://www.barcelona.cat/barcelonaciencia/en/citizen-science>
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3:2, 77-101, DOI: 10.1191/1478088706qp0630a
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social Research Methods*. Fourth edition, Oxford University Press.
- Burgess, H. K., DeBey, L. B., Froehlich, H. E., Schmidt, N., Theobald, E. J., Ettinger, A. K., HilleRisLambers, J., Tewksbury, J., Parrish, J. K. (2017). *Biological Conservation* 208 (2017) 113–120. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2016.05.014>
- Butkeviciene E. (2020). Citizen science or non-professional scientists. Retrieved from: <https://ktu.edu/news/ktu-mokslininke-pilieciu-mokslas-arba-mokslininkas-neprofesionalas-pakankamai-nauja-auganti-sritis/>
- Butteriss C. (2019). Lessons from citizen science for community engagement practice. *Bangthetable*. Retrieved from: <https://www.bangthetable.com/blog/lessons-from-citizen-science-for-community-engagement-practice/>
- Collins, A., Doersch, K., Herszenhorn, L., Johnson, R., Matson, C. & Young, A. (2015). *Citizen Science Toolkit*. California Academy of Sciences. Retrieved from: <https://www.calacademy.org/educators/citizen-science-toolkit>
- DESI (2019). Human Capital Digital Inclusion and Skills. Retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/human-capital>
- DRG (2021, 23/07, last accessed). Which Methodology is Right for You? Qualitative? Quantitative? Or Both? Retrieved from: <https://www.thedrg.com/qual-vs-quant/> Asingizwe, D., Poortvliet, P., Koenraad, C., van Vliet, A., Ingabire, C., Mutesa, L., & Leeuwis, C. (2020). Why (not) participate in citizen science? Motivational factors and barriers to participate in a citizen science program for malaria control in Rwanda. *PLOS ONE*, 15(8), e0237396. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0237396
- ECSA (2015). Ten principles of Citizen Science. Retrieved from: https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/ecsa_ten_principles_of_citizen_science.pdf

EPA (2019). Basic Information about Citizen Science. Retrieved from: <https://www.epa.gov/citizen-science/basic-information-about-citizen-science-o>

European Citizen Science Association. (2015). The Ten Principles of Citizen Science. London. Retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Citizen_science

European Commission (2021, 07/07, last accessed). Responsible research & innovation. Retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/responsible-research-innovation>

European Commission. (2020). Citizen science. Policy. Retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/citizen-science>

Garcia-Soto, C., van der Meeren, G. I., Busch, J. A., Delany, J., Domegan, C., Dubsky, K., Fauville, G., Gorsky, G., von Juterzenka, K., Malfatti, F., Mannaerts, G., McHugh, P., Monestiez, P., Seys, J., Węstawski, J.M. & Zielinski, O. (2017). Advancing Citizen Science for Coastal and Ocean Research. French, V., Kellett, P., Delany, J., McDonough, N. [Eds.] Position Paper 23 of the European Marine Board, Ostend, Belgium. 112pp. ISBN: 978-94-92043-30-6

Geoghegan, H., Dyke, A., Pateman, R., West, S. & Everett, G. (2016) Understanding motivations for citizen science. Final report on behalf of UKEOF, University of Reading, Stockholm Environment Institute (University of York) and University of the West of England.

Gordienko, Y. G. (2013). Green Paper on Citizen Science. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259230549_Green_Paper_on_Citizen_Science

Grey, F., Wyler, D., Fröhlich, J., & Maes, K. (2016). Citizen science at universities: Trends, guidelines and recommendations. Retrieved from: <https://www.leru.org/files/Citizen-Science-at-Universities-Trends-Guidelines-and-Recommendations-Full-paper.pdf>

Haklay, M. M., Dörler, D., Heigl, F., Manzoni, M., Hecker, S., & Vohland, K. (2021). Haklay M., Dörler D., Heigl F., Manzoni M., Hecker S., Vohland K. (2021) What Is Citizen Science? The Challenges of Definition. In: Vohland K. et al. (eds) The Science of Citizen Science. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_2

Hammersley, M. (2008). Troubles with triangulation. In: Bergman, Manfred Max ed. Advances in Mixed Methods Research. London: Sage, pp. 22–36.

Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J. & Bonn, A. (2018). Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy. London: UCL Press. <https://doi.org/10.14324/111.9781787352339>

Heiss R, Matthes J (2017). Citizen science in the social sciences: a call for more evidence. GAIA-Ecol Perspect Sci Soc, Vol. 26(1), pp. 22–26.

HubB30 (2021). Retrieved from: <https://hubb30.cat/en>

Jennett, C., Kloetzer, L., Schneider, D., Iacovides, I., Cox, A. L., Gold, M., Fuchs, B., Eveleigh, A., Mathieu, K., Ajani, Z., and Talsi, Y. (2016). Motivations, learning and creativity in online citizen science. Journal of Science Communication 15(03).

Johnson, R. B., and Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2004). Mixed Methods Research: A Research Paradigm Whose Time Has Come. Educational Researcher, Vol. 33, No. 7, pp. 14–26.

Kasperowski, D., Kullenberg, C., & Mäkitalo, Å. (2017). Embedding citizen science in research: Forms of engagement, scientific output and values for science, policy and society. SocArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/tfsgb>.

Kassandros, Th., Bakousi, A., Gavros, A., Karatzas K. (2021). Citizens in the loop for air quality monitoring in Thessaloniki, Greece. Advances and New trends in environmental Informatics, Digital Twins for

Sustainability (eds: Kamilaris A., Wohlgemuth V., Karatzas K., Athanasiadis I.), pp. 121-130. Springer AG, Switzerland, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61969-5>.

Kleinke, B., Prajzner, S., Gordon, C., Hoekstra, N., Kautz, A., and Gardiner, M. (2018). Identifying Barriers to Citizen Scientist Retention When Measuring Pollination Services. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 3(1): 2, pp. 1-10, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.99>

Kragh, G. (2016). The motivations of volunteers in citizen science. In "They walk among us. The rise of citizen science". *Journal of the Institution of Environmental Sciences*. August 2016.

Larson, L. R., Cooper, C. B., Futch S., Sing D., Shipley N. J., Dale K., LeBaron G. S., Takekawa J. Y. (2020). The diverse motivations of citizen scientists: Does conservation emphasis grow as volunteer participation progresses? *Biological Conservation* 242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108428>

Mačiulienė, M., Skaržauskienė, A. (2016). Evaluation of co-creation perspective in networked collaboration platforms, *Journal of business research*. New York: Elsevier Science, Vol. 69 (11).

Martin, V. Y., Christidis, L., Lloyd, D. J., and Pecl, G. T. (2016). Understanding drivers, barriers and information sources for public participation in marine citizen science. *Journal of Science Communication* 15(02)(2016)A02

Mitchell N, Triska M, Liberatore A, Ashcroft L, Weatherill R, Longnecker N (2017). Benefits and challenges of incorporating citizen science into university education. Vol.12(11), <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0186285>

Mitchell, N., Triska, M., Liberatore, A., Ashcroft, L., Weatherill, R., & Longnecker, N. (2017). Benefits and challenges of incorporating citizen science into university education. *PLOS ONE*, 12(11), e0186285. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0186285

National Geographic (2021a). Citizen science. Resource Library. Encyclopedic Entry. Retrieved from: <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/encyclopedia/citizen-science/>

National Geographic (2021b) Citizen science. Resource Library. Collection. Retrieved from: https://www.nationalgeographic.org/topics/citizen-science/?q=&page=1&per_page=25

NPOS (2020) Knowledge and strengths combined – citizen science in the Netherlands. Final report of the Citizen Science Working Group.

PARTHENOS Project (2019). Challenges of Conducting a Citizen Science Project. Retrieved from: <https://training.parthenos-project.eu/sample-page/citizen-science-in-the-digital-arts-and-humanities/what-is-citizen-science/challenges-of-conducting-a-citizen-science-project/>

Pérez, A., & Costa, N. (2018). Deliverable D3.1: Initial report on market analysis and market uptake. Ground Truth 2.0. Retrieved from: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5b8e06f3b&appld=PPGMS>

Peterson, E. E., Santos-Fernández, E., Chen, C., Clifford, S., Vercelloni, J., Pearse, A., Brown, R., Christensen, B., James, A., Anthony, K., Loder, J., González-Riverod, M., Roelfsema, C., Julian C. M., Mellin, C., Bednarz, T., and Mengersen, K. (2020). Monitoring through many eyes: Integrating disparate datasets to improve monitoring of the Great Barrier Reef. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 124, 104557. Retrieved from: <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1808/1808.05298.pdf>

Pocock, M., Roy, H., August, T., Kuria, A., Barasa, F., & Bett, J. et al. (2018). Developing the global potential of citizen science: Assessing opportunities that benefit people, society and the environment in East Africa. *Journal Of Applied Ecology*, 56(2), 274-281. doi: 10.1111/1365-2664.13279

Robinson L.D., Cawthray, J.L., West, S.E., Bonn, A., & Ansine, J. (2018). Ten principles of citizen science. In S. Hecker, M. Haklay, A. Bowser, Z. Makuch, J. Vogel, & A. Bonn. *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*. London, UCL Press. 1–23.

Robson, C. and McCartan, K. (2016). *Real World Research*. Fourth Edition, John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

Rotman, D., Hammock J., Preece, J., Hansen, D., Boston, C., Bowser, A. and He Y. (2014b). Motivations Affecting Initial and Long-Term Participation in Citizen Science Projects in Three Countries. DOI:10.9776/14054

Rotman, D., Hammock, J., Preece, J., Boston, C., Hansen, D., Bowser, A., & He, Y. (2014a). Does motivation in citizen science change with time and culture? *Proceedings Of The Companion Publication Of The 17Th ACM Conference On Computer Supported Cooperative Work & Social Computing - CSCW Companion '14*. doi: 10.1145/2556420.2556492

Saunders B., Sim, J., Kingstone, T., Baker, S., Waterfield, J., Bartlam, B., Burroughs, H., Jinks, C. (2018). Saturation in qualitative research: exploring its conceptualization and operationalization. *Qual Quant* (2018) 52:1893–1907. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-017-0574-8>
Asingizwe, D., Poortvliet, P., Koenraadt, C., van Vliet, A., Ingabire, C., Mutesa, L., & Leeuwis, C. (2020). Why (not) participate in citizen science? Motivational factors and barriers to participate in a citizen science program for malaria control in Rwanda. *PLOS ONE*, 15(8), eo237396. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0237396

Science Communication Unit, University of the West of England, Bristol (2013). *Science for Environment Policy In-depth Report: Environmental Citizen Science*. Report produced for the European Commission DG Environment, December 2013. Retrieved from: <http://ec.europa.eu/science-environment-policy>

Scistarter (2021). What is Citizen Science? Retrieved from: <https://scistarter.org/citizen-science>

Scotland Counts (2016). *Citizen Science – Motivations, Progression and Accreditation*. Retrieved from: https://www.tcv.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/citizen_science_motivation_report.pdf

Silvertown, J. (2009). A new dawn for citizen science. *Trends in ecology & evolution*, 24(9), 467–471. Retrieved from: <https://www.cybertracker.org/downloads/2015-Our-Story/F-3-Citizen-Science-Silvertown.pdf>

Skaržauskienė, A. et al. (2015). *Social technologies and collective intelligence*. Vilnius: MRU.

Statista (2021, 26/07, last accessed). *Population of Europe in 2020, by country and gender*. Retrieved from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/611318/population-of-europe-by-country-and-gender/>

Tauginienė, L., Butkevičienė, E., Vohland, K., Heinisch, b., Daskolia, M. (2020). *Citizen science in the social sciences and humanities: the power of interdisciplinarity*, Palgrave Communications 6 (1), 1–11.

UAB (2021). *UAB Initiatives*. Retrieved from: <https://www.uab.cat/web/research/itineraries/uab-research/responsible-research-and-innovation/citizen-science/uab-initiatives-1345824010650.html>

UAB Open Labs (2020). Retrieved from: <https://www.uab.cat/web/uab-open-labs-1345823387910.html>

Vohland K., Göbel C., Balázs B., Butkevičienė E., Daskolia M., Duží B., Hecker S., Manzoni M. & Schade S., (2021). *Citizen Science in Europe. The Science of Citizen Science*, Springer pp 35–53. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_3

Wikipedia (2021). *Citizen science*. Retrieved from: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Citizen_science

Wilson Center: Commons Lab (2014). *An Exploratory Study on Barriers*. Retrieved from: <https://stipcommunia.wordpress.com/2014/09/07/an-exploratory-study-on-barriers/>

Annex A: Interview guide

Welcome to INCENTIVE

"The project INCENTIVE – "Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society" (GA no. 101005330) invites you to participate in this face-to-face interview. It will take approximately 30 minutes of your time. Thank you very much in advance for your support, which is very much appreciated. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask at any stage. There are no right or wrong answers, and all the information you will provide should reflect only your own ideas, concerns and perspectives and not the organization you are affiliated with."

INTERVIEW GUIDE | Total duration: 30'

PART 1 | OPENING (WARM - UP) | Appr. 7-8'

1. *"How do you feel today? What is the situation there with the lockdown?"*
2. *"You have been invited to represent your country and regional area regarding past and current experiences on projects or activities that are related to the principles and practices of citizen science".*
3. *How long have you been in the position you are now?*
4. *How familiar are you with the concept of "citizen science"? What has been your personal experience with citizen science initiatives in your country so far?*

PART 2 | MAIN PART (CORE QUESTIONS) | Appr. 15'

"We can now proceed with the main part of our interview. We want to ask you some general questions that regard your personal experiences, perspectives and views on the development and evolution of citizen science initiatives in your national, regional and local context. I recall that there are no wrong or correct answers; we only want to hear your opinion. In case you don't understand a question or you want us to clarify, do not hesitate to say so."

Category 1: state-of-play at national, regional and local level (appr. 5')

5. *"What type of engagement, directly (as citizen) or indirectly (e.g., through your institution or agency), have you had with any citizen science initiatives in your country, and how much successful were these initiatives?"*
6. *"In your opinion, how citizen science is understood and implemented in your country, either at national or at local level?"*

Category 2: discovering barriers and obstacles (appr. 5')

7. *"What type of major limitations and problems have you been observing in the citizen science initiatives that you had personally participated to, but also initiatives in general in your country?"*

8. *"In your opinion, which are the factors that can most seriously threaten the success of a new citizen science initiative in your country, at national, regional or local level?"*

Category 3: understanding driving factors and enablers (appr. 5')

9. *"When designing a citizen science project in your country, which dimensions should be taken into account in order the initiative to succeed?"*

10. *"What elements does a citizen science project depend on to maintain the necessary participation rates from citizens and other contributing stakeholder groups (e.g., scientists, researchers, policy makers, investors, etc.)?"*

PART 3 | CLOSING (CLEAN - UP) | Appr. 7-8'

11. *"Would you like to follow up on any things I might have not asked you?"*

12. *"Do you have any final thought to share?"*

PART 4 | BACKGROUND INFORMATION | Appr. 1'

Now, we have reached almost the end of the interview. I would like to ask you some final background information.

13. *"Which category of the following does your current occupation falls under?"*

- Research/academia*
- Government/policy-maker*
- Business/private sector*
- Civil Society/individual*

14. *"Your Gender":*

- Female*
- Male*

15. *"Your nationality": _____*

16. *"What is your highest educational degree achieved?"*

- Anchored by less than high school*
- High school/GED*
- Some college but no degree*
- Bachelor's degree or equivalent*
- Master's degree or equivalent*
- Doctoral or professional degree (PhD/JD/MD)*

I would like to thank you for taking your time for providing valuable insights in your perspective.

Annex B: Consent form and privacy policy

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are:

We are White Research SRL, and we are contacting you in the framework of INCENTIVE, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description of how INCENTIVE handles personal data is presented in the project's Privacy Policy that accompanies this Consent Form (see below).

Project: INCENTIVE - Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society (GA Number 101005330).

Partner:

Organisation name: White Research SRL

Address: Avenue de la Toison d'Or, 67

Phone: +32 2 520 00 09

E-mail: info@white-research.eu

Responsible persons:

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	INCENTIVE Project Manager – Interviewer no. 1	Artemis Psaltoglou	apsaltoglou@white-research.eu
2	INCENTIVE Associate Project Manager – Interviewer no. 2	Thomas Bakratsas	tbakratsas@white-research.eu

What do we need from you?

You have been invited to take part in this interview because you have been identified as a key stakeholder for the INCENTIVE project. There are approximately 10 questions in this questionnaire related to (i) familiarity with the concept of “citizen science”; (ii) personal past and current experiences in regional citizen science initiatives; (iii) type of personal engagement in citizen science initiatives; (iv) limitations and space for further improvement for further public

engagement; (v) views on how to design and implement a robust citizen science initiative; (vi) some background information.

This will ultimately help us better shape the project's outcomes and its offers to your needs. The interview is expected to last for no more than 30 – 35 minutes. We will take written notes during the interview.

To effectively conduct this interview, we need to process some of your personal data (background information):

- Some basic demographics (e.g., age, gender)
- Your professional info (organization, job position, field of expertise)
- Your education level
- Your personal opinions on the subject matter.

Why do we need your data & what will we do with them?

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out the aforementioned interview and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of the interview. We also need to record your data to keep track of the interview process. The project's deliverables that will be derived by the interview will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. Your personal data will remain on our written notes (interview's transcript) we will make during the interview.

We will share your data with the other INCENTIVE project partners involved in this task and who will participate in the drafting of the relevant deliverables. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

We would also be very happy if you give us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project's activities (e.g., surveys, interviews, INCENTIVE Advisory Board, etc.) and also to inform you about the project's progress (e.g., by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

How can you withdraw your consent?

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed on the previous page. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters you can always opt-out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that you do not consent to the relevant subject.)

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in an interview that will be carried out by INCENTIVE to learn more about my experience and personal views on citizen science initiatives in my region and the involvement of general public and stakeholders in it	
2	My participation in future activities of INCENTIVE	
3	Receiving newsletters and messages regarding INCENTIVE activities	

Name of participant

Date

Signature

INCENTIVE – PRIVACY POLICY

LAST UPDATE: 19/02/2021

1. Who we are:

INCENTIVE is a three-year-long project funded by the European Union within the H2020 Research and Innovation programme. It aims at establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations (RPFOS) to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) in society. The project's rationale starts from the belief that mainstreaming institutional changes to foster RRI in research institutions is key to promoting RRI in Europe's societies. However, until now, only a small number of world-leading RPFOS worldwide have made concerted, organisation-wide efforts to establish sustainable transdisciplinary hubs to stimulate and support excellent citizen science with active roles for all Research and Innovation (R&I) stakeholders. In INCENTIVE, we broadly reference these hubs as "Citizen Science Hubs", and our ambition is to empower European RPFOS to communicate and adapt this state-of-the-art paradigm into their institutional contexts, as a vehicle of institutional change. To this end, INCENTIVE brings on board four RPFOS, namely University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT), and supports them to establish their own Citizen Science Hubs.

INCENTIVE entails several activities that involve collecting, producing, and processing data to generate meaningful insights that will feed into the project and fuel the co-creation and delivery of demand-driven and evidence-based results. Thus, the INCENTIVE consortium partners, listed below, process certain types of personal data. Each partner is responsible for the personal data they collect and process during their activities under the framework of the project:

- UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE, the Netherlands, <https://www.utwente.nl/>
- UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA, Spain, <https://www.uab.cat/>
- ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS, Greece, <https://www.auth.gr/>
- VILNIAUS GEDIMINO TECHNIKOS UNIVERSITETAS, Lithuania, <https://www.vgtu.lt/>
- UNIVERSITÄT ZÜRICH, Switzerland, <https://www.uzh.ch/>
- UNIVERSITÀ COMMERCIALE LUIGI BOCCONI, Italy, https://www.unibocconi.it/wps/wcm/connect/Bocconi/SitoPubblico_IT/Albero+di+navigazione/Home/
- Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC, Greece, <https://qplan-intl.gr/>
- WHITE RESEARCH SPRL, Belgium, www.white-research.eu
- VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN - ECSA E.V., Germany, <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/>

For further information, please contact us via e-mail, at l.kalverda@utwente.nl

2. How we collect your personal data

We collect personal data both directly and indirectly:

Directly. We obtain personal data directly from individuals in a variety of ways, including but not limited to the following cases:

- an individual subscribes to our newsletter/s;
- an individual registers to attend in meetings and events we host and during attendance at such events;
- we establish cooperative relationships with an individual;
- we provide professional services pursuant to our contract with the European Commission;
- an individual participates in an interview or survey organised by us.

Indirectly. We obtain personal data indirectly about individuals from a variety of sources, including:

- our research partners;
- our networks and contacts;
- public and open data sources such as public registers, news articles and internet searches;
- social and professional networking sites (e.g. LinkedIn).

3. What types of data we collect?

We only collect the data that are necessary for the smooth implementation of our project. These data fall into the following categories:

- **contact details** (name/ surname, e-mail address, street address, mobile phone number, land line phone number);
- **professional information** (job title, organisation, field of expertise);
- **demographics** (e.g. age, gender, nationality);
- **information about what a person knows or believes.**
- **videos and photos** (from people that attend our events).

4. Bases of lawful processing

We process personal data on the following legal bases:

Legal obligations - for processing activities required for compliance both with applicable national and European legislation, as well as with the specific legal and regulatory framework of the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union.

Consent - for processing activities such as organisation of surveys and interviews, completing of questionnaires and dissemination of project's results.

Contractual obligations - for processing activities such as reporting to the European Commission and complying with project's publicity obligations.

5. What we do with your personal data

We process your personal data with the purpose of:

- Conducting research (e.g., interviews, surveys);
- Dissemination our project's results to different types of stakeholder;
- Sending invitations and providing access to guests attending our events and webinars;
- Administering, maintaining, and ensuring the security of our information systems, applications, and websites;
- Processing online requests or queries, including responding to communications from individuals;
- Complying with contractual, legal, and regulatory obligations.

6. How we secure your personal data when we process it

We continuously apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten your personal data. Based on the results of this risk assessment, we define and apply a set of both technical and organisational measures to mitigate the above security risks, including but not limited to:

- Data Protection Policies to guide our personnel when processing your data;
- Written contracts with organisations that process personal data on our behalf;
- Non-Disclosure Agreements with our personnel;
- Back up process, antimalware protection, access control mechanisms, etc.
- Some of/ all our partners have appointed a Data Protection Officer.

7. Do we share personal data with third parties?

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before we share the data. We may engage with several or all the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Dropbox, Microsoft Teams, Google Drive);
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;
- Dissemination services providers (e.g., MailChimp);
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with applicable law or regulation;
- The European Commission, according to our relevant contractual obligations.

8. Do we transfer your personal data outside the European Economic Area?

We do not own file servers located outside the European Economic Area (EEA). However, some partners may use cloud and/or marketing services from reputable providers such as SharePoint, DropBox, MailChimp, Google, etc., situated both inside and outside the EEA. We always check

that such providers comply with the relevant GDPR requirements before start using their services.

9. Do we use cookies?

Our website uses cookies. A statement will be sent to your browser explaining the use of cookies.

10. Your rights

You have the following rights regarding our processing of your personal data:

- **Right to withdraw consent** – You can withdraw consent that you have previously given to one or more specified purposes to process your personal data. This will not affect the lawfulness of any processing carried out before you withdraw your consent.
- **Right of access** – You can ask us to verify whether we are processing personal data about you and, if so, to have access to a copy of such data.
- **Right to rectification and erasure** – You can ask us to correct our records if you believe they contain incorrect or incomplete information about you or ask us to erase your personal data after you withdraw your consent to processing or when we no longer need it for the purpose it was originally collected.
- **Right to restriction of processing** – You can ask us to temporarily restrict our processing of your personal data if you contest the accuracy of your personal data, prefer to restrict its use rather than having us erase it, or need us to preserve it for you to establish, exercise or defend a legal claim. A temporary restriction may apply while verifying whether we have overriding legitimate grounds to process it. You can ask us to inform you before we lift that temporary processing restriction.
- **Right to data portability** – In some circumstances, where you have provided personal data to us, you can ask us to transmit that personal data (in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format) directly to another entity.
- **Right to object** – You can object to our use of your personal data for direct marketing purposes, including profiling or where processing has taken the form of automated decision-making. However, we may need to keep some minimal information (e.g., e-mail address) to comply with your request to cease marketing to you.
- **Right to make a complaint to your local Data Protection Authority (DPA)** (see https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/structure/data-protection-authorities/index_en.htm) regarding any concerns you may have about our data handling practices.

To ask us to do anything of the above, you can contact us by e-mail: L.kalverda@utwente.nl. We will promptly examine your request against the relevant requirements of the laws and regulations governing privacy and personal data protection, and we will answer the latest within 30 days after receiving your request. We will ask you for some kind of identification (e.g. photocopy of your identity card or passport) to avoid non-authorized reveal of your personal data. If, due to the complexity of the request or a multitude of requests, we are unable to respond promptly, we will notify you within 30 days of any delay, which in no case may exceed two months from the expiration of the 30-day deadline.

11. How long do we retain personal data?

We retain personal data to provide our services, stay in contact with you and to comply with applicable laws, regulations, and contractual obligations to which we are subject. Please note that we are obliged to retain data concerning projects funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union for up to five years after the project's end (unless auditors request further retention). After the expiry of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, we will dispose of personal data securely.

12. Disclaimer of liability for third party websites

Although our site may contain links to third-party sites, including the sites of the consortium partners, we are not responsible for the privacy practices or content of these sites and we expressly disclaim any liability for any loss or damage that may be caused by the use of these links. We do not monitor the privacy practices or the content of these sites. If you have any questions about the privacy practices of another site, you should contact the site's responsible personnel. We suggest you read the privacy policy of each website you interact with, before allowing the collection and use of your personal data.

We may also provide social media features that allow you to share information on your social networks and interact with our project on various social media sites. The use of these social media features may result in the collection or sharing of information about you. We recommend that you check the privacy policies and regulations of the social networking sites you interact with, so that you can be sure that you understand what information may be collected, used and disclosed by these sites.

13. Children

We do not knowingly collect, use, or disclose information from children under the age of 16. If we learn that we have collected the personal information of a child under 16 we will take steps to delete the information as soon as possible. Please immediately contact us if you become aware that a child under 16 has provided us with personal information.

14. Revisions of this Privacy Policy

This Privacy Policy is valid from 19/02/2021 and replaces any other previous notifications that we had issued in the past regarding our personal data management practices. We reserve the right to revise this Policy at any time. The current version will always be uploaded to our website indicating the date of entry into force, so you know when the most recent revision took place. If there are critical changes in this Policy or our personal data practices change significantly in the future, we will notify you by posting the changes on our website.

Annex C: Methodological note on the statistical analysis

In this section we present the methodological details related to the statistical analysis we performed for identifying the main drivers, barriers and benefits related to positive perceptions and increased involvement to citizen science projects.

To estimate the effects of selected parameters on general public perceptions and willingness to participate in citizen science projects, measured in a 5-point Likert scale, we developed the model presented below:

$$y_i = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 X_i + \beta_2 Z_i + \beta_3 DEMO_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

Where X_i refers to a set of general individual characteristics related to familiarity with terms relevant to citizen science (FAM), previous experience (PREV_EXP) and type of educational/professional background (SOCIAL, LIFE, STEM); Z_i includes a set of independent variables related to potential factors that can act as benefits (BEN_X), barriers (BAR_X) and drivers (DR_X) for citizen science initiatives, whereas $DEMO_i$ controls for a set of demographic characteristics related to each individual. We use the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimator to estimate the above model.

In our case, we choose to use a set of two dependent variables including aspects of perceptions related to citizen science and willingness to join that type of initiatives. Below, **Table A1** presents the main variables used for our analysis. As we can see, we have a set of variables referring to general background and demographic information for each individual, together with three different groups of variables capturing aspects related to benefits, barriers and drivers for citizen science perceptions and involvement.

Table A1: Main variables used for our analysis.

Name	Short description	Related question
FAM	Familiarity with terms related to citizen science	Q1
PREV_EXP	Previous experience with citizen science	Q2
SOCIAL	Social sciences, arts and humanities (history, law, linguistics, economics, sociology, psychology, political sciences, philosophy, etc.)	Q4_1
LIFE	Life and health sciences (medicine, biology, ecology, zoology, botany, earth science etc.)	Q4_2
STEM	STEM (science, technology, engineering, mathematics, computer science etc.)	Q4_3
BEN_IND	Benefits related to the individual (economic, social, educational).	Q6_1
BEN_SKILL	Benefits related to knowledge and skills.	Q6_2
BEN_HOBBY	Benefits derived when considering citizen science as a hobby.	Q6_3
BEN_PROF	Benefits related to new professional/career opportunities.	Q6_4
BEN_ENV	Benefits related to society and/or natural environment.	Q6_5
BAR_SKILLS	Lack of skills	Q10_1
BAR_TECH	Lack of technical equipment	Q10_2
BAR_INCL	Lack of inclusion	Q10_3

BAR_GUID	Lack of guidance	Q10_4
BAR_PART	Lack of participation	Q10_5
BAR_TRUST	Lack of trust	Q10_6
BAR_WORTH	Lack of contribution's worth	Q10_7
BAR_TIME	Lack of time	Q10_8
BAR_FIN	Lack of financial incentives	Q10_9
BAR_INTER	Lack of interest	Q10_10
BAR_COOP	Lack of cooperation	Q10_11
BAR_ORG	Lack of organization	Q10_12
DR_FEED	Continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project	Q12_1
DR_ACKN	Acknowledgement of the contribution (e.g., certificate, monetary rewards, public acknowledgment)	Q12_2
DR_ORGAN	The project is well-organized and managed	Q12_3
DR_INSPIRE	Inspiring coordination team	Q12_4
DR_GUIDE	Clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks	Q12_5
GENDER	Dummy variable for gender (1 if female, 0 otherwise)	Q16
AGE	Age group	Q17
EDU	Educational level	Q19
ACADEMIA	Dummy variable for being academic type stakeholder	Q3
STUDENT	Dummy variable for being a student	Q20
INCOME	Income level	Q21

The analysis that follows tries to shed light on the specific factors that are significant for general public perceptions and willingness to participate in citizen science projects. In this Annex, we present the detail findings of our analysis in the form of tables, indicating the significance of each factor. Four different groups of models have been estimated, focusing on the benefits, barriers, drivers and variations between the different stakeholder groups for citizen science perceptions and involvement. In the first three cases, we have performed the analysis at a pilot level to investigate differences between our four pilot countries, whilst variations between the various stakeholder types have been explored using our dataset as a whole. In the latter case, we did not perform the analysis at a country level due to the lack of adequate number of observations for each stakeholder group within each country dataset.

Benefits, barriers and drivers for the four pilot countries

Table A2 presents our results regarding the factors acting as significant benefits for promoting a positive attitude towards citizen science initiatives. As we can see, individual benefits and benefits related to skills' development and the environment are statistically significant in all countries, whereas benefits related to professional opportunities are related to lower positive perceptions for participants coming from Greece. A similar pattern can also be observed for the case we investigate the willingness to be involved in citizen science projects. Taking a closer look at the independent variables of our model, we can see that familiarity with terms related to citizen science relates to increased positive perceptions in all countries, whilst being a woman positively affects involvement in these initiatives in Lithuania and Spain.

Table A3 shows the corresponding findings regarding a set of potential factors acting as barriers to citizen science initiatives. For Greece, we can see that lower levels of overall perceptions are associated to sceptical attitudes about cooperating with other stakeholder groups and fear of lack of proper organization and management. When it comes to actual involvement, our findings indicate that lack of the necessary skills and knowledge, low participation rate and time are three additional factors that emerge as barriers for participants in Greece.

In the case of Lithuania, lower levels of overall perception are related to lack of the technological equipment that might be required (e.g., personal computer, smartphone, internet access) and low participation rates, whilst persons who think that they lack time for participating in these initiatives indicate better attitude towards them. Moreover, we can see that the role of these barriers is reversed when it comes to willingness to be involved in citizen science. In addition, fear that the contribution might lead to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions and lack of financial incentives are two additional barriers for persons who would like to participate in those initiatives. On the contrary, persons who are not so willing to participate in citizen science initiatives think of lack of time and proper organization/management as barriers and are sceptical about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.

Lack of the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities together with a lack of trust on the ways in which the inputs will be used for scientific purposes are received as significant barriers for participants who are positive towards citizen science from the Netherlands, whilst fear of harmful contributions, lack of time and organization/management are the main barriers for persons who do not indicate positive attitudes towards citizen science initiatives. When it comes to willingness to be involved, lack of inclusion is a significant barrier for people who want to participate, whereas lack of time, cooperation and fear of harmful contributions are the main barriers for those persons who do not indicate high levels of willingness to be involved.

For the case of Spain, lack of skills act as barriers for the persons with increased positive perceptions, whereas lack of inclusion and cooperation between the various stakeholder groups significantly affect persons with low levels of positive perceptions. In terms of willingness to participate, people who want to be involved in citizen science are affected by low participation and lack of trust to the institutions who are responsible for running those initiatives, whilst significant factors that relate to low levels of involvement include lack of the technological equipment that might be required, lack of time, lack of interesting research topics, lack of cooperation and fear of harmful contributions.

Table A4 presents our findings regarding the factors that act as drivers. As we can see, receiving continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project and having clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks are two factors that are essential for improving overall perceptions about citizen science in all countries. The first one, also applies as a driver for increasing willingness to participate in relevant initiatives. The project being well-organized and managed is significant for participants from Lithuania, whilst participants from Greece with low levels of

willingness to be involved have stressed that receiving appropriate acknowledgements for their contributions (e.g., certificate, monetary rewards, public acknowledgment) might act as a driver. This factor also works as a driver for the Netherlands for persons who are already willing to participate in citizen science projects.

Benefits, barriers and drivers based on different stakeholder types

Our analysis also aims to shed light on the factors affecting the various types of stakeholders towards being involved in citizen science projects. **Tables A5-A7** present the detailed statistical analysis results for all cases. As we can see, benefits related to the environment are statistically significant in all types of stakeholders (**Table A5**), whereas benefits referring to skills development apply in all cases except participants coming from the public sector. Professional benefits seem to affect stakeholders coming from the academia and industry.

In terms of identified barriers (**Table A6**), lack of inclusion, cooperation between various groups of stakeholders, organizational aspects and lack of time are the ones that are related to persons from academia who do not indicate high levels of positive perceptions and intention to participate in citizen science projects. Lack of cooperation has also been spotted as a barrier by public sector participants with low levels of positive attitude towards citizen sciences, whereas lack of guidance and lack of trust are two aspects that policymakers with positive attitudes think should be improved. Participants from the industry sector feel cautious due to potential lack of the technological equipment that might be required (e.g., personal computer, smartphone, internet access) and guidance that might be missing from these initiatives, alongside lack of time and cooperation. When it comes to citizens, evidence suggest that almost all factors included in our model are statistically significant for their perceptions and willingness to join citizen science projects. Lack of skills, inclusion, trust, technological equipment and low participation rates mostly affect persons with positive perceptions on citizen science, whilst lack of technological equipment, guidance, recognition, cooperation, organization and time are the factors affecting mostly persons with low levels of citizen science acceptance.

Results shown in **Table A7** indicate that receiving continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the projects is essential for improving overall perceptions about citizen science across all types of stakeholders. At the same time, having clear guidelines and instructions on the tasks is a significant driver for participants coming from academia, public sector and general public. Business-oriented participants also seem to be motivated from citizen science initiatives that are well-organized and properly managed.

Table A2: OLS results for the factors acting as significant benefits for citizen science overall perception and willingness to participate in citizen science initiatives, per pilot country.

DV IVs	Overall perception				Willingness to be involved			
	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
FAM	0.163 ***	0.160 ***	0.037	-0.059	0.037	-0.059	0.130 ***	0.061
PREV_EXP	0.132	0.093	0.170	0.140	0.170	0.140	-0.006	0.211 *
SOCIAL_SC	-0.128	0.208 **	0.124	0.283 **	0.124	0.283 **	0.167 *	0.051
LIFE_SC	0.007	-0.013	0.217 *	0.204 **	0.217 *	0.204	0.233 **	0.203 *
STEM	0.029	0.114	0.155	0.295 **	0.155	0.295 **	-0.028	0.204 **
BEN_IND	0.106 *	0.094	0.131 **	0.165	0.131 **	0.165	0.254 ***	0.064
BEN_SKILL	0.277 ***	0.247 ***	0.224 ***	-0.082	0.224 ***	-0.082	0.272 ***	0.217 ***
BEN_HOBBY	-0.008	0.027	-0.029	0.042	-0.029	0.042	-0.032	0.001
BEN_PROF	-0.108 **	0.025	0.092 *	0.237 ***	0.092 *	0.237 ***	0.105 **	0.105 **
BEN_ENV	0.287 ***	0.447 ***	0.192 ***	0.204 *	0.192 ***	0.204 *	0.171 ***	0.239 ***
GENDER	-0.067	-0.021	-0.003	0.496 ***	-0.003	0.496 ***	-0.015	0.148 *
AGE	-0.040	-0.021	-0.026	-0.064	-0.026	-0.064	0.013	-0.015
EDU	-0.004	-0.025	-0.084	0.053	-0.084	0.053	0.024	0.080 *
ACADEMIA	0.132	-0.054	0.039	0.021	0.039	0.021	-0.012	-0.061
STUDENT	0.029	0.095	-0.197	-0.226	-0.197	-0.226	0.028	-0.189 *
INCOME	-0.076	0.044	0.022	-0.124	0.022	-0.124	-0.017	-0.122 *
CONST	1.553 ***	0.140	1.612 ***	1.553 ***	1.612 ***	1.553 ***	0.068	1.034 ***
Observations	278	305	613	580	278	305	613	580
Prob.	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Adj-R2	0.3554	0.7877	0.5427	0.3829	0.2880	0.4287	0.3421	0.2330

Source: Authors' calculations

Table A3: OLS results for the factors acting as significant barriers for citizen science overall perception and willingness to participate in citizen science initiatives, per pilot country.

DV IVs	Overall perception				Willingness to be involved			
	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain	Greece	Lithuania	Netherlands	Spain
FAM	0.208 ***	0.414 ***	0.246 ***	0.221 ***	0.081	0.186 ***	0.230 ***	0.124 ***
PREV_EXP	0.212	0.284 **	0.135	0.125	0.201	0.219	0.020	0.279 **
SOCIAL_SC	-0.033	0.661 ***	0.117 *	0.102	0.090	0.661 ***	0.357 ***	0.119
LIFE_SC	0.127	0.322 **	0.176 **	0.207 **	0.183	0.367 **	0.337 ***	0.180
STEM	0.116	0.274 *	0.169 **	0.246 **	0.142	0.375 **	0.149	0.253 **
BAR_SKILLS	-0.039	0.025	0.072 **	0.073 **	-0.092 *	-0.073	0.042	0.025
BAR_TECH	-0.016	-0.116 *	-0.030	0.009	0.092	0.122 *	0.008	-0.068 *
BAR_INCL	-0.054	0.067	0.009	-0.072 **	-0.035	-0.026	0.115 ***	0.019
BAR_GUID	0.001	0.038	0.008	-0.005	0.014	-0.037	0.071	-0.005
BAR_PART	-0.009	-0.135 *	0.015	0.062	-0.112 **	0.075	0.009	0.191 ***
BAR_TRUST	0.011	0.067	0.107 ***	0.058	0.043	0.092	0.032	0.111 **
BAR_WORTH	-0.019	-0.096	-0.077 **	-0.002	0.047	0.164 *	-0.097 *	-0.064 *
BAR_TIME	0.020	0.133 *	-0.094 ***	-0.022	-0.219 ***	-0.125 *	-0.327 ***	-0.225 ***
BAR_FIN	-0.061	-0.042	0.027	0.028	-0.052	0.121 *	-0.062	0.039
BAR_INTER	0.064	-0.035	0.014	-0.051	-0.038	-0.209 **	-0.015	-0.139 ***
BAR_COOP	-0.131 ***	-0.128	-0.009	-0.116 ***	-0.115 **	-0.220 ***	-0.113 **	-0.089 **
BAR_ORG	-0.102 **	-0.054	-0.113 ***	-0.057	0.050	0.097	0.098 *	0.016
GENDER	0.048	0.158	-0.010	0.011	0.058	0.481 ***	-0.006	0.131 *
AGE	-0.068	-0.105 **	0.017	-0.021	-0.095 **	-0.146 ***	-0.016	-0.066 *
EDU	-0.078	0.127	0.009	-0.037	-0.117 *	0.180 **	-0.012	0.071
ACADEMIA	0.095	-0.010	0.032	0.025	0.034	0.053	-0.030	-0.105
STUDENT	0.039	0.137	0.056	-0.035	-0.281 *	-0.269	0.087	-0.154
INCOME	-0.081	-0.190 **	0.057	-0.115	0.077	-0.215 **	0.069	-0.102
CONST	4.759 ***	2.982 ***	2.817 ***	3.698 ***	5.402 ***	2.524 ***	3.233 ***	3.752 ***
Observations	278	305	613	580	278	305	613	580
Prob.	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Adj-R2	0.1974	0.5192	0.3019	0.1146	0.2274	0.3077	0.2760	0.2263

Source: Authors' calculations

Table A4: OLS results for the factors acting as significant benefits for citizen science overall perception and willingness to participate in citizen science initiatives, per pilot country.

DV	Overall perception								Willingness to be involved							
IVs	Greece		Lithuania		Netherlands		Spain		Greece		Lithuania		Netherlands		Spain	
FAM	0.259	***	0.496	***	0.186	***	0.203	***	0.139	***	0.097	*	0.174	***	0.139	***
PREV_EXP	0.186		0.162		0.152	**	0.033		0.131		0.137		0.099		0.173	
SOCIAL_SC	-0.076		0.721	***	0.066		0.033		0.196		0.494	***	0.250	***	0.017	
LIFE_SC	0.051		0.293	*	0.198	***	0.161	*	0.250	*	0.350	**	0.367	***	0.188	*
STEM	0.037		0.295	*	0.099		0.180	**	0.165		0.314	**	0.021		0.194	**
DR_FEED	0.182	**	-0.059		0.153	***	0.157	***	0.356	***	0.373	***	0.450	***	0.382	***
DR_ACKN	-0.079	*	-0.043		-0.009		-0.023		-0.169	***	0.042		0.119	***	-0.013	
DR_ORGAN	-0.066		0.217	*	0.010		0.093		-0.066		0.053		-0.048		0.081	
DR_INSPIRE	0.049		-0.021		0.038		0.085		0.079		0.174		0.030		0.053	
DR_GUIDE	0.140	*	0.238	*	0.144	***	0.217	***	0.037		-0.115		0.048		0.179	***
GENDER	-0.010		-0.038		-0.022		0.005		0.100		0.432	***	-0.012		0.147	*
AGE	-0.107	**	-0.109	**	0.018		-0.039		-0.123	**	0.108	**	0.005		0.069	*
EDU	-0.049		0.135		0.005		-0.052		-0.137	**	0.175	**	-0.012		0.076	*
ACADEMIA	0.147		0.012		0.032		0.024		0.019		0.038		-0.034		-0.121	
STUDENT	-0.068		0.285		-0.030		-0.046		-0.324	**	0.014		-0.048		-0.181	
INCOME	0.016		-0.079		0.034		-0.037		0.103		-0.192	**	0.009		0.032	
CONST	2.759	***	0.329		1.640	***	1.471	***	2.958	***	0.942	**	0.537	**	0.492	
Observations	278		305		613		580		278		305		613		580	
Prob.	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000	
Adj-R2	0.1702		0.5161		0.3773		0.2147		0.1614		0.3680		0.3380		0.2658	

Source: Authors' calculations

Table A5: OLS results for the factors acting as significant benefits for citizen science overall perception and willingness to participate in citizen science initiatives, per pilot country.

DV	Overall perception				Willingness to be involved			
IVs	Academia/ Research	Public sector	Industry	Citizens & civil society	Academia/ Research	Public sector	Industry	Citizens & civil society
FAM	0.134 ***	0.090 *	0.183 ***	0.127 ***	0.071 *	0.017	0.094	0.088 **
PREV_EXP	0.011	0.067	0.087	0.099	0.096	0.005	0.046	0.187
SOCIAL_SC	-0.056	-0.013	0.082	0.047	0.099	0.296 **	-0.042	0.232 ***
LIFE_SC	0.022	0.113	0.104	-0.098 *	0.112	0.348 *	0.542 ***	0.265 ***
STEM	0.020	0.199	0.119	0.005	0.160	0.408 **	0.303 **	0.165 *
BEN_IND	0.130 ***	0.114	0.175 ***	0.170 ***	-0.001	0.087	0.150 *	0.192 ***
BEN_SKILL	0.267 ***	0.051	0.255 ***	0.359 ***	0.332 ***	-0.010	0.244 ***	0.138 **
BEN_HOBBY	0.026	-0.029	0.014	0.044 **	-0.018	-0.024	-0.016	-0.039
BEN_PROF	-0.077 **	-0.064	0.138 **	-0.034	0.128 ***	0.066	0.107	0.089 *
BEN_ENV	0.364 ***	0.563 ***	0.176 ***	0.290 ***	0.239 ***	0.386 ***	0.221 **	0.183 ***
GENDER	-0.129 **	0.168 *	0.005	-0.006	0.123	0.051	0.153	0.162 **
AGE	-0.005	0.028	0.035	-0.003	0.040	0.053	-0.019	-0.058 **
EDU	-0.013	-0.028	-0.107 **	-0.059 **	0.034	0.021	0.155 **	0.126 ***
ACADEMIA	-0.104	-0.072	-0.249	0.030	0.116	-0.143	-0.352	0.051
STUDENT	-0.113	0.426 *	-0.323	0.048	-0.059	-0.177	0.167	-0.118
INCOME	-0.059	-0.009	-0.101	-0.002	-0.034	-0.019	-0.229 ***	-0.110 *
CONST	1.123 ***	0.885 **	0.849 ***	0.493 ***	0.721 **	1.287 **	0.540	1.093 ***
Observations	475	189	337	800	475	189	337	800
Prob.	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Adj-R2	0.4205	0.5226	0.5841	0.6595	0.2989	0.2634	0.3999	0.3550

Source: Authors' calculations

Table A6: OLS results for the factors acting as significant barriers for citizen science overall perception and willingness to participate in citizen science initiatives, per stakeholder group.

DV	Overall perception				Willingness to be involved			
IVs	Academia/ Research	Public sector	Industry	Citizens & civil society	Academia/ Research	Public sector	Industry	Citizens & civil society
FAM	0.231 ***	0.304 ***	0.396 ***	0.330 ***	0.171 ***	0.158 **	0.257 ***	0.196 ***
PREV_EXP	0.017	0.059	0.057	0.158	0.077	0.029	0.006	0.244 **
SOCIAL_SC	-0.009	0.072	0.188	0.194 ***	0.151	0.345 **	0.119	0.304 ***
LIFE_SC	0.127	0.272	-0.080	0.038	0.218 *	0.569 ***	0.240	0.272 ***
STEM	0.168	0.316 *	0.049	0.128	0.187	0.470 ***	0.292 **	0.181 *
BAR_SKILLS	0.010	0.033	0.081	0.069 **	0.037	0.071	0.027	-0.022
BAR_TECH	0.012	-0.011	-0.092 **	-0.066 **	-0.040	0.006	0.006	0.062 *
BAR_INCL	-0.096 **	-0.045	0.080 *	0.087 ***	-0.032	-0.017	0.054	-0.018
BAR_GUID	0.091 **	-0.082	-0.135 **	-0.127 ***	0.030	0.167 **	-0.110	0.060
BAR_PART	0.022	0.031	0.084	-0.002	0.035	-0.052	0.203 ***	0.094 **
BAR_TRUST	0.024	0.029	0.004	0.126 ***	0.050	0.262 ***	0.047	0.093 **
BAR_WORTH	0.002	0.020	-0.065	-0.112 ***	0.097	0.006	-0.037	-0.133 ***
BAR_TIME	0.015	0.028	-0.032	-0.041	-0.176 ***	-0.123	-0.300 ***	-0.317 ***
BAR_FIN	-0.011	0.053	-0.005	0.026	-0.050	-0.074	0.052	0.038
BAR_INTER	-0.034	-0.030	0.019	-0.004	-0.080 *	-0.030	-0.098	-0.100 **
BAR_COOP	-0.092 **	-0.176 **	-0.117 **	-0.137 ***	-0.149 ***	-0.263 ***	-0.054	-0.104 **
BAR_ORG	-0.120 ***	-0.045	0.003	-0.106 ***	0.091 **	0.071	0.045	0.057
GENDER	-0.040	0.173	0.095	0.077	0.138	-0.012	0.237 **	0.214 ***
AGE	-0.035	0.006	-0.047	-0.040 **	-0.091 **	0.033	-0.110 **	-0.102 ***
EDU	0.006	-0.049	-0.228 ***	-0.068 *	0.059	0.051	0.042	0.100 **
ACADEMIA	0.137	0.074	0.084	-0.006	0.012	-0.005	-0.111	0.014
STUDENT	0.137	0.301	-0.427	-0.031	0.070	-0.306	0.241	-0.143
INCOME	0.005	-0.040	-0.186 **	-0.020	-0.018	-0.010	-0.241 ***	-0.120 **
CONST	3.717 ***	3.387 ***	4.255 ***	3.895 ***	3.492 ***	2.613 ***	3.829 ***	3.848 ***
Observations	475	189	337	800	475	189	337	800
Prob.	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Adj-R2	0.1470	0.1924	0.3410	0.3870	0.1637	0.2087	0.2980	0.3175

Source: Authors' calculations

Table A7: OLS results for the factors acting as significant benefits for citizen science overall perception and willingness to participate in citizen science initiatives, per stakeholder group.

DV	Overall perception				Willingness to be involved			
IVs	Academia/ Research	Public sector	Industry	Citizens & civil society	Academia/ Research	Public sector	Industry	Citizens and civil society
FAM	0.208 ***	0.247 ***	0.382 ***	0.368 ***	0.128 ***	0.102 *	0.253 ***	0.191 ***
PREV_EXP	0.024	-0.012	0.139	0.165	0.028	-0.025	0.114	0.228 **
SOCIAL_SC	-0.086	0.120	0.104	0.155 **	0.114	0.391 ***	-0.023	0.210 ***
LIFE_SC	0.051	0.177	-0.043	-0.042	0.171	0.388 **	0.420 ***	0.209 **
STEM	0.052	0.268 *	0.005	-0.058	0.147	0.447 ***	0.224 *	0.029
DR_FEED	0.141 **	0.162 *	0.145 *	0.224 ***	0.353 ***	0.362 ***	0.338 ***	0.511 ***
DR_ACKN	-0.028	-0.029	-0.037	-0.113 ***	0.085 **	0.051	-0.040	0.009
DR_ORGAN	0.021	0.129	0.253 ***	0.075	0.010	-0.004	0.137	0.019
DR_INSPIRE	0.086	-0.030	0.002	0.005	0.127 **	0.176 *	0.015	0.013
DR_GUIDE	0.150 **	0.303 ***	0.093	0.206 ***	0.152 **	0.057	0.129	0.037
GENDER	-0.066	0.067	0.128	0.006	0.147 *	-0.083	0.275 ***	0.146 **
AGE	-0.046	0.015	-0.051	-0.022	-0.103 ***	0.031	-0.090 **	-0.060 **
EDU	-0.010	-0.013	0.260 ***	-0.169 ***	0.001	0.032	0.011	0.063
ACADEMIA	0.133	0.072	0.175 **	-0.055	-0.012	-0.027	0.030	-0.057
STUDENT	-0.010	0.409	-0.442 *	-0.023	0.096	-0.022	0.066	-0.049
INCOME	0.049	-0.083	-0.072	0.038	0.064	-0.039	-0.186 **	-0.051
CONST	1.999 ***	0.889 *	1.816 ***	1.615 ***	1.130 ***	0.559	0.919 **	0.720 ***
Observations	475	189	337	800	475	189	337	800
Prob.	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Adj-R2	0.1804	0.319	0.4084	0.3766	0.2357	0.2833	0.3311	0.3842

Source: Authors' calculations

Annex D: Survey questionnaire

[Welcome note](#)

Dear participant, welcome to our survey!

The survey lasts **about 10-15 minutes**. There are no right or wrong answers, this is only about your personal views. All data will be anonymised, and your privacy is guaranteed.

Thank you for helping us gather relevant information!

[What is the INCENTIVE project?](#)

INCENTIVE is an EU-funded Horizon 2020 project (GA no. 101005330) which aims to foster the design of inclusive and sustainable research and innovation through the establishment of Citizen Science Hubs in four European universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

The objectives of INCENTIVE are threefold:

- (1) bring citizens, public administration and private sector closer to the research community;
- (2) demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs in the participating universities;
- (3) provide practices, methods, and tools that will navigate and support other research institutions across Europe to create and operate their own Citizen Science Hubs;

With this survey, we aim at collecting information regarding perceptions, opinions, needs and factors shaping the willingness of people to actively participate in the Citizen Science Hubs.

[Informed consent](#)

This privacy policy details information collection practises related to your personal data and other related information and the limited manner in which the INCENTIVE project will use and disclose the information provided to us when you responded the survey.

If you have any questions concerning this privacy policy or our data collection practises you may contact us at info@incentive-project.eu. We reserve the right to change this privacy policy

at any time and inform all participants about the updates.

In addition to your opinion, we are collecting some personal information such as age, country of residence and educational status for socio-demographic purposes. The collected data will be saved and used until the end of the research period of the INCENTIVE project (31/01/2024). The data will be only used for the purpose of the INCENTIVE project, funded under the European Union Horizon 2020 programme.

The lawfulness of the processing of personal data is determined pursuant to Article 6 of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). With respect to personal data, the processing of personal data is based on consent. White Research will be responsible for accessing and processing the data.

"By participating in the survey, I voluntarily consent to the collection and use of my information by INCENTIVE as set forth in this privacy policy."

Introduction to the topic

Q1. To what extent are you familiar with the following terms? (1 = Not at all familiar; 2 = Slightly Familiar; 3 = Somewhat familiar; 4 = Moderately familiar; 5 = Extremely Familiar)

To ensure that all participants have a common understanding of the terminology used in the survey, the definition of each term is briefly provided below. We invite you to read the definitions before answering the survey's questions.

	1	2	3	4	5
Q1_1. – Citizen Science Citizen science refers to the active engagement of the general public in scientific research tasks of several disciplines (from natural sciences to social sciences and humanities) and the collaborative production of new knowledge.					
Q1_2. – Responsible Research and Innovation Responsible Research and Innovation is an approach that anticipates and assesses potential implications and societal expectations with regard to research and innovation, with the aim to foster the design of inclusive and sustainable research and innovation.					
Q1_3. – Open science Open science refers to a process where researchers share knowledge and data as early as possible in the research process with all relevant actors with the aim diffuse the latest knowledge to as many people as possible. It is related to the concept of open access.					
Q1_4. – Co-creation Co-creation refers to the active involvement of end-users and stakeholders in the design process and is interwoven with concepts such as "co-production", "public participation", "collaborative governance" and "community involvement".					

Q2_1. Do you have any experience with citizen science?

- Yes
- No

Q2_2. Please specify the type of experience (if yes):

Please select one option.

- I have heard the term citizen science
- I have an acquaintance/friend who is involved in a citizen science project
- I have participated myself in a citizen science project
- I have initiated and/or designed myself a citizen science project
- Other

Q2_3. (Other) Could you please specify the type of experience? (max. 200 characters)

Q3. In which of the following groups do you belong?

(please select one answer)

- Academia / Research
- Public administration
- Private sector/ Industry
- Civil society (e.g., NGOs, environmental or civic associations, etc.)
- General public

Q4. Do you have academic/practical knowledge or working experience (e.g., university degree, extra-curricular activities, hobbies, et.) on any of the following scientific fields?

(up to two options can be selected)

- Social sciences, arts and humanities (history, law, linguistics, economics, sociology, psychology, political sciences, philosophy, etc.)
- Life and health sciences (medicine, biology, ecology, zoology, botany, earth science etc.)
- STEM (science, technology, engineering, mathematics, computer science etc.)
- I do not have any knowledge in science

Perceptions

Please indicate your agreement with the following statement [1=Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neither agree nor disagree; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly agree]

	1	2	3	4	5
Q5. My overall perception of:					
Q5.1. Citizen science is positive.					
Q5.2. The collaboration between scientists and citizens is positive.					
Q5.3. Citizen science has limited potential.					
Q5_4. Current scientific and innovation policies is positive.					

Q6. Participation in citizen science:					
Q6_1. Will provide benefits to me (economic, social, educational).					
Q6_2. Will improve my knowledge and skills.					
Q6_3. Is something that I consider as a hobby.					
Q6_4. Will open up new professional/career opportunities.					
Q6_5. Will have a positive impact on society and/or natural environment.					

Q7. I would like Citizen Science Hubs* to:					
*A Citizen Science Hub is a scientific organisation (or part of a scientific organisation) with the purpose to initiate, execute, promote and coordinate participatory Research and Innovation (R&I) with and for citizens. As such, it brings together the scientific community with external stakeholders.					
Q7_1. Act as open places for discussion about scientific progress and societal challenges					
Q7_2. Enhance soft and technical skills and improve citizens' understanding of scientific knowledge					
Q7_3. Empower citizens to become more actively involved in science and initiate their own citizen science projects					
Q7_4. Involve vulnerable groups (e.g., migrants, minorities, elderly, people with disabilities, etc).					

Q8. I believe/feel that:					
Q8_1. Traditional scientific policies and research do not suffice to deal with current challenges					
Q8_2. Both scientists and citizens can benefit significantly and mutually from citizen science.					
Q8_3. Citizen science is increasingly acknowledged at the policy level					
Q8_4. Citizen science provides opportunity for greater public engagement and democratisation and inclusiveness of science					

Q9. In my opinion, citizens:					
Q9_1. Should have an active role in the design and execution of scientific projects.					
Q9_2. Lack the knowledge and skills to be part of the scientific					

process.					
Q9_3. Need to be trained in order to participate in science.					

Barriers

Please indicate your agreement with the following statement (1=Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neither agree nor disagree; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly agree)

	1	2	3	4	5
Q10. Regarding my participation in citizen science, I am concerned about the following:					
Q10_1. I lack the necessary skills and knowledge to be involved in such activities.					
Q10_2. I lack the technological equipment that might be required (e.g., personal computer, smartphone, internet access).					
Q10_3. I belong to a sociodemographic group that is underrepresented in the scientific community (e.g., in a vulnerable group).					
Q10_4. I will not receive the necessary guidelines and feedback during the project.					
Q10_5. I am worried that there will be low participation rate.					
Q10_6. I don't know how my contribution will be exploited by scientists/policy makers.					
Q10_7. I am afraid my contribution might lead to wrong or harmful scientific or policy decisions.					
Q10_8. I do not have the time to participate in such activities.					
Q10_9. I lack financial incentives to participate.					
Q10_10. I am afraid that I will find the research topic not interesting enough					
Q10_11. I am sceptical about cooperating with other stakeholder groups.					
Q10_12. I am afraid that the project will not be properly organised and managed.					
Q10_13. Other – Please specify: (max. 200 characters)					

Drivers

Please indicate your agreement with the following statement (1=Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neither agree nor disagree; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly agree)

	1	2	3	4	5
Q11. I would participate in a citizen science project to:					
Q11_1. Fulfil my personal interest and curiosity for the scientific field of the project					
Q11_2. Express my personal values, ideas and creativity					
Q11_3. Gain knowledge and learn new technical skills					
Q11_4. Feel useful to scientific research					
Q11_5. Extend my professional network and enhance my career					
Q11_6. Meet new people with common interests					
Q11_7. Gain financial rewards					
Q11_8. Be part of a community and commit to a common cause that benefits society/natural environment					

Q12. When participating in a citizen science project it is important that:					
Q12_1. I receive continuous feedback and updates about the progress of the project					
Q12_2. My contribution is properly acknowledged (e.g., certificate, monetary rewards, public acknowledgment)					
Q12_3. The project is well-organised and managed					
Q12_4. The coordination team can inspire me					
Q12_5. I have clear guidelines and instructions on my tasks					
Q12_6. Other – Please specify: (max. 200 characters)					

Willingness to join

Please indicate your agreement with the following statement (1=Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Neither agree nor disagree; 4=Agree; 5=Strongly agree)

Q13. I would:	1	2	3	4	5
Q13_1. Like to be involved in citizen science activities.					
Q13_2. Encourage people from my friends and family to get involved in citizen science activities.					
Q13_3. Like to be involved in the creation of my local Citizen Science Hub.					

Q13_4. Be interested in initiating and/or leading a citizen science project in my Citizen Science Hub.					
--	--	--	--	--	--

Q14_1. What topics would you be interested in, in relation to a citizen science project? (up to three options can be selected):

- Energy & Sustainability
- Circular Economy
- Transport & Mobility
- Health
- Educational sciences
- Human media interaction
- Public administration and policy
- Communication sciences
- Environmental Sciences
- Information Technologies
- Other

Q14_2. (Other) Please specify: (max. 200 characters)

Q15_1. In which stage of the research process would you like to be involved? (up to three options can be selected)

- Identify a research question
- Design a study
- Collect data
- Analyse data
- Interpret results and write reports
- Exploit research outcomes
- Other

Q15_2. (Other) Please specify: (max. 200 characters)

General Information

Q16. Gender:

- Female

- Male
- Non-binary
- Other
- I prefer not to answer

Q17. What is your age?

- Under 20 years
- 20-29 years
- 30-39 years
- 40-49 years
- 50-59 years
- 60+ years

Q18_1. In which country do you live?

- The Netherlands
- Spain
- Greece
- Lithuania
- Other

Q18_2. (Other) Please specify: (max. 200 characters)

Q19. What is the highest level of education you have attended?

- Less than a High School Diploma
- High School Diploma
- Bachelor's Degree or equivalent
- Master's Degree or equivalent
- PhD or equivalent

Q20. What is your occupational status?

- Employed
- Unemployed
- Self-employed/entrepreneur
- Student
- Household activity
- Retired
- Other

Q21. How would you classify the net household income of your family? (*optional*)

- Low income
- Medium income
- High income

Survey end

Thank you for taking part in this survey and contributing to our understanding of the factors that can enable or hinder participation of citizens in Citizen Science Hubs.

Your input will help us a great deal to identify key elements and perceptions that should be considered during the implementation of our project.

Do you have any questions or comments? You can contact us at info@incentive-project.eu.

Feel free to follow the INCENTIVE social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) for more information!

Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/INCENTIVEproje1>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/76793163/>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/incentiveH2020>

ABOUT THE PROJECT

INCENTIVE aims to demonstrate the potential of citizen science through the co-creation, establishment and assessment of Citizen Science Hubs in four EU Universities: University of Twente (NL), Autonomous University of Barcelona (ES), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (EL) and Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (LT).

By doing so, the project accelerates the transition of these institutions to more inclusive, open and democratic innovation and scientific governance, under the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation. The project seeks to deliver a legacy to European and international research institutes on how to create and operate their own Hub with the aim to secure a sustainable future.

COORDINATOR

UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE (DesignLab)

PARTNERS

UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE (DesignLab)
www.utwente.nl/en/designlab

UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA
www.uab.es

ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS
www.auth.gr

VILNIAUS GEDIMINO TECHNIKOS UNIVERSITETAS
vilniustech.lt

UNIVERSITAT ZURICH
www.uzh.ch

UNIVERSITA COMMERCIALE LUIGI BOCCONI
www.unibocconi.eu

Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS
qplan-intl.gr

WHITE RESEARCH SRL
white-research.eu

VEREIN DER EUROPAEISCHEN BURGERWISSENSCHAFTEN – ECSA
ecsa.citizen-science.net

CONTACT US

info@incentive-project.eu

- [incentive-project](#)
- [incentiveH2020](#)
- [incentive-project](#)
- [incentive_eu](#)

